

**Shareholders Perception on Corporate Governance Implementation in
Nigerian Commercial Banks**

A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of
Doctor of Business Administration

by

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Declaration

The thesis is an original work by the researcher and no part of this study has been submitted in support for an application for another degree of qualification in this university or any other higher institution of learning.

Dedication

I dedicate this thesis to my parents- Mr. Emmanuel Eze and in the memory and honour of my beloved mother (Felicia Eze) for their unwavering support and influence in shaping my aspirations and values. May God grant her eternal rest.

Above all, to the Almighty God for his strength and perseverance.

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ABSTRACT

The global economic meltdown of 2007/2008 which resulted in the collapse of many multimillion companies and recessions in both developed and developing economies, reinvigorated individual concerns on the need for accountability, disclosure, transparency in organisations and effective corporate governance implementation. The board of directors were charged with the role of controlling, monitoring and strategic planning in organisations. Consequently, this raised key concerns for board effectiveness to ensure corporate governance implementation and firm performance.

Therefore, this thesis examined the prevailing corporate governance challenges in Nigerian banks, the consequences of such challenges and ways to ensure proper corporate governance principles implementation. Most previous studies on corporate governance and board effectiveness, only independently examined the board characteristics without consulting the principal (shareholders) and agents (management) on the challenges that hampers board effectiveness. Though some corporate organisations complied to the requirements of corporate governance principles; they were still overwhelmed by scandals that led to company collapse. This thesis is not only examining board effectiveness in implementing corporate governance, but also, ascertaining the prevailing environmental challenges that might hamper corporate governance effectiveness in Nigerian commercial banks.

In addition, this thesis developed a framework — based on previous research works — on board effectiveness in developed and emerging economies. The framework examined the relationship between board characteristics and effective corporate governance implementation. The board characteristics examined in the framework includes board diversity, size, committees, leadership duality and board composition of executive and non-executive directors. It further examined prevailing factors that undermines effective implementation of corporate governance principles.

The thesis adopted qualitative method of data collection by conducting semi-structured interviews which created opportunity for an in-depth and detailed opinion and sentiments of the players and observers in the Nigerian commercial banks on challenges, effects, and possible solution to corporate governance implantation.

The findings show that factors like corruption, unethical practices, ownership structure, multiple board representation, lack of diversity and transparency as challenges facing effective corporate governance implementation and board effectiveness. The above-mentioned challenges, if not addressed, will not only undermine corporate governance implementation but company performance. Moreover, the findings indicate that diversity should go beyond gender inclusion and consider diversity based on skills, experience, and knowledge. The findings acknowledge the importance of diversity base on gender; however, competence should be prioritized. Furthermore, the findings identified the need for regular board training and seminars, adequate remuneration based on performance and favourable government policies through governmental institutions like the Central Banks.

This thesis contributes an instant and long-term solution in ensuring board effectiveness which will result to effective corporate governance implementation and company performance. The instant policy includes immediate review of the remuneration policy by organisations. On the other hand, the review of corporate governance codes by regulatory bodies by enacting codes that serve as a check on the board, and constant training of the board to be abreast with contemporary corporate governance practices and prevailing issues that might undermine their effectiveness. The framework and findings of this study will invigorate researchers in identifying other issues that might undermine board effectiveness and corporate governance implementation and comparative study on impact of ownership structure (disperse and concentrated) on corporate board effectiveness.

Table of Contents

Declaration	II
Dedication	III
Acknowledgement	IV
Abstract	V
Table of contents	VII
List of Figures	XII
List of Tables	XII
List of Abbreviation	XIII
1. Chapter 1: Introduction	
1.1 Background of Study	1
1.2 Aim and Objectives of the Research	5
1.2.1 Research Aim	5
1.2.2 Objectives of study	6
1.2.3 Research Questions	6
1.3 Research Problem	7
1.4 Research Gaps	9
1.5 Research Methodology	10
1.6 Outline of the thesis	12
1.7 Nature and Scope of the Research	13
1.8 Contribution of study	14
1.9 Conclusion	15
2. Chapter 2: Literature Review	16
2.0 Introduction	16
2.1 Contextual Literature	17
2.1.1 Nigerian Context	17
2.1.2 Nigerian Corporate governance	19
2.2.0 Conceptual Literature	21
2.2.1 Corporate Governance Models	21

2.3 Corporate Governance Models	22
2.3.1 The Anglo-Saxon Model	23
2.3.2 Continental European Model	26
2.3.3 The Anglo-Saxon and Continental European Models	28
2.3.4 Japanese Corporate Governance Model	29
2.4 Corporate Governance Theories	32
2.4.1 Agency theory and corporate board effectiveness	32
2.4.2 Stakeholder Theory and Board Effectiveness	34
2.4.3 Stewardship Theory and Board Effectiveness	36
2.4.4 Resource Dependency Theory and Board Effectiveness	39
2.4.5 Managerial Hegemony and Board Effectiveness	42
2.5 Corporate Governance Characteristics and Board Implementation	44
2.5.1 Non-Executive Directors	44
2.5.2 Board Size and corporate board effectiveness	46
2.5.3 Board Leadership and board effectiveness	50
2.5.4 Board diversity and board effectiveness	54
2.5.5 Institutional investors and board effectiveness	56
2.5.6 Audit Committee and board effectiveness	58
2.5.7 Remuneration Committee and Board Effectiveness	62
2.5.8 Ownership Structure and board effectiveness	63
2.6 Directors Over-boarding	65
2.7 Pension Fund and Board Effectiveness	66
2.8 Directors Remuneration and board effectiveness	68
2.9 Government influence on corporate board	69
2.10. Development of Conceptual Framework	80
2.10.1 Introduction	80
2.10.2 The Sharma Board Effectiveness Framework	80

2.10.3 Levrau and Van den Berghe Framework	83
2.11 Discussion of the research conceptual Framework	85
2.12 Conclusion	89
Chapter 3: Research Methodology and Design	90
3.0 Introduction	90
3.1 Research Philosophy	90
3.2 Research Approach	92
3.3 Research Methods	93
3.3.1 Introduction	93
3.3.2 Mono Method	94
3.4 Semi-Structured Interviews	96
3.5 Case Study Research	100
3.5.1 Multiple Case Study	100
3.6 Research Ethics	102
3.7 Reliability and Validity of Study	105
3.8 Time Horizon	106
3.9 Selection of Sample Size	107
3.10. Description of the case studies	111
3.10.1 Introduction	111
3.10.2 First bank Nigeria Limited	112
3.10.2.1 Corporate Governance in First Bank	112
3.10.3 Zenith Bank Plc	113
3.10.3.1 Corporate Governance in Zenith Bank Plc	114
3.10.4 Case Study 3: United Bank for Africa PLC (UBA)	115
3.10.4.1 UBA Plc Corporate Governance	116
3.10.5 Case Study 4: Fidelity Bank Plc	117
3.10.5.1 Fidelity Bank Plc Corporate Governance Code	118
3.10.6 Case Study 5: Union Bank of Nigeria Plc	120

3.10.6.1 Corporate Governance in the Union Bank of Nigeria	121
3.10.7 Summary	122
3.11 Data Analysis	125
3.11.1 Thematic Analysis	125
3.12 Pilot Study	128
3.13 conclusion	129
Chapter 4: Data Analysis and presentation	130
4.1 Introduction	130
4.2 Board structure and leadership issues	131
4.2.1 Lack of Corporate governance implementation	131
4.2.2 Unethical Leadership	134
4.3 Respective Shareholders interest challenges	137
4.4. Ownership Structure challenge in Nigeria Banks	141
4.5 Bank Distress and Bailout Fund	149
4.6 Multiple Board Representation and Bank Distress	153
4.7 Effective Corporate Governance in Nigerian Banks	156
4.8 Policy Implementation	157
4.9 Training, Seminars and Conferences	159
4.10 Conclusion	164
Chapter 5: Discussion of Findings	167
5.0 Introduction	167
5.1 Analysed Data in Relation to Research Objective 1	168
5.2 Analysed Data in Relation to Research Objective 2	172
5.2.1 Corporate Governance and Board Diversity	172
5.2.2 ownership structure Challenge	175
5.2.3 Issues of Bank Distress and Bailout Fund	176

5.2.4 Issues of Board Function	177
5.2.5 Challenges of Multiple Board Directorship	179
5.3. Analysed Data in Relation to Research Objective 3	182
5.3.1 Board Trainings and Seminars	183
5.3.2 Government Institutions and policies	186
5.3.3 Directors Remuneration and CG implementation	188
5.4 Summary of Discussion	190
Chapter 6: Recommendation, Contribution and Conclusion	191
6.0 Recommendations	191
6.1 Introduction	191
6.2.1 Government Policy in Nigerian Commercial Banks	192
6.2.2 Effective Board Training and Seminars	194
6.2.3 Remuneration Policy	196
6.2.4 Ownership and Control	198
6.2.5 Conclusion	199
6.3.0 Managerial Contribution	199
6.3.1 Contribution	199
6.4 Conceptual Model	201
6.5 Limitation of Study	203
6.6 Recommendations for Future Research	204
6.7 Conclusion	205
References	207
Appendices	227

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.1 Sharma Firm performance framework	83
Figure 2.2 Levrau and Van den Berghe Board Effectiveness of board Framework	85
Figure 2.3 Research Conceptual Framework	88
Figure 5.1 Minority investors protection	171
Figure 5.2 Sectors with highest number of non-performing loans in Nigeria	185
Figure 6.1 Directors Remuneration and board effectiveness	198
Figure 6.2 Conceptual model	202

LIST OF TABLES

Table 2.1. Themes from the literature	72
Table 3.1 Banks with local or international authorization (Case population)	109
Table 3.2 Nigerian commercial banks employed for the case study	110
Table 3.3 Portfolios and qualifications of interview participants	110
Table 3.4 Linking Objectives/Research Questions to Interview Questions	123
Table 3.5 Six-Steps of Thematic Analysis	127

List of Abbreviations

CG – Corporate Governance

CEO – Chief Executive Officer

AGM – Annual General Meeting

NSE – Nigerian Stock Exchange

SEC – Security and Exchange Commissions

CBN – Central Bank of Nigeria

BOFIA – Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act

OECD - Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

TA – Thematic Analysis

NED – NON-EXECUTIVE DIRECTOR

Chapter One

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background of Study

The revitalisation of interest on corporate governance and board effectiveness, both in private and public sectors resulted from scandals suffered by big organizations globally (Kartal, Ibis and Catikkas 2018; Mallin, 2016). Some of these notable organizations include Barings Bank, Enron, Paramat, RBS (Royal Bank of Scotland). Mallin (2016) argued that the corporate failures amounted to the need for review, amendment, and full implementation of the corporate governance codes, to eradicate reoccurrence of any future corporate scandal.

The aftermath of the enumerated scandals resulted in the development of several corporate governance codes and acts, which recommended panaceas to unravel challenges, including lack of board efficacy that resulted to several corporate failures. These codes include, Cadbury report (1992) Sarbanes-Oxley Act (2002), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2004) and Nigerian corporate governance code (2016). The Cadbury committee (1992) was among the first known committees that holistically addressed most of the issues surrounding corporate governance paucity, especially on how to enhance board effectiveness in organizations. According to the committee, they defined corporate governance as a *system by which companies are directed and controlled*. Corporate governance is also defined as ways the supplier of finance assures themselves of getting return on their investment (Shleifer and Vishny, 1997).

In Nigeria, measures were put in place to eradicate corporate failures through development of “code of corporate governance best practices” (2003) and lately, an updated version in 2016. The Nigerian corporate code (2013) recommended that the board should direct and appoint a qualified individual as the CEO to oversee daily operation of the firm (Kajola 2008). However, despite incorporation of corporate governance codes in Nigeria, addressing how companies should be directed and controlled; misfortunes have engulfed different companies as corporate scandals are yet to be nipped in the bud. This gave rise for the need to address, improve, and amend the existing corporate practices, which will consider the demography, political cum ethnic diversity of the country. This is to ensure that that the suppliers of finance (shareholders) and other stakeholders get back returns on their investments, enjoy necessary benefits associated to their stakes and enhance company performance.

Furthermore, Ehikioya (2009) argued that good corporate governance encompasses principles of transparency, accountability, responsibility, and fairness in carrying out the activities of the firm by the management. But lack of the good corporate governance has resulted to corporate failures and feud between the shareholders and management. The feud between shareholders and management exists where ownership and control are separated. Jensen and Meckling (1976) in other terms, referred the feud between shareholders and managers as Agent-Principal problem. This is where agents, also known as managers, oversees the day-to-day activities of the firm on behalf of the owners (principals). They noted that the agents do over time develop selfish interest to achieve personal economic gain, that do not align with the interest of the principals. Adeyemi (2011), found that lack of transparency by the board is one the biggest challenges that promoted bank failures. He therefore recommended that the post of Chairman and CEO should be

separated to achieve transparency, eradicate selfish interest of the directors, and enhance board effectiveness.

The economic meltdown of 2007/2008 plunged many multinational companies into financial crisis, including companies in both developed and developing economies. Sener, Varoglu and Aren (2011) argued that one the major reasons that resulted to the financial crisis is board of director's paucity in carrying out their directorial duties. This, therefore, gave rise for need to critically evaluate the roles and characteristics of board of directors and possible adjustment needed to enhance its effectiveness to achieve company performance. Müller (2014) noted that financial performance is paramount to the entire stakeholders, especially to the shareholders who contribute immensely to ensure that the business continue to exist in a foreseeable future. He noted that the board (executive and non-executive directors) is charged with the responsibility of carrying the activities of the firm. Therefore, the level of their effectiveness does not only enhance company performance but attract prospective investors. Isukul and Chizea (2015) expressed that lack of implementation of principles of corporate governance and corruption in Nigeria still hinders company performance.

The banking sector both in emerging and developed economies are entrusted with financial activities of entire economy. They are involved in lending, financing of agricultural programs, businesses, mortgages, and capital formation (Koko and Hassan, 2017). Since the banks are the life wire of any given economy, and virtually connected to most businesses, the need for it to be effectively managed arises.

The Nigerian banking sector over the years has experienced series of financial instability and crises in its operation, which has undermined its performance and credibility. Oboh and Ajibolade (2017) argued that the instability is caused by corruption and deficiency in its management. The Nigerian banks are highly regulated. The regulations include Bank and Other Financial Institution Act (BOFIA) 2007, Code of Corporate governance (2003), and lately Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria corporate governance code (2018), which recommends the composition of the board to achieve board effectiveness.

However, some of the policies of the government and political disruption have compromised the banking ethics and norms, which led to its deviation from the international standard (Koko and Hassan, 2017; Adeyemi, 2011; Sanusi 2010; Okpara, 2009). In most cases, these deficiencies and challenges have undermined the effectiveness of the board in the banking sector. Considering the importance of banks and roles it plays in any given economy, and consequences that might arise when it suffers any form of distress; the need for proactive measures to be taken comes in place. Thus, having an effective board can be a panacea to eliminate the corrupt practices and poor management found in this sector.

Beside other challenges already highlighted, lack of proper monitoring in the board, breach of fiduciary duty and insider trading by the directors were among identified prevailing issues that plunged some Nigerian banks into distress (Olukayode, 2017). To enhance board effectiveness, Pearce and Patel (2017) argued that there should be inclusion of outside directors (Non-Executive Directors) in the board to bring check and balances. They noted that executive directors can easily align with managers to accomplish selfish economic desires, whereas effective non-executive directors can bring proper monitoring to eliminate executive directors' selfish interest.

Other than board composition and characteristics, the presence of Institutional directors in the board is considered major factor that facilitates effectiveness of the board (Cleary and Wang, 2016). However, there are contradictory opinion on institutional investors' capability to effectively monitor board effectiveness as institutional investors in some cases do compel managers to satisfy their selfish interest against other stakeholders (Harford *et al.*, 2015).

Although a reasonable number of studies have researched on corporate governance and board effectiveness in the developed economy, limited works have been done in emerging economies like Nigeria. This research will, therefore, critically analyse board effectiveness in implementing corporate governance in Nigerian commercial banks, considering that banks are major players in supplying of funds for businesses and very necessary for economic growth.

1.2 Aim and Objectives of the Research

1.2.1 Research Aim

One of the most debated corporate governance mechanisms is the effect of presence of corporate board (Executive and non-executive directors) in achieving company performance. Most of the big organizations that have previously experienced corporate failure or scandals all had board of directors, yet their presence could not avert such corporate failures. The scandals could be attributed to a lack of effectiveness on the part of board of directors.

This thesis therefore aims to critically evaluate the effectiveness of board of directors in implementing good corporate governance practice in Nigerian banks. The evaluation will be

basically, from the shareholders point of view on the general issues surrounding corporate governance and board effectiveness. The shareholders include government, investors, insurance companies, pension fund and ordinary shareholders.

Moreover, different corporate governance model will be evaluated; models such as the continental European CG model, Anglo-Saxon CG model and Japanese CG model. These are different models that determines the type of CG being practiced in respective economies. The study will examine the contemporary challenges that hampers corporate governance implementation in Nigerian commercial banks. The study will further explore board characteristics, which includes the board size, diversity, leadership duality, board composition and board committees. These factors are among the militating factors that might undermine or underpin corporate board effectiveness and company performance. It will further examine different corporate governance theories as they help in understanding possible challenges and prospects of corporate governance and board effectiveness.

At the end of this thesis, there will be a recommendation on possible solutions to ensure proper CG implementation and board effectiveness.

1.2.2 Objectives of study

To achieve the general aims of the study, the following objectives were developed.

1. To critically evaluate the literature on the effective implementation of corporate governance codes in the Nigerian commercial banks.

2. To examine and understand the prevalent issues of corporate governance in Nigerian Banks.
3. To critically evaluate the influence of those corporate governance issues and how they affect corporate governance effectiveness in Nigerian banks.
4. To examine the process of implementing the suggested changes to enhance corporate governance effectiveness in Nigerian commercial banks.
5. To make recommendations on how to engage shareholders for effective implementation of corporate governance.

1.2.3 Research Questions

To critically evaluate the corporate board effectiveness in the Nigerian commercial banks, and make proper recommendations on how to enhance its effectiveness, the following research questions were developed:

1. What are the prevailing issues of corporate governance in Nigerian commercial banks?
2. What are the effects of these corporate governance issues on the current corporate governance regulations?
3. What are the appropriate ways to implement the findings?
4. What recommendations should be made on engaging the shareholders for effective corporate governance?

1.3 Research Problem

The global economic crisis of 2007/2008 led to the improvement of different corporate governance codes, which included the UK Corporate governance code (2016) and in United States, NYSE: Corporate Governance Guide (2014). The emerging economies also never relented, as corporate governance codes were developed in some of these countries to tackle such crisis and be abreast with other developed economies. In Nigeria, the Security and Exchange Commission developed corporate governance codes of 2008 in response to the global economic crises and King III code in South Africa.

Despite all the efforts to totally eradicate corporate scandals through theories and principles of corporate governance, a satisfactory achievement is yet to be attained as businesses still experience challenges, which has undermined company performance. Mallin (2016) identified paucity in the board as one of the notable factors that undermines company performance.

In Nigeria, the situation is not far from corporate failures happening elsewhere in the world, especially in the banking sectors. The now defunct Oceanic Bank is one of the biggest bank scandals of twenty-first century in Nigeria, which folded in 2010 leaving many people jobless and businesses connected to the bank liquidated. Recently, Sahara Reporters (2015) noted that up to nine banks are on the verge of being distressed in Nigeria, which is an effect of poorly performing loans and inability to maintain healthy capital liquidity. They also reported that some banks give loans without collateral.

Adeyemi (2011), in addressing bank scandals in Nigeria, highlighted some of the biggest challenges facing Nigerian banks. They include limited transparency, challenges of non-

performing loans and inadequate capital. The level of loan performance can impact positively or negatively on any economy. Adeyefa *et al.*, (2016) noted that performing loans enhances both company and economy performance, whereas the contrary undermines overall performance.

Nigeria is considered as an emerging economy. Therefore, to attain the status of a 'developed economy', the bank, which is the major financier to businesses needed to be upgraded to international standards since weaknesses in corporate governance system, especially in monitoring and strategic role played by board is identified as a significant challenge (Oluwakayode, 2017). This research, therefore, tends to critically evaluate from a shareholder's perception, the factors that might undermine or mitigate implementation of effective corporate governance principles. The research will be more precise on board of directors, considering that the board is paramount in facilitating company performance and plays pertinent roles of overseeing, directing, and strategising (Müller, 2014; Sener, Varoglu and Aren, 2011).

1.4 Research Gaps

This section provides the gaps on corporate governance adoption in emerging markets like Nigeria. In the course of carrying out this research, some gaps were identified in the literature, which this study intends to fill. First, Oyerinde (2014) noted that despite a lot of work done on areas of corporate governance, less attention was given to the arrears of financial sector, especially banks. He also identified the need on how the board should effectively handle the issue of insider loans which has engulfed the Nigerian banking system. Moreover, despite the efforts by banks to develop and implement unique corporate governance especially on ethics and

leadership, banks are yet to holistically adopt these measures (Onakoya, Moses, Iyiola, Salau and Ayoade, 2018). This research will, therefore, hope to identify why banks have not entirely adopted corporate governance codes for banks and necessary amendments needed to suit the Nigerian economy.

On the other hand, setting up directors' compensation has become an area of interest among nexus of individuals, shareholders, researchers, and directors. The level compensation is viewed as one of the most appropriate ways to motivate directors to effectively implement holistically corporate governance codes in organizations (Walther, Moltner and Morner, 2017). However, no specific way has been identified as the most appropriate since companies operate differently. Pergola and Joseph (2011) noted that some directors are motivated through equity ownership, Hoi and Robin (2004) argued it could be through stock options while Withers *et al.*, (2012) suggested firm Identification. This research will through the interview conducted contribute to the body of knowledge on the best way to compensate the directors to harness the potentials they possessed.

Ogbechie, Koufopoulos and Argyropoulou (2009) noted that Nigerian economic environment has improved compared to the years prior to their research. However, they reiterated that more needed to be done especially in the areas of implementation of corporate governance as the country is yet to entirely achieve robust effective corporate governance in organisation. This study intends to fill this gap by making suggestions based on the findings on how to engage the board on corporate governance implementation. Moreover, religiosity was identified as one of the major issues undermining effective implementation of corporate governance in Nigeria (Nakpodia, Shrives and Sorour, 2018). The researcher, will therefore, ascertain through

interviews, on how to juxtapose this conflicting factor, especially in board diversity and inclusion of women in the board. Besides religiosity and other challenges of good corporate governance, Bonorchis (2016) indicated that Nigerian banks have over the years been engulfed in financial crisis. Some of the palpable factors militating such crisis include lack of information on the side of the board on what corporate governance is all about and the need to implement it to achieve company performance (Nakpodia, 2018).

At the end of this study, the researcher tends to fill all the identified gaps in the literature. The study will make recommendation to the body of knowledge, which will as well be immensely beneficial to Nigerian banks on the implementation of corporate governance that will aid board effectiveness and company performance. Based on the limitation of the study, this study will recommend areas of further research.

1.5 Research Methodology

Previous studies on corporate governance have adopted qualitative data collection technique Nakpodiaa and Adegbiteb (2018). It includes collection of data through observation, surveys, and semi-structured interviews. However, some corporate governance research works have adopted both mixed method, which is quantitative and qualitative research method (Levrau and Van den Berghe, 2006)

The thesis adopted interpretivism philosophical approach as it gives the researcher the opportunity to have a detailed understanding of the phenomena this study addresses. Moreover,

inductive approach of research helped the researcher recommend process for board effectiveness and corporate governance implementation.

To achieve the objectives of this study, qualitative research method was adopted. Barnham (2015) argued that qualitative studies offer hard and factual data. It involves the use of semi-structured interview, which enables the researcher to ascertain in detail, the opinion, and sentiments of the participants. Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler (2014) noted that use of semi-structured interview in data collection is imperative in achieving the overall aims of a research.

The interview questions were developed based on prevailing issues of corporate governance in Nigeria. The participants who are mainly top managers were contacted and often reminded on the scheduled interviews. The participants were selected from the first-tier banks in Nigeria. The researcher succeeded in carrying out 15 interviews.

Multiple cases of five banks were adopted in this research. The banks are located all over Nigeria with regional headquarters in the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria. The participants of the study were made to understand the ethics of this research which ensures that their identity remains anonymous. The excerpts of the interview were passworded to ensure the anonymity of the participants are maintained.

After the interview, the responses were transcribed and were analysed using Thematic analysis, which was vital in coding and grouping the outcome of the interview in themes.

1.6 Outline of the Thesis

There are total of six (6) chapters in this study. The first chapter provides a background of the study and analysed the importance of research work. It encompasses the motivations for engaging on this study, aim and contribution to the body of knowledge.

The second chapter presents a comprehensive detail of review of related literature. The first part of the literature reviewed different major corporate governance model practiced across the globe, such as Continental European, Japanese, and Anglo-Saxon model of corporate governance. The chapter further analysed different corporate governance theories like agency, resource dependency and stewardship theories. The board characteristics like the board size, diversity and leadership duality were evaluated. The second section of chapter two presents the theoretical framework examining possible challenges of corporate governance implementation and key solution to eradicate such challenges.

The chapter three of the study provides the methodology employed for this study; it includes the philosophy, design and general approach. The population, sample, data collection and analytical tool adopted, were described. It also has tables showing the case studies and qualifications of the participants.

Chapter four presents a detailed analysis of the findings using thematic analysis. The excerpts of interviews were coded and separated and grouped into themes. The themes were discussed to address the aims and objectives of this research work.

The fifth chapter presents the discussion of findings in this study. It addresses the primary objectives of this research. The three objectives discussed was used to ascertain the prevailing

issues of corporate governance, the effect of lack of such challenges on corporate governance implementation and possible ways to ensure that the suggested solutions are effectively implemented.

Chapter six is the concluding phase of this thesis. It encompasses summary of findings, presentation of managerial contribution, recommendation, limitation of study and possible future research.

1.7 Nature and Scope of the Research

In this present-day, adoption and implementation of good corporate governance has been identified as a factor which underpins bank performance and has escalated unwinding interest from nexus of individuals including, academics, governments, and economists (Salim, Arjomandi and Seufert, 2016). According to Isukul and Chizea (2017), lack of corporate governance effectiveness including: disclosure, transparency in business transactions, effective directorship and shareholders right are among the factors which caused the recent global economic meltdown and may shrink the confidence of investors. Lack of implementation of corporate governance by the executive is referred as agency problem. Agency theory addressed reasons for lack of corporate governance implementation in organizations by executives. It assumes human beings are self-centred, which exacerbates conflict of interest between the principals and the agents (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Considering that lack of alignment of interest between principal and Agents might lead to poor corporate performance, this research therefore studied shareholders perception on corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks. Corporate

governance being a contemporary issue in emerging economies like Nigeria, not many researchers have focused on how the nexus of shareholders in Nigerian banks view the extent to which directors implement corporate governance principles in banks. Thus, this study will critically examine shareholders perception on management (Directors) effectiveness in implementing corporate governance code, challenges facing its implementation and possible solutions to eliminate such challenges.

This study employed qualitative method in providing vital evidence and proof which will be helpful to organizations in making informed decisions. It will also create opportunities for prospective researchers to further their investigations on proper corporate governance implementation in banks. The qualitative nature of this study (semi-structure interview) is advantageous as it encourages an in-depth finding on the phenomenon under investigation (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2007).

The scope of this study is limited within the banking sector. The mitigating factor behind the researcher's intent of narrowing this study to only banking sector is because of the complexity and uniqueness of the sector. Therefore, researching unaligned sectors, which are respectively guided by different principles will be uneasy to carry out as the data might not be juxtaposed. However, the methodology employed in this study will facilitate and build a foundation for future researchers who intend to either investigate corporate governance implementation in banking sector and any other sector.

1.8 Contribution of Study

A framework which is suitable for emerging economy and beyond was developed in this thesis. Besides, it is one of the very few studies that have successfully examined and empirically tested board effectiveness in implementing corporate governance codes. Consequently, this study has filled empirical gap in corporate governance literature. It has also contributed to the body of knowledge on factors that undermine corporate governance implementation in banks. The suggestion on the solutions of eradicating prevailing challenges of corporate governance can be replicated in other emerging markets considering that emerging markets share similar challenges.

1.9 Conclusion

This thesis intends to have a comprehensive understanding of underlying factors that erode corporate governance implementation in Nigerian commercial banks. The ability of the board to implement corporate governance principles is largely determined by their effectiveness. Therefore, this thesis examines the board characteristics like board size, diversity, and leadership. This chapter provides a holistic summary of the thesis. it encompasses the background of study, Nigerian context, aims and objectives, motivation of study, methodology and theoretical framework of the study. The next chapter presents the related literature review on corporate governance models, board characteristics and respective theories.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter deals with review of related literatures on corporate board effectiveness. It further analyses different corporate governance models and theories, and their impact on board effectiveness. The literature is divided into sections. The first section examines different corporate board models and its relationship to corporate governance, while the second section reviews related studies previously done on board of directors, which elaborate to an extent the roles of board of directors. This will help in the critical examination of the board effectiveness. The last section finally examines the viewpoints of relevant theories which are related to board effectiveness and performance.

Corporate board is an important aspect of corporate governance in any organisation being charged with duty of accenting financial decisions, strategic planning, and formulation of policies. However, the composition of this board has over time been a prevailing issue as it determines how effective the board will be. Some researchers have argued that when the board is effectively selected, it enhances effectiveness of the board of directors towards discharging their duties (Naciciti 2019 and Ferreira, 2010).

Despite the importance and need for effective governance, yet there is no single criterion to define an effective corporate board (Rachana Vishwakarma 2017). Literature has evidenced that there are diverse opinions on the factors that contributes to effectiveness of corporate board, which metamorphosis into company performance (Sheikh and Alom, 2021; Naciciti, 2019 and Ntim, 2015). As enshrined in principles of corporate governance and company laws, there are

specified guidelines which enhances effectiveness of corporate board (Mallin 2016). These corporate governance guidelines are distinctive and, in most cases, peculiar to individual countries.

In examining corporate governance structure and firm performance in emerging economies, it was identified in the literature that despite existing corporate governance guidelines existing in emerging economies, like in Nigeria, weak legal system still poses challenges in its full implementation and effectiveness of corporate governance (Arslan and Alqatan, 2020 and Ehikoya, 2007). Therefore, this weak legal system undermines both effectiveness of the board and company performance. La Rosa, Bernini and Terzani (2021) found that countries with high corruption level and corporate corruption negatively correlates with CEO corruption. This is exactly why corporate corruption is largely found in developing economies. As such, this has negatively affected corporate governance implementation in Nigeria.

The first part of this literature review presents the contextual literature by analyzing the Nigerian corporate board situation within the Nigerian context. It explains the Nigerian economic, political, and cultural structure. It further explains the Nigerian corporate governance practices and how codes have evolved over the years. The second part of this chapter presents the conceptual literature of this study. It encompasses the effectiveness of corporate governance, different models of corporate governance and board characteristics.

2.1 Contextual Literature

2.1.1 Nigerian Context

This study was carried out to examine shareholders perception on corporate governance implementation in Nigeria commercial banks. Therefore, it becomes imperative to holistically understand Nigeria, especially economic, political, and social cum cultural factors. Nigeria is the most populous country in Africa with a population of about 220 million inhabitants and located in West Africa. The land area is measured to be about 923,773 square metres. The country is one the many British colonies in West Africa and was officially recognised as one country in 1914 after the merging of the Southern and Northern Protectorates by Lord Frederick Lugard. Nigeria is a conglomerate of people of different ethnicity, language, culture and religions. The most recognised tribes in Nigeria include Igbos in the East, Hausas in the North and Yorubas in the West. Nigerian government and politics have been hugely divided across diversities of ethnicity, religions, geopolitical zones and class. In the country, Christianity and Islam are predominant and there are about 300 to 500 different languages spoken across the country. However, English remains the official language as it makes communication easier among the different ethnic groups.

Basically, Nigeria is regarded as the “Giant of Africa” and has the largest economy in the continent and 24th in the world. The economy is hugely dependent on its oil sector, which yields 95% of the foreign exchange earnings. Moreover, the Nigerian economy is worth about \$450 billion and \$1 trillion when it comes to nominal GDP and purchasing power parity. Despite being tagged a regional power in Africa and an emerging global power, Nigeria sits right at 158th position in the

world when it comes to Human Development Index (HDI). Nigeria and her inhabitants have been classified as a lower middle-income country. The gross national income per capita is between \$1,026 and \$3,986.

For the past few years, the government of the country had functioned with massive deficit budget. The deficit is estimated to be around 3-5% of the Gross Domestic Product level. The government hugely depends on both international and domestic borrowings to finance the country's budget. Currently, Nigeria is estimated to have a total external debt of \$40.96 billion. The debt profile is predicted to increase considering the impact of COVID-19 on the economy and continuous contraction of the GDP and collapse of global oil prices.

The government is now planning on more prudent fiscal policy and prediction of more favourable oil price which will possibly enhance the level of income. However, government efforts are undermined by weak institutions and corruption which remains endemic.

2.1.2 Nigerian Corporate governance

Corporate governance, which in simple terms mean the act of directing and controlling (Cadbury, 1992), has recently become paramount for most developed economies of the world because researchers have found that a positive relationship exists between good corporate governance practice and company performance (García-Meca, García-Sánchez and Martínez-Ferrero, 2015; Farhat, 2014). However, emerging economies in continents such as Asia and Africa, especially Nigeria, are now quite determined to be abreast with the best corporate practices of the developed economies in Western Europe and USA. Over a period of time, corporate governance

and its principles have gained a lot of attention in Nigerian economy as shareholders and other stakeholders need a medium to take the economy to a higher level. The principles of corporate governance in Nigeria are enshrined in the CAMA (Companies and Allied Matters Act 1990) and Code of Corporate Governance (2003). Moreover, in year (2008), SEC (Security and Exchange Commission) came up with more advanced corporate governance codes that will ensure transparency, accountability and good governance in organizations as weak corporate governance is blamed for corporate failures. To ensure that codes of corporate governance are updated to tackle prevailing economic challenges, Nigerian Financial Reporting Council (2016) amended some of the existing corporate governance codes which required the following: An increase in the minimum number of directors, that the NEDs should make up two-third of the board, half of the NEDs should be independent, and the CEO should be different from Chairman unless in special occasion where minority investors have given their consent (Deloitte Nigeria, 2017; Omolayo, Otome and Atekebo, 2017)

Despite sophisticated measures to ensure that corporate governance codes are incorporated into the Nigerian economy, Nmehielle and Nwauche (2004) argued that it is still a 'work in progress' considering how advanced other developed countries have gone. Though it is regarded as work in progress, the determination to enhance corporate governance in Nigeria is on its apogee as corporate organizations intend to build a sustainable and conducive economic environment especially in financial and capital markets, which will attract foreign and domestic investors (Munisi and Randoy, 2013). The drive for corporate governance reforms in Africa was also accelerated by economic globalisation and need for unification of standards. However, economic, cultural, and political differences have hindered the progress of these codes Tsamenyi and Uddin

(2008). Moreover, lack of supervision and enforcement, weaknesses in the legal system, and corruption have posed challenges to effective corporate governance not only in Nigeria but most African countries (Okpara, 2011; Munisi and Randoy, 2013, Cahn, 2004; Nmehielle and Nwauche, 2004; Garay and González ,2008). These challenges have led to poor composition and incompetence in the board, poor relationship between employees and managers and falsification of company accounts, which may have affected performance (Inyang, 2014).

2.2.0 Conceptual Literature

2.2.1 Corporate Board Effectiveness

Recent economic scandals have raised concern among nexus of individuals, which include shareholders, prospective investors, and researchers on the need to re-evaluate factors that mitigate board effectiveness. The major concern is, what defines 'effectiveness' of a board? Some authors have in their own different capacities tried to define what constitute or may be considered as board effectiveness. According to Jaskyte (2018), a corporate board effectiveness can be defined as the ability of the board to implement an idea, procedure, process, structure, and existing practice in an organisation. This means that in selecting the board members, it will be paramount to engage individuals who have the mental ability to develop an idea and can implement the prevailing guidelines of corporate governance in the organisation. Moreover, Harjoto, Laksmana and Yang (2018) noted that board effectiveness encompasses the readiness of the board to execute the fiduciary duty of monitoring and advisory roles they are entrusted

with. In juxtaposing these views of what effectiveness is, the definitions can be narrowed down to 'the ability of the board to implement' rules and regulation of an entity.

Previous studies have identified paucity in the board as one major challenge affecting corporate governance adoption in organization (Fedaseyeu, Linck and Wagner, 2018; Agara and Stainbank, 2014). However, board characteristics such as duality of Chairman and CEO positions, age of directors, size of the board, board diversity (number of female directors in the board) and number of meetings held annually are vital for good governance (Hongsong *et al.*, 2021 and Agara and Stainbank, 2014). Thus, these board characteristics if judiciously recognised and implemented can holistically improve firm performance. We will, therefore, discuss critically to ascertain the prospects and constrains associated with them especially when it comes to adoption of best corporate governance practice.

2.3 Corporate Governance Models

In discussing the effectiveness of the board on implementation of corporate governance, it is important to elucidate some factors which may undermine or underpin board characteristics in different economies of the world. Some of these factors include different corporate governance models practiced globally and the roles performed by the board in the organisation.

Basically, there are several corporate governance systems practiced globally to promote effectiveness and cohesiveness in the board (Ahmad and Omar, 2014). However, Ross (2018) noted that there are three main corporate governance systems practiced globally, which are as follows: The Anglo-Saxon, The Continental, and The Japanese Models. This research has limited

its scope on the three main leading corporate governance models, as it apparently represents the leading economies of the world and the most discussed models. The different economies of the world have developed models to accommodate and fit into their environment, culture, social cum political practices. It will also be pertinent to ascertain how emerging economies like Nigeria have been influenced by these models.

In countries like US, UK and Canada, the Anglo-Saxon model is adopted which is referred to as a one-tier board model. The Continental European model, which is a two-tier board model is widely practiced in European economies like Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Austria, Switzerland, and Finland. While the Japanese model is predominantly used in Japan and few other Asian countries including South Korea. The different models have its peculiarity on determination of the size and structure and effectiveness of board of directors. Corporate ownership system and the structure of businesses are differently operated under each model. Therefore, managerial behaviour under various models is shaped both by the legal and political practices in their respective environments (Ogbechie, 2012).

2.3.1 The Anglo-Saxon Model

The Anglo-Saxon, also known as Anglo-US model, is a corporate governance model that was originally adopted in UK and USA, respectively and now dominant across the globe (U-Din, 2021; Ahmad and Omar, 2014; Shalba 2016). This model has been rephrased into numerous names like; outsider model, equity-based model, market-centric model, shareholders model, principal-agent model, equity-based model, and finance model (Ahmad and Omar, 2014; Ooghe and Langhe,

2002). Empirical studies show that this model has been widely accepted globally especially among most commonwealth nations and some other developing economies (Uddin, Jayasinghe and Ahmed 2017; Chen *et al.*, 2015; Ahmad and Omar, 2014). However, U-Din (2021) argued that despite wide acceptance of Anglo-Saxon corporate governance model, that the continental model seems closer in achieving effective corporate governance in entities like banks.

In the Anglo-Saxon model, corporate ownership is fragmented and the owners of the corporation exercise indirect control over the activities of the organization (Ben, 2017). The model promotes ownership and control, where a set of individuals known as principals or shareholders relinquish the power of control to another set of individuals known as agents or managers to make decisions on their behalf. This relationship is classified as Agent-Principal relationship (Fedaseyeu, Linck and Wanger, 2018).

The principals are the owners and shareholders of firms that appoints the Agents to manage the affairs of the organization on their behalf (Chang, Kang and Li 2015). The Anglo-US model is a trio-based system that prioritise shareholders and other institutional shareholders. The other key players that make up the three sides of this corporate governance triangle in the Anglo-US model are the board of directors and the management (Shalba, 2016; Ogbechie, 2012). Furthermore, this model is designed to promote separation of ownership and control of any corporation, where the affair of the firm is absolutely run by the management and monitored by board of directors on behalf of shareholders (Chang, Kang and Li 2015). This helps to ensure board effectiveness and avoid agents' entrenchment, where the agents tend to satisfy their selfish interests at the expense of shareholders (Munisi and Mersland, 2016). This model requires that the board of directors encompasses both executive and non-executive (including independent) directors to

bring proper monitoring over management decisions, as non-executive directors protect shareholders interest more (Moumen, Othman and Hussainey, 2017).

Traditionally, in Anglo-US model, there are a few discrepancies in their application of the one-tier board system. This has affected how the shareholders evaluate the board to see that they effectively carry out their fiduciary duty (Ahmad and Omar, 2014; Meier and Meier, 2014). In the UK, it is not permissible, for one person to hold the position of CEO and Chairman of the board of directors. Though, it should be explained in a situation where it is practiced (Ahmad and Omar, 2014). However, researchers have noted that when the power of chairman and CEO is concentrated on an individual, it does lead to abuse of power. This has resulted in many companies including more outside independent directors in their firms to curtail such hegemony and boost board effectiveness. On the contrary, Meier and Meier (2014) explained that CEO duality, is accepted in the USA. This is a situation where an individual assumes both the chairmanship and CEO duty of a company which contradicts UK corporate governance guidelines.

Despite broader similarities shared by the UK and US corporate governance model, such as the separation of ownership and control, one-tier board system which includes executive and non-executive directors and board sub-committees like audit and remuneration committees (Chang, Kang and Li 2015; Fedaseyeu, Linck and Wanger, 2018); the respective economies still have limitations that have engulfed proper board monitoring, which has in turn led to deficiencies in board effectiveness. Siepel and Nightingale (2014) noted that in the USA, the dual-forked governance structure mitigated Delaware law, where managers control is highly favoured and not liable to some of their actions. This can be seen in the case of Lehman Bros where the managerial team successfully manipulated the true status of the company's account without

retrospective actions to penalise them. This, however, is not obtainable in the UK, as boards are liable for any misleading information with the intention to deceive. On the other hand, they noted the UK model has been undermined by systematic failure, poor management decisions, paucity of voting of unknowledgeable shareholders, improper board decision and deficiencies in regulation as seen in RBS (Royal Bank of Scotland) scandal.

To enhance board effectiveness, many researchers have suggested market-based rewards, as a panacea (Gehrke *et al.*, 2019 and Ogbuchie, 2012). This is where managers are rewarded according to their progress and company performances and will be a measure to increase discipline and sense of responsibility among board of directors and the managers. Therefore, this implies that the board will be effective when they are rewarded according to their respective performances. Moreover, the shareholders, through their voting rights can eliminate ineffective board members during annual meetings (Meier and Meier, 2014). This can be a factor which will facilitate board members to be on their toes when carrying out the fiduciary duty of the organization. However, determining what constitutes good individual performances may become a challenge and will require further research.

Chen *et al.*, (2015) argued that some aspects of Anglo-Saxon characteristics can be effective in some other economies. Their study shows that there is increase in earnings in Japanese firms when Audit committees were incorporated to Japanese corporate governance model. However, they noted that this was only achievable in companies that effectively implemented audit committees against those that did it ceremonially.

2.3.2 Continental European Model

The Continental European Model is also referred as ‘the Two Tier-Board’ or the Insider Model (Shalba, 2016). This model is overwhelmingly practiced in most continental European countries like Germany, Netherlands, and Poland (Bohdanowicz, 2015). Although there are some existing divergencies in its implementation in respective continental European countries, there are greater convergences which have positively influenced and affected board effectiveness (Uddin, Jayasinghe and Ahmed, 2016; Meier and Meier, 2014; Belot *et al.*, 2014).

Unlike the Anglo-Saxon model which basically prioritises shareholders interest, the Continental European model concentrates more on the interests of the entire stakeholders. These stakeholders include employees, customers, government, and all institutional and individual shareholders (Ahmad and Omar, 2014). De Gooyert *et al.* (2017) noted that stakeholders do play vital roles in influencing decisions of the management board which serves as a check to board activities. Furthermore, they argued that managers who intend to create value, sustainability, and ethics, do align the interests of the entire spectrum of stakeholders.

Moreover, there are some other notable characteristics which differentiates continental European model from other corporate governance models. Among them is board structure. This model is characterized by a two-tier board structure, where the executive (management) board is separate from the non-executive board. The executive board headed by the CEO oversees the managerial aspect of the organization whereas the non-executive board supervise the activities of the board (Ahmad and Omar, 2014). The non-executive board are also charged with the fiduciary duty of appointing and dismissing the management board, while the members of the

supervisory board are elected by the shareholders (Belot *et al.*, 2014). This model has a top to down checks and balances to ensure the effectiveness of the boards. This is achievable by the power of the supervisory board to hire or fire non-performing managers, and ability of the shareholders to vote out members of the supervisory board.

Meier and Meier (2014) found that most countries practicing continental European model have their corporate governance codes embedded in their civil law. This means that companies listed under this countries stock exchange are obliged to comply with its corporate governance codes to the letter. However, it contradicts the Anglo-Saxon codes, especially in the UK where companies can either comply or explain (Siepel and Nightingale; 2014).

In most Continental European countries, the structure of company ownership is concentrated on private individuals and families. In this setting, most companies are preferably financed by the banks as against equity financing which is mostly obtainable in the UK and US (Ahmad and Omar, 2014). They noted that the board becomes more effective under this model as the banks constitute part of the supervisory board. However, Bohdanowicz (2015) argued that continental European model does not holistically promote board effectiveness and facilitate company performance. In his research, he found that, in scenarios where the ownership is highly concentrated on an individual who also performs the duties of the CEO, the supervisory board selection can be flawed and manipulated. This further undermines transparency and limits the supervisory boards' eagerness for proper check on the management activities, as they can easily be cowed by the owner.

Based on the poor transparency in disclosure in family-owned businesses, Meier and Meier (2014) argued that it deters prospective investors in such organization. This, however, has led to some continental European companies listing their organizations either in UK or US stock so that it can Adopt the Anglo-Saxon Corporate governance codes.

2.3.3 The Anglo-Saxon and Continental European Models

Having critically examined both models, the major concern becomes; which of these models is the best? And which model does facilitate or undermine the board's ability to carry out their monitoring role effectively and ensure company performance? In the Anglo Saxon or One tier system, the executive and non-executive directors collectively operate as a board, whereas the continental European model separates its board into two – the supervisory and managerial board. Belot *et al.*, (2014) argued that the continental European board is more contemporary as it does not only protect shareholders interest but the entire stakeholders. They further argued that separation of the board into supervisory and managerial board provides equilibrium of power which enhances board effectiveness. However, Meier and Meier (2014) noted that ownership structure in continental European model has undermined the level of transparency when compared to the Anglo-Saxon model. As a result of this poor disclosure, some European companies opted quoting their companies in the US to boost global competition and attract investors. Having identified challenges faced by the respective models, Belot *et al.*, (2014) suggested that companies facing challenges of asymmetric information may opt for Anglo-Saxon

board system, while companies focusing on a future private benefit would utilize the two-tier system.

2.3.4 Japanese Corporate Governance Model

The Japanese corporate governance model is also referred to as 'inner model'. Before now, it was mainly practiced in Japan and few other Asian countries like South Korea (Solomon 2013). Prior to Japanese corporate governance board reformation in 2000's, the corporate board of most public corporations were traditionally characterized with large boards made up of only executive directors (Managers) who oversee the affairs of the organization (Miyajima *et al*, 2018). However, they note that after the commercial code amendment of 2003, and increase in the presence of institutional investors in most public corporations, it prompted many companies, for the first time, to include outside directors into the board.

In this corporate governance model, the banks are one of the major players. Unlike the previously discussed corporate governance models (Anglo-Saxon and Continental European) where funds are raised basically through equity in shares; in the Japanese model, the banks are the major suppliers of funds to organizations, thereby making them their largest shareholders. In this regard, banks and corporations tend to have a long-consolidated relationship in the Japanese economy (Hoshi, Koibuchi and Schaede, 2018). They also noted that in most cases, when top bank executive directors retire, they automatically assume executive directorship post in their client's firms.

Ogbechie (2012) noted that there are existing conglomerates in Japan, known as *Keiretsu*, which is very vital in how company operates under this model. He defined *Keiretsu* as a situation where organizations combine their resources in shares while they operate as different companies. The conglomerate companies are connected to each other through interconnected directors. Usually, the banks are an integral part of this conglomerate, and the firms operate through the help of each other, by buying one another's shares. Moreover, he expressed that this model covers four major nexus of players which include the bank, associate company, management, and the government.

In the late 1990's, there was massive shift in the Japanese corporate governance model. This is as a result of collapse in the Japanese bubble economy, as well the effect of financial deregulation. In this cause, more Japanese companies became more market-oriented and there was a drastic decline in bank domination in companies, just like practices in the Anglo-Saxon model (Solomon 2013). However, as there were persistent dwindle in bank ownership in companies, Miyajima *et al.*, (2018) expressed that there was a contra upsurge on the influx of foreign institutional investors in the ownership of Japanese companies, attaining about 75% ownership of firms, as of 2013. This means that the post economic bubble gave a rethink and caused changes in the Japanese corporate governance model, therefore, attracting external investors.

The effectiveness of board of directors under Japanese model could be classified into pre- and post-Japanese economic bubble, as there is indication that there was a post-economic bubble corporate governance model amendment (Solomon, 2013). Moreover, in the application of this model in companies, there are prospects and constraints on the effectiveness of the board of

directors. The importance of discussing both before and after economic bubbles of Japan is based on the fact that all Japanese companies are yet to holistically employ the post economic bubble corporate governance recommendations (Solomon 2013; Mun and Jung 2017; Miyajima *et al.*, 2018).

Prior to the economic bubble scandal, most of the Japanese firms' ownership were concentrated. The implication of such concentration is that external monitoring is undermined, meaning that it will be easier for managers to manoeuvre the company account and limits the ability of the external disciplinary action to be taken (Fukuda, Kasuya and Nakajima, 2018). Nevertheless, since the management of the company is basically undertaken by the owners in a concentrated ownership, they always act in the interest of the company. Contrarily, Tanaka (2014) argued that CEO ownership makes the CEO too powerful, thereby limiting the ability of the rest of board members to overturn his decisions. However, when the ownership is dispersed among nexus of shareholders, which requires separation of ownership and control; there are tendencies of slowdown in performance of companies especially in a scenario where managers act on their self-interest (Miyajima *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, they stated that in Japanese *Keiretsu*, where a company is owned by different companies, in order to ensure the effectiveness of the board, the parent company gives incentives to performing managers of the subsidiaries, and on the contrary, discipline the non-performing management by either replacing the president of the subsidiary or their representative.

Furthermore, Pandey and Rhee (2014) argued on the importance of foreign CEOs on the effectiveness of the board in the Japanese post-economic bubble scandal. In their empirical research, they found out that foreign CEOs enhanced board effectiveness. The home CEOs hardly

switch from the status quo or the previous model to the amended corporate governance model. They also found that the home CEO's lack the required courage of taking risks of re-strategizing towards achieving greater performance, whereas the foreign CEOs typically adjust and change their traditional strategies where necessary to make the company competitive in the market, thereby, enhancing the effectiveness of the entire board.

2.4 Corporate Governance Theories

2.4.1 Agency Theory and Corporate Board Effectiveness

The Agent-Principal problem is not peculiar to an industry, rather it has become a phenomenon associated with organizations where there is a separation of ownership and control (Zhang *et al.*, 2020 and Hamzah and Zulkafli, 2014). Conflict of interest arising from the agents' selfish desires, which imminently exacerbates into managerial opportunism has become one of the biggest challenges faced by the principals. Moreover, Zhang *et al.*, (2020) noted that there is high tendency of the board becoming inefficient in carrying out their monitoring and controlling role and become puppets of the executive. To reconcile this agent-principal dichotomy, agency theory focuses on devising avenues to minimize opportunism exhibited by managers in order to achieve organisational goals and maximize shareholders wealth (Shaikh and Colarelli O'Connor, 2020 and Munisi and Randøy, 2013).

To optimize the effectiveness of the board, literature on corporate governance, precisely on agency theory has gained prominence to address issues of remuneration, considering its motivational prowess for board performance (Akter *et al.*, 2020 and Fernandes *et al.*, 2013).

Despite Akter *et al.*, (2020) arguing in favour of positive relation between company performance and directors' remuneration, they noted that the positive correlation is not holistic. This indicates that there are other factors which affect company performance. Furthermore, we found out that most literature are more concerned on executive directors' remuneration, with limited attention to Independent Non-Executive directors. However, studies have revealed that the level of remuneration creates a lot of positive impact on the effectiveness of Independent Non-Executive Directors in discharging their directorial duties (Harymawan *et al.*, 2020; Aslam, Haron and Tahir, 2019 and Mallin, Melis and Gaia, 2015). The disagreements that arise between the managers and owners, and challenges of information asymmetry between management and the board have necessitated the increase in non-executive director's duties, as they tend to bring harmony through legal responsibilities, independent opinion, effective supervision, and adoption of current regulatory initiatives of respective countries (Hoitash and Mkrtychyan, 2021 and Lazar, Metzner, Rapp, & Wolff, 2014). Although the above assertions claimed a positive relationship between remuneration and corporate board effectiveness, an insight on how to measure individual board performance was vague. This work will expressively proffer means to evaluate each board member's contribution and subsequently, fill this knowledge gap.

Besides board compensation, another bottleneck facing an organisation is 'agency cost', which can be measured by decrease in the value of the firm, and cost incurred by the board in bonding and monitoring activities of the management (Silaghi and Sarkar, 2021 and García-Ramos and García-Olalla, 2011). The challenges of agency cost therefore, raises the question; 'Should the principals be allowed to manage their own firms?' Varela (2017) argued that corporate boards are more effective in bigger firms and outperform firms with ownership controls, especially in

some economies (Italy), where principal-principal problems exist. This consolidates the works of (Bendickson *et al.* 2016) that claimed agents manage organizations better than the shareholders.

2.4.2 Stakeholder Theory and Board Effectiveness

Among other theories, the propagations of stakeholder's theory have contributed immensely towards board of directors' effectiveness and company performance (Dal Maso *et al.*, 2018). The emergence of this theory was to address issues surrounding all the stakeholders that have been neglected by other corporate governance theories (Freeman, Phillips and Sisodia, 2018 and Tullberg, 2013). It was argued that considerable number of studies ignored the importance of all stakeholders, as attention was given only to the primary stakeholders (shareholders) and their key business partners; thereby, neglecting the likes of employees and the management team (Tullberg, 2013). Moreover, stakeholder theory addresses the need to give a wide range of stakeholders the necessary attention and solve their wants; in establishing trade-offs that are important to achieve a competitive advantage (Patel *et al.*, 2016). On the other hand, Freeman, Philips and Sisodia (2018) noted the importance of stakeholder theory and argued that it is vital in strategic management.

However, Freeman (1983) posited that the development of stakeholder theory was as a result of some underlying circumstances. It includes drastic globalisation businesses, changes in IT (Information Technology), increase on the individuals' sensitivity on how businesses operate in their respective environment, and reduction in government monopoly in planning and ownership of companies.

Also, the definition of who should be regarded as a stakeholder has raised interest among spectrum of researchers, as divergent opinions are given. Ogbechie (2012) defined stakeholders as all those who are interested and concerned in the business and will be at risk if the business fails. For example, employees who might be unemployed if the company is liquidated; creditors who may be at risk if they do not recover their full debt in a case of insolvency; suppliers that had them as major customer; and entire communities that depend on the company as major employer. Moreover, stakeholders can be classified as those who are connected directly and indirectly to any business (Mallin, 2016). Among them are the owners of the business, creditors, suppliers, employees, government, and the community.

To ensure the effectiveness the board, respective shareholders employ different measures to influence and ensure transparency and voluntary disclosure in organizations (Thijssens *et al* 2015; Oliveira, Rodrigues and Craig, 2013; Qu *et al*, 2012). For example, the customers might stop patronising the organization, and potential investors declining the interest of investing the firm, and minority shareholders pulling out. When a company discloses its activities, it helps the stakeholders, especially investors, to make an informed decision (Sanusi 2010). Moreover, a group of stakeholders capable of influencing voluntary disclosure by the organization have been identified by numerous researchers, and this group of shareholders include the minority investors, creditors, employees, and consumers (Thrassou *et al.*, 2020 and Oliveira, Rodrigues and Craig, 2013). Nyahas *et al.*, (2018) argued that the firms are eager to respond to powerful stakeholder's request, as they are vital in the business sustainability. This suggests that priority will be given to such powerful stakeholders against minor shareholders. In this situation, the

corporate social responsibility of an organisation can be undermined where stakeholders are not powerful.

Moreover, Clark Howard (2018) noted that the consumer pressures can be utilised in influencing wrong decisions made by the board of any organization. In his research on illegal fishing, he argued that the customers have the right to question and trace the source of their seafood, which can be rejected if there is notion of illegal fishing. However, this may only be achievable in the western developed economies considering the fact that most developing economies do not key into such regulation. He expressed that beside the fishing industry, this method of questioning organisational activities can be applied in all industries.

Contrary to the assertion of Sanusi (2010), who argued that there is weak involuntary disclosure in the Nigerian economy, which has undermined organisational growth; Nyahas *et al.*, 2018 explained that stakeholders in the Nigerian environment have understood and realized their powers to influence management decisions, which is backed by the country's labour laws. They further stated that the stakeholders can embark on industrial actions to achieve their aim.

2.4.3 Stewardship Theory and Board Effectiveness

The emergency of stewardship theory was to address the relationship between the business owners and managers based on behavioural factors (Dodd and Dyck 2015). The word 'Stewardship', which can also be referred Agency, simply means delegation (Krzeminska and Zeyen 2017). In defining the differences between Agency and Stewardship theories, they noted that agency theory is of the view that the agents, who have been delegated to pilot the activities

of an organization (on behalf of the owners) tend to develop selfish interests. In doing so, they contradict the interest of the principals who are the owners of the business. However, the Stewardship theory, which originated from sociology and psychology, posit that managers without compulsion, work towards the interest of the shareholders. This means that managers in stewardship theory will require little or no check to execute their duties.

Mathias *et al.*, (2017) defined this managerial behavioural under stewardship theory — where managers act selflessly and prioritise the interest of owners — as an ‘intrinsic behaviour’. In this regard, managers are naturally motivated to align their interest with that of the shareholders. Considering the effectiveness of the board under this theory, it failed to recognise that when there is no proper monitoring or checks and balances, that there are possibilities of managers exhibiting promiscuous behaviour, which may result in corporate failure. Some studies have identified major corporate scandals and failures that were traceable to paucity in the monitoring efficacy of the board of directors. For example, Enron, Parmalat, and Barings banks, respectively (Mallin 2016; Solomon 2013).

Although the stewardship theory eased the concept of managerial opportunism and selfish interests being exhibited by managers, as posited in the agency theory; the stewardship theory submit that managers can actually be self-motivated to act selflessly for principals, thereby aligning their interests to that of the shareholders (Le Breton-Miller, Miller, & Lester, 2011). However, Dodd and Dyck (2015) argued that the position of stewardship theory cannot be holistically applicable to all businesses but will be favourable to mainly family-owned businesses. When businesses are managed by owners, they will be willing to pilot company activities effectively without any form subjugation, having in mind that any form of negligence will

undermine the performance of the company. This may not be the case where a business is owned by a nexus of shareholders, because there are possibilities of having different set of individuals influencing the decisions of the management, which will lead to asymmetric information, lack of transparency and undermine the board's effectiveness.

Furthermore, for companies to achieve greater board effectiveness, Maidson, Kellermanns and Munyon (2017) suggested that an organisation should not focus only on stewardship theory to achieve their goals but rather employ both stewardship and agency theories in the daily operations of the firm. They argued that both theories have important roles to play. While the agency theory gives impact on the oversights and monitoring, the stewardship theory promotes an intrinsic behaviour of the managers to act on trust. However, to solidify their argument on the application of dual theories, they noted that through the sole implementation of stewardship theory, there is a possibility that some of the manager's actions would be made in good faith, yet would not depict the interests of the shareholders.

To achieve broader board effectiveness then, there is need to revisit the scope of stewardship theory and effect changes to contain the prevailing challenges faced by different organizations. This theory which was developed by Donaldson and Davis (1991 & 1993) believed that stewards can research on the interest of the shareholders and align theirs to that of the shareholders. However, this recommendation may not fit into every sector of the economy or culture as individuals' mindset are shaped by the environment. If stewardship theory is employed in a firm, it may lead to a dichotomy of interests from managers, as some may be pursuing selfish economic benefits while others may align their interest to that of the shareholders. Therefore, how to identify managers that will align their interests with that of shareholders becomes a problem.

Additionally, Stout (2013) noted that guidelines of stewardship theory have become obsolete as it was previously practiced in UK and USA in 1920s to early 1970s, as the term 'Managerialism'.

Despite the limitations associated with Stewardship theory, Chen, Yang and Chen (2015) argued that it can be a tool to enhance board performance. This can be achievable in companies that practice 'CEO succession'. A scenario where firms prefer an internal succession to the apex position based on performance. Internal succession can be beneficial to organizations in so many ways, which include reduction in cost of hiring an external professional and cost of training a new CEO. The most notable advantage of this practice is that most managers will prioritise the interest of the shareholders with the intention of becoming a CEO, which will enhance board effectiveness and eradicate managerial opportunism.

Today, individual companies have reserved the right to decide whether to employ the Stewardship theory, Agency theory or both depending on the environment the entity is domiciled and nature of ownership. However, the dynamism of human behaviour should be considered as a factor in making such a key decision. Keay (2017) argued that directors are mortal, and as such have their flaws and unpredictable tendencies. Thus, accountability is necessary to make the board more effective.

Considering the Nigerian environment, which is an emerging market, it will be necessary for companies to inject proper internal control system. This type of internal control system is the one recommended by the agency theory, where the chairman of a company is different from the CEO to avoid any scandalous mismanagement.

2.4.4 Resource Dependency Theory and Board Effectiveness

Most of the theories, including Agency, Stewardship and Stakeholder's theory concentrated more on behaviours and relationships between owners, management and those connected to the business in one way or the other. However, Resource Dependency theory addresses endogenous factors, where board of directors are seen as suppliers of resources to the organization (Bhatt and Bhattacharya 2015). They noted that this is achievable through external links of the board which will promote the influx of resources into the company.

Wang *et al.*, (2017) highlighted members of the board as resources considering their roles in mapping out strategies and connecting the company with the external environment. Moreover, Power and Chuong (2010) elaborated more on this resourceful links of the board of directors – which is the ability of the board to influence the environment that they solely depend on for business and survival. Some of the individuals that constitute this environment include the suppliers, trade creditors and consumers. According to their empirical research, they found that a good relationship with suppliers which necessitate supply of standard goods and quality services for consumers, positively correlates to company performance and good relationship with customers. This means that customers are opportunistic in nature, they place priority over quality goods and services to any other private relationships established in the organization.

To achieve greater board effectiveness under Resource Dependency theory, Bhatt and Bhattacharya (2015) argued that greater board size enhances the effectiveness of the board. They believe greater board size accommodates more expertise in the board, which will improve the exogenous relationship of the firm. This assertion of greater board size and company

performance is consistent with the previous findings of Wang, Chen, Fang and Tian (2017); Pfeffer & Salancik (2003). Contrarily, De Andres *et al.* (2005) argued that there is a negative relationship between board size and performance; that the more the board size increases, the higher the possibility it might undermine effective communication of the board, thereby limiting board effectiveness and company performance. García-Olalla (2011) opined that increase in board size is more favourable to family owned and controlled businesses. As the study carried out on board characteristics of European firms show increased performance on family-controlled business with large board size.

Besides board size and board effectiveness, Bhatt and Bhattacharya (2015) posit that frequent board activity does enhance board effectiveness. For example, increase in number of meetings held by the board can boost its resourcefulness to the organization and do help the board to have massive understanding, improve on the outlined strategies and take proper control of the company's activities. This finding aligns to the study by Brick and Chidambaran (2010), who found a positive relationship between board activities and company performance. Moreover, Bhatt and Bhattacharya (2015) noted that companies that increased the number of meetings held by the board, did so because of poor performance previously experienced in the firm. In Nigeria, the corporate governance code (2016) recommends that the board should meet at least once every quarter to ensure proper monitoring and effective oversight function.

Furthermore, under the Resource Dependency theory, it posits that board interlock increases board effectiveness and brings resources into a firm (Zona *et al.*, 2018). They defined 'board interlock' as a scenario where a board member or members can undertake directorial position in two or more companies. The dual directorial position establish links to companies involved and

is expected to accrue resources into the firms. Pro-dependency theorists believe that organisational relationships are reciprocal (Wry, Cobb, & Aldrich, 2013). This means that no company is an island, and the ability to establish links with each other can boost the exchange of necessary resources that will enhance company performance.

However, board interlock contravenes the posit of agency theory (Dalton, Hitt, Certo, and Dalton, 2007). The agency believe that managers are opportunistic and prioritise their economic interests above that of shareholder. Therefore, when managers are directors in two or more companies, they tend to favour the company paying higher, which will impair their oversight duty over the company paying lesser remuneration. Secondly, this gives advantage to managers to earn higher than their worth, as companies will be determined to pay higher for their companies to be prioritized, thereby, exacerbating the agency cost.

Zona *et al.* (2018) argued that the dichotomy arising from the view of agency and resource dependency theories may be applicable in different organizations. They noted that board interlock can improve board effectiveness when the CEO holds a stake in the company. This means that the CEO will act holistically in the interest of the shareholders and make good decision that will enhance company performance, because any scandal that faces the company will affect his stake.

In Germany, resource dependency theory is used to assess the effectiveness of board of directors. It serves as a parameter to evaluate human capital and the management performance, as well as, in planning, directing, strategising, and controlling (Torrington, Hall, Taylor, & Atkinson, 2011). Resource dependency theory helps a company to overcome environmental constraints through

the creation of external relationships and political links (Amalou-Dopke and Suß 2014). This means that in selecting directors, the company will prioritise people with links externally, which will facilitate resource influx into the company. There are prospects and constraints that might arise in such situation. The company may lack directors who have skills to make strategic decisions over those with external links that might bring resources. A company with resources without skillful directors, might run the risk of undermining utilization of such resources through bad decisions. Therefore, companies should incorporate for both skillful and non-skillful directors with external connections.

2.4.5 Managerial Hegemony and Board Effectiveness

The literature on managerial hegemony is heavily undermined due to limited studies available at the time of carrying out this work, especially on how it affects the board of directors' effectiveness. However, this research has meticulously utilized the available studies, as this theory is paramount for a core understanding of factors which could underpin or undermine board effectiveness.

Adebite (2012) defined the concept of managerial hegemony in line with the previous works of (Galbraith, 1967; Mace, 1971; Herman, 1981; Vance, 1983; Wolfson, 1984); which assumes that the board is a legal fiction, which fails in its legal duty to alleviate conflict of interest between corporate management and shareholders, considering its supervisory and monitoring power over the executives.

The conflict of interests arising from the dichotomy of interest between the management and shareholders does not necessarily mean that the corporate managers are always wrong in some of the decisions made. Instead, because managers are always under pressure to perform, they become hegemonic in nature. They set targets to achieve financial performance, which might be contrary to the interests of the investors (Cushen, 2013). This hegemonic attitude of managers does facilitate performance, but the company may be at risk of poor performance in a long run. The poor performance by the managers in the long run may be as result of overturning the freedom given to them to pilot company affairs in the best interest of the company to their selfish economic interest. This contradicts the recommendation of corporate governance that encourages independent directorship to bring checks and balances into the system. Although the stewardship theory posits that managers tend to act in the interest of the shareholders (Mathias *et al.*, 2017), it will be important to have routine checks to avoid managerial opportunism in a long run.

Furthermore, Ashraf and Uddin (2015) noted that there are occasions where there is horizontal hegemony in an organization. Sometimes it may be dual, and in some cases tripartite hegemony. For the purpose of this research, the focus will be on the dual hegemony, which is always between the employees and the management team. They noted that one bloc (management) achieves managerial hegemony through coercion on the employees; by threat of redundancies and cut in wages and salary, so as the achieve their aims. However, in a reprisal response, it mitigates the employees forming their own bloc to resist any form of imperialism from the management team. This type of relationship does negatively affect the performance of the company as it portrays lack of cohesiveness in operation of the company.

To eradicate any form of managerial hegemony, teamwork should be encouraged in organizations (Vallas, 2003). This will help to limit the excessive power that the management may exhibit. However, the effectiveness of teamwork between employees and employers may vary from time to time as some skilled workers form a domineering group to achieve their own economic gain. In this case, classes of employees should be mixed up (top-down) in a team to avoid any hegemonic situation.

Moreover, Adegbite (2013) argued that when the management is involved in selection of the board, it results to lack of separation of board from the management and facilitate management dominance. To achieve board effectiveness, he recommends (just like corporate governance codes) that the board should be dominated by independent non-executive directors not appointed by the management.

In Nigeria and other emerging economies, it will be beneficial to assimilate this system of greater independent non-executive directors in the board. It will help to alleviate any form of entrenchment by the management and bring proper checks and balances.

2.5 Corporate Governance Characteristics and Board Implementation

2.5.1 Non-Executive Directors

The presence of independent and outside directors has become imperative in every organisation. According to Kouaib, Mhiri and Jarboui (2020), the number of non-executive directors are used to determine the level of independence in a board. Consequently, the need for large presence of

non-executive directors in companies also arises. Although the non-executive directors can be beneficial to a respective organization, the size of the non-executives should not be prioritized but the quality of the members of the board (Mollah, Liljeblom and Mobarek, 2021). Quality ranges from experience, skills, knowledge and areas of expertise.

The need for inclusion and strengthening of the roles of Non-Executive Directors (NEDs after here) in the board resulted from the corporate scandals experienced globally. They include Enron, Parmalat, Barings banks (Treadwell, 2006). He noted that NED's role metamorphosed from bringing external experience in the board to monitoring the activities of the board to eradicate any opportunistic behaviour by executive directors.

However, how to maximize the efficiency of the board of directors through incorporation of NEDs becomes a challenge to an organization. To enhance the effectiveness of the board, the pro-Agency Theorists led by Fama and Jensen (1983) recommended that the board leadership role should be separated into CEO and Chairman and the roles assumed by separate individuals. The CEO with the executive directors is charged with piloting the daily activities of the firm, while the chairman through his monitoring role, checks the activities of the executive directors alongside other NEDs.

When the board leadership is dualized, it brings checks and balances in the board. It also eliminates selfish economic interests exhibited by executive directors and protect the interests of the shareholders, especially in developing economies like Nigeria, where the legal system is weak (Ehikioya, 2007). Appropriate proportion of both executive and NEDs in the board does

enhance the effectiveness of the board in carrying out their monitoring role and consequently, boost organisational performance (Oyerinde, 2014).

Nevertheless, there are mix empirical results on the impact of NEDs on the effectiveness of board and company performance. Prior studies like Rosenstein and Wyatt (1990); Mehran (1995); John and Senbet (1998) found a positive correlation between presence of NEDs in the board and effectiveness of the board which ensures company performance. On the contrary, other studies such as Weir and Laing, (2001); Pinteris (2001); Kajola (2000) found no positive relationship between NEDs and performance, especially in accounting profit and value creation.

For the NEDs to be effective in carrying out their directorial activities, Walther, Möltner and Morner (2017) argued that the NEDs should be properly motivated; as motivation will encourage the skillful directors to keep serving on the board and achieve company performance. Prior research has also shown some of the impacts of the presence of NEDs in the board. For example, highly motivated NEDs are more vigilant in monitoring the activities of the CEOs compared to the less motivated ones (Hambrick *et al.*, 2015). However, there are challenges of a specific motivation factor that will enhance board effectiveness and company performance. Gagné and Deci (2005) noted that human psychology differs, therefore, what motivates individuals may differ. At the end of this research, the findings will be relevant in filling the gap in literature on what best motivates a NED.

2.5.2 Board Size and corporate board effectiveness

The need for board size reform and its effectiveness on board of directors has conspicuously drawn attention among spectrum of researchers. The board size deals with the totality of directors in any corporate entity. Hence, the number of directors which an entity should hire becomes vital as it is a major factor in boosting or undermining board effectiveness and company performance. Namanya, Nuwagaba and Nyende (2021) argued that the board should consist of an average of nine members. This is to achieve high level of cohesion during meetings and avoid drawbacks like limited attendance when the board size is too many.

The impact of board size on the effectiveness of board of directors and company performance has raised a dichotomous view among many researchers. Some are of the view that they are positively correlated (Ilaboya and Obaretin, 2015; Johl, Kaur and Cooper, 2015; Arayssi, *et al.*, 2016); while others have a contrary view that large board size is negatively correlated to board effectiveness and company performance (Kalsie and Shrivastav, 2016; Müller 2014; Sakawa and Watanabel, 2011).

In examining 166 quoted companies in the Nigerian stock exchange market from 2005 to 2012, Ilaboya and Obaretin (2015) found that most companies with greater number of board members performed overwhelmingly above those who have lesser board size. Similarly, Johl, Kaur and Cooper (2015) argued that larger boards boost effectiveness of board of directors. In observing 700 Malaysian firms in 2009, they observed that boards with higher number of directors, especially those who had directors with accounting and financial experiences and expertise, were more effective compared to smaller boards. They argued that a board with larger number of

directors will give the company a better opportunity to encompass arrays of expertise who can actually work together to achieve set organisational goals.

Furthermore, to optimise the effectiveness of the board of directors, larger board size has been identified as a good way to enhance the fiduciary duty of the board in monitoring the management activities (Arayssi *et al.*, 2016). They suggested that independence of the outside directors is an added advantage, which also enhances the effectiveness of the board. There are other empirical studies that have argued in support of large board size being more effective compared to smaller corporate boards (Adhikary, Huynh, & Hoang, 2014; Sahu & Manna, 2013).

Hsu and Wu (2013) argued that though the issue of board size is pertinent as it is correlated to board effectiveness and company performance, the ratio of the grey directors (NED's) to executive directors should be given utmost attention as it augments board effectiveness. In a study carried out in UK on corporate failures, they found that companies with greater number of grey directors against executive directors performed better than companies with lesser grey directors.

Moreover, Fauver *et al.*, (2017) reiterated the need for increase in the total number of independent non-Executive directors to eliminate the tendency of CEO turning the board members into his cronies. Besides the size of the board and its effect on the board, Fauver *et al.*, (2017) claimed that an upsurge in the appeal for reformation of the board system, considering that it does attract potential investors and increases confidence of shareholders in such company, is not necessary. They further argued that the pre-existing board roles put into consideration necessitate factors that facilitate board effectiveness. The argument, however,

does not consider change in time which will probably need dynamism in the board roles. This change in time may be as a result technological and innovation change, which may invariably bring changes in people's mindset and the environment.

On the contrary, Kalsie and Shrivastav (2016) posits that managers require less monitoring to be effective and in dispensation of their fiduciary duties as managers. This argument posits that, large board size does not necessary determine board effectiveness, as smaller boards can monitor the activities of the managers and minimize the remuneration cost associate with large board size.

In the Japanese financial sector, Sakawa and Watanabel (2017) found the existence of a negative relationship between larger boards and effectiveness of corporate board, thereby, negatively affects board effectiveness and company performance. They noted that there are deficiencies in the monitoring and advisory roles of large board size and outside directors, as seen recently in Japanese banks. In Italy, the case is not different, as the board size had an insignificant influence on the effectiveness of Italian water utility companies as there was limited positive relationship (Guerrini and Romano, 2014). This is as a result of political influence in board decision which undermined the board effectiveness of these companies.

Furthermore, in examining Spanish SMEs, Arosa, Iturralde and Maseda (2013) found that companies with large board members and more outside directors are negatively correlated to board effectiveness and company performance. Nevertheless, to achieve greater board effectiveness, they recommended that the board should accommodate more insider directors because they are engaged in daily activities of the company and have knowledge of challenges

facing the organization. In this case, their recommendation compromises the corporate governance recommendation and the possibilities of the CEO turning a smaller board into his cronies is highly possible.

De Andres *et al.*, (2005) argued that larger boards undermine board effectiveness. It creates lapses in the board and undermines the appraisal of the individual board members. But when the board is small, it gives opportunity for active participation of every board member. However, they also expressed the importance of diversity in the board to enhance board effectiveness.

Garcia-Torea *et al.* (2015) noted that board size is recommended to be between 5-9, and that both the proponents and opponents of large board size posit the same range of board size for effectiveness of the board. The major dichotomy here is how to determine when the board size is under or over boarded.

Apart from empirical findings and literatures on the importance of board size and company performance, some corporate governance codes have respective recommendations on board size for effectiveness of the board. For example, in America, most of the corporate governance act recommend larger board size as it was argued to be more effective compared to organizations with smaller boards. Among the corporate governance codes are Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002 (SOX) and NYSE (The New York Stock Exchange) /NASDAQ (National Association of Securities Dealers Automated Quotations exchange) recommend increase on the status quo of the numbers of the corporate board members to substantiate the effectiveness of the board and eliminate corporate scandals (Lee, Bosworth and Kudo, 2016).

Furthermore, Agency theory suggested that greater representation in the board leverages board's ability to execute their monitoring roles, augment company's resources and eradicate any form of dominance, which the CEOs tend to exhibit (Pearce and Patel, 2017). The assertion of dousing CEOs dominance may be achievable by the large board size, but it will be important that executive directors are not included in the selection process, to bring objectivity among the directors.

2.5.3 Board Leadership and board effectiveness

The leadership of a board addresses the situation where one person assumes the duty of both the CEO and chairman of an organization or where the duty of CEO and Chairman is acted independently by respective individuals. Aberg and Shen (2020) argued that the chairperson of a board has the greatest influence in determining the governance of an organisation. Some researchers have raised arguments on the importance of board leadership structure and their effect on corporate governance implementation and company performance. For example, Puni and Anlesinya (2020) found that a sizable board and frequency of board meetings had a positive impact on corporate governance and company performance. However, they found no correlation between board duality and firm performance. This explains the arguments of Arosa, Iturralde and Maseda (2013), who explained that prior literatures have acknowledged that the duty of CEO and that of chairman has a lot of impact on the board effectiveness, whether two individuals assume both duties respectively or it is performed simultaneously by an individual.

For effectiveness of the board, García-Olalla and García-Ramos (2010) posits that separation of the duty of chairman and CEO is paramount and that both duties should be carried out by respective individuals. They noted that it enhances the board's ability to execute their monitoring, supervisory and advisory roles independently and effectively. In Spain, a study carried out on how effectiveness of the board can enhance corporate outcomes (Bravo, Reguera-Alvarado and del Pilar Pérez, 2018), found that a board is more effective when the duty of CEO and Chairman is separated, especially in corporate disclosure. It also alleviates the tendencies of the CEO turning the board members into his cronies to achieve personal economic gains.

Furthermore, the CEO duality promotes open dialogue in the board, where independent view is aired and put into consideration between the executive (CEO) and non-executive (Chairman) directors (Bailey and Peck, 2013). This system helps to promote transparency and accountability in the organization. It will also give opportunity for proper evaluation of any prospective risks that might pose a threat to corporate performance and relevance. However, they noted whether it enhances company performance is yet to be agreed on by different researchers.

Among the dangers of non-duality of board leadership is 'hubristic attitude' by CEOs. This attitude has been identified as a factor which might weaken the effectiveness of the corporate board (Park *et al.*, 2015). They defined 'CEO hubris' as a situation where CEOs overhype their self-confidence and exhibit pride in the execution of their duties. Moreover, Malmendier and Tate (2008) argued that CEO hubris could endanger the prospects of a company, because they are always optimistic that their actions will align with the interest of the shareholders, even when their activities may be disastrous to the company's existence.

To address the issues surrounding CEO hubris which can exacerbate into CEO entrenchment and affects effectiveness of the board, Park *et al.*, (2015) stated that the board can nip to bud this situation by becoming more vigilant in discharging their monitory and supervisory roles. Thus, it will be of utmost importance for the function of the CEO and chairman to be separated to achieve independent supervision. It will help to eliminate the tendency of the CEO becoming too powerful, which might mitigate conflict of interest between him and that of the shareholders.

The challenges of non-duality also include the unforeseeable attitude the executive directors (who are also part of the managerial team) tend to exhibit if left unmonitored. de Villiers *et al.*, (2011) argued that CEOs are always eager to abandon long-term investments that will be more profitable to a company in the future, in preference for short-term projects that will yield momentary return on equity. However, this conflict of interest is not about financial gains but about job security. CEOs are aware of the risk of being relieved of their duty if the company does not perform economically great in the current year because the shareholders do not always deem it wise to consider long term effect of management actions. However, the concept of stewardship theory contradicts the view that directors are selfish and act to achieve personal gains instead of tackling the shareholders need (Mathias *et al.*, 2017). It will be good if opportunities are given to mangers to make long term plans that would be beneficial and will not plunge the entity into scandals. Nevertheless, monitoring is very crucial, which implies that having a chairman as the head among other non-executive directors, to bring checks and balances and prevent any opportunistic behaviour, is highly needed.

However, Samaha *et al.*, (2015) noted that though duality of board leadership may enhance board effectiveness, it is very negatively correlated to voluntary disclosure. This means that when

the chairman and CEO are different persons, the CEO is always under compulsion to make disclosures. Under such scenario, the board cohesiveness maybe undermined. They noted that the environment further influences the voluntary disclosure under CEO duality.

In Nigeria, the situation of CEO entrenchment has been found in banks, which has undermined the level of monitoring by the boards, because the CEOs/Chairmen are highly influential (Aliyu, Jamil and Mohamed, 2014). This is primarily due to lapses in independent opinion of the board, both in monitoring and supervising, which affected growth and development of the banks (CBN, 2010). However, to eliminate such CEO entrenchment and enhance board effectiveness both in banks and other private businesses, the FRCN (2016) recommends that separate individuals should assume the duty of the CEO and that of the Chairman.

Obigbemi *et al.*, (2016) in examining 137 quoted Nigerian companies, found that separation of CEO and chairman does not enhance earning management, though it does boost valuation of the company. This study predated the amendment of the Nigerian corporate governance codes of 2016 and was conducted in a non-financial sector. This study will therefore, base its work on post-amendment of Nigeria corporate governance, specifically in the financial sector, to examine its effect both on board effectiveness and company performance.

However, despite changes and review of the codes of corporate governance in Nigeria, there are still environmental factors affecting its full implementation and viability. Isukul and Chizea (2015) noted that lack of implementation in firms resulted from Government ineffectiveness. If the government makes laws to penalize board members for misdeeds, it may go a long way to enhance board effectiveness.

2.5.4 Board diversity and board effectiveness

Corporate board diversity encompasses demographic representation, which includes ethnic and cultural representation and percentage of women in a board (Frijns, Dodd and Cimerova, 2016). More often, it has been argued that if a corporate board directorship is properly diversified, it does enhance the board's effectiveness and create value for the company (Sanan, 2016; Mori, 2014). To express the importance of board diversity, some countries do assign quota of gender, ethnic and religious representation in a board, especially in public/state owned organizations (Ferrero-Ferrero *et al.*, 2013).

Among the compendium about board diversity is the presence of women in the board, which has handful of literature addressing its effect on the board's effectiveness, especially in developing economies, like Nigeria. Despite limited number of literatures addressing this issue, few others have discovered the importance of discussing it (Goergen and Renneboog, 2014; Matsa and Miller, 2013).

When women are equitably represented in the board, it does enhance effectiveness of the board in carrying out their duties judiciously on behalf of the shareholders (Balasubramanian & Mohanty (2015) and promote transparency in decision making (Upadhyay and Zeng, 2014). The assertions of a board being more effective when women are included, may not be replicable from one organization, industry, or economy to another (García-Meca, García-Sánchez and Martínez-Ferrero, 2015). Moreover, in support of women's importance to board effectiveness, Sanan (2016) noted that women are more risk averse, sensitive to issues and bring cohesion in executing their directorial duties. However, the criteria for selecting women in the board was not clearly

defined, to know if all women possessed the aforementioned traits or if they need special training in exhibiting such qualities. A study that was carried out in Nigeria and Turkey on Board Composition and Gender Diversity by Şener and Karaye (2014) found that companies that have incorporated a specific percentage of women in their board outperformed those that did not; though this result was more prominent in Turkey than Nigeria. They highlighted some qualities possessed by female directors which include diligence in monitoring organisational performance and in attending board and sub-committee meetings compared to male directors, and their presence in the board further enhanced investors' confidence.

Besides gender representation in the board, Kalsie and Shrivastav (2016) also found that a more diversified board boosts corporate board effectiveness as experiences of individuals from different ethnic or religious backgrounds and gender will unify their diversified ideas to make a positive strategic plan and monitoring. It was also found that board diversity, especially that which incorporates foreign and multicultural board composition has the tenacity to minimize information asymmetry connected to agency, enhance the financial flexibility of the organization, and attract investors, agglomerate diversified knowledge, and technology (Fogel *et al.*, 2013).

However, Ararat *et al.* (2015) argued that when a corporate board is diversified, it can also adversely affect and undermine the effectiveness and capability of the board to execute its monitoring duty. The reason for such wedge in monitoring of the managers can be explicitly seen as bias among the board members who share common ethnic, religious or gender affiliation. In postulating solutions for greater boards effectiveness, (Mori, 2014) contradicted the assertion that a proper diversified board promotes board effectiveness, rather he is of the view that board members should be equipped with academic qualification and other leadership skills. He further

noted that companies that incorporate highly educated executives into their boards tend to be more effective than companies that have done otherwise. More literatures suggested that board members knowledge, skills and abilities enhance effectiveness of board of directors (Badru, Ahmad-Zaluki; Wan-Hussin, 2017). The researcher in analysing respective arguments believes that though knowledge and skills should be prioritized, a more diversified board gives every stakeholder/shareholder directly/indirectly involved in business sense of belonging when they are represented.

Board heterogeneity, in terms of age, human capital and ethnic tribe are important diversity parameters that must be contextually considered in order to promote board cohesiveness and effectiveness in Nigeria (Adegbite 2014). He, however, stated that heterogeneity of board is not reflective in most firms that operates nationally.

2.5.5 Institutional investors and board effectiveness

Institutional investors, which includes investment banks and pension funds, who invest individuals' wealth managed by them in other organizations are considered as a major factor that can stimulate and enhance corporate board effectiveness and company performance (Cleary and Wang, 2016; Murthy and Singh, 2013; Ertuna and Tükel, 2013).

Thus, diverse opinion has been expressed in the literature on how institutional investors underpin board effectiveness. We, therefore, carefully considered wide range of literature to holistically ascertain and analyse the prospects and constraints of organizations with this class of investors.

Cleary and Wang (2016) noted that institutional investors automatically bring checks and balances to the board. This is achieved through high quality professionalism exhibited by institutional investors both in possessing judgement and the level of knowledge which exceeds that of private investors. These qualities help in proper speculation of the stock market for accurate long-term forecast, which the board benefits from in the formulation of their strategies and decision making. Furthermore, it is argued that the institutional investors possess strong incentives and prerogative power to access information, which helps them in proper monitoring of the board and organisational behaviour in its entirety (Harford *et al.*, 2015; Cleary and Wang 2016). Based on the assertion of prerogative powers of the institutional investors, we are of the opinion that there may be possibility of them abusing such powers of information asymmetry to the detriment of other private shareholders, and this has created gap that needs to be addressed.

However, Harford *et al.*, (2015) argued that not all institutional investors enhance board performance and have access to information, which helps in monitoring board activities. They categorically stated that it is mostly enjoyed by long term institutional investors against the short-term institutional investors. Therefore, they found that firms with higher number of long-term institutional shareholders have more effective board, higher board independence and surge in board meeting attendance. Similarly, Hao (2014) stated that since short-term institutional investors have limited incentives, which results to less monitoring by them; it implies that the board effectiveness can be undermined in the long run if dominated by short-term institutional investors. Hence, long term institutional shareholders play a better role in monitoring, which deter boards from misusing shareholders wealth and manipulations to satisfy their selfish interest at the expense of organisational shareholders.

Furthermore, in emerging economies like Nigeria and other Sub-Saharan African countries, disclosure and transparency in organizations have become bottle necks that have negatively affected the efficiency of companies and undermine board reputation and its effectiveness (Ertuna and Tükel, 2013). Corrupt practices and ineffectiveness of the board have been identified as some of the major challenges that aggravated poor disclosure and transparency (Adegbite 2014). Although, this is a major challenge facing emerging economies, which often scares away foreign institutional investors, Ertuna and Tükel, (2013) found that some organizations utilize this opportunity by implementing required corporate governance codes and guidelines, which makes them unique, makes the board effective, then attracts foreign and local institutional investors, which gives them an edge over other competitors who failed in that aspect.

Attig *et al.*, (2013) in examining the impact of institutional investor on board effectiveness, ascertained that the presence of institutional investors does bring harmony to the board and helps in reduction of Agency Cost (cost incurred in monitoring the management). Besides, Cleary and Wang (2016) noted how domineering long-term institutional investors could be in boards' decisions as they always threaten the board with stock pull out from the entity if their opinion is not respected. This may lead to a dichotomy of interest among the short- and long-term institutional investors, as both parties are respectively interested in short and long-term recoupment period, which may inadvertently affect board performance (Hao, 2014).

The arguments of respective researchers were logical; however, the prerogative powers of the institutional investors could be anarchical as they will mostly influence decisions that will suit their selfish interest. For example, Harford *et al.*, (2015) stated that institutional investors have access to internal information, which leads to information asymmetry.

2.5.6 Audit Committee and board effectiveness

Audit committee is seamlessly regarded as one the most important board committees, which could mitigate or enhance effectiveness of the board and company performance (Samaha *et al.*, 2015; Lee, 2015; Karim, Robin and Suh, 2015). They are involved in monitoring and reviewing the financial reports and statements of an entity, which they do as a subcommittee since they cannot effectively participate in the day-to-day activities (QU, 2018). Paucity of audit committee could impair board effectiveness and company performance (Mallin, 2016). For example, Enron (2001) scandal is traceable to poor performance of the audit committee. An active Audit committee boost the level of confidence in ascertaining comprehensible, relevant, and unabridged information (Khlif and Samaha ,2014)

Paucity in financial accountability has resulted in the bankruptcy and liquidation of big companies, as seen in Enron and Barings Bank (Mallin, 2016). The issues of rampant corporate failures facilitated the upsurge and need for review of the composition of board of directors including the audit committee (Ghafran and O'Sullivan, 2017). Strengthening of Audit committee is one major way to minimize and eradicate corporate financial fraudulent activities (OECD, 2004). Cai *et al.*, (2015) noted that a positive relationship has been found recently between effective audit committee and managerial accountability. This means that effectiveness of the audit committee enhances the effectiveness of the board. They also found that in China, audit committees are usually associated with companies where an individual act as both Chairman and CEO to bring checks and balances. However, the country's code does not compel, but advises companies to incorporate an audit committee in their board.

Samaha *et al.*, (2015) in their empirical research using meta-analysis technique, found that presence of Audit committee is important towards achieving voluntary disclosure in the board. Audit committee works as a control mechanism in appraisal of the top management and assessing their behaviours through voluntary disclosure (Allegrini and Greco, 2013). The big question here is, 'who and who should make up the audit committee to achieve desired board effectiveness?'

Aliyu *et al.*, (2014) describe audit committee as a sensitive aspect of the board that helps in the monitoring and control roles of the board. To achieve effectiveness of the board, they argued that members of the committee should be made up of financial experts for easy interpretation of the financial information and reports. Moreover, quality of the board and audit committee is measured and determined by number of accounting and financial expertise forming part of the board (Albring *et al.*, 2013). When the audit committee accommodates financial experts, it enhances the effectiveness of the board and provides proper monitoring, which gives credibility and reliability to the company's balance sheet (Abernathy, Herrmann, Kang, & Krishnan, 2013).

The level of financial expertise in the Audit committee has been regarded as crucial, which is paramount in safeguarding the standard of processing financial reporting (Tanyi and Smith, 2015). They also noted that the committee adds value in the board especially in the areas that requires technicality and in decision making. Beside audit committee being instrumental towards interpretation of the financial reports, DeFond and Zhang (2014) argued that they are vital to audit clients to accomplish a targeted audit quality. Nevertheless, they highlighted the need for independence and quality of audit committee to achieve required audit quality.

However, Ghafran and O'Sullivan (2017) argued that the assertion that financial expertise in the board does enhance audit quality is contradictory to their empirical finding. They noted that financial experts in the audit committee undermines the external auditor's ability to carry out statutory independent examination. On the other hand, when the committee is made up non-financial experts, it boosts the audit quality because the auditor will be in-depth in scrutinizing company's financial records. However, when the board is made up of non-accounting experts, the audit cost is higher because of the intensity of the external auditor's job. The audit quality is thus very important in guiding prospective investors in making informed decisions. Nevertheless, the claim that financial experts does enhance audit quality (Ghafran and O'Sullivan, 2017) supports the view of Beasley *et al.*, 2009. They noted that intentional misstatement is hard to detect and when this intentional error is not detected by audit committee, they still fail to take responsibility as are not by any act meant to detect fraud.

Beside whom or who should be incorporated into the audit committee, whether financial expertise or otherwise; Gao and Huang (2018) suggested that for an audit committee to be effective, especially in checkmating entrenched management and improving independence in the board, the audit committee should be odd numbered. They noted audit committee members do vote based on information at hand if they are odd numbered. However, if they have even number, it undermines objectivity, because they tend to vote to conform to the rest of the members and avoid being in isolation. This act is regarded as conformity preference over performance, which undermines audit committee effectiveness and corporate earnings quality.

Furthermore, the challenges affecting effectiveness of audit committee could arise from the type of corporate governance model that operates in the economy. For example, in Nigeria, most of

the corporate governance codes is borrowed from the Anglo-Saxon Model and other international bodies recommendations like IMF and OECD (Adegbite, 2012), which requires that audit committee members should consist of independent directors. However, in the Chinese economy, the case is quite different as employees form part of the audit committee (Lee, 2015). He noted the consequence of having employees in the audit committee being a lack of independence, as they will not objectively question the hierarchy of the management. The employees may also risk losing their jobs in this cause if they contradict management report. To achieve audit committee effectiveness, it will be necessary for all the committee members to be all independent non-executive directors.

Moreover, Lee (2015) noted that lack of financial expertise and experience in the audit committee and failure of duty specification between supervisory board and audit committee could limit board effectiveness and incoherence in the board. This suggest that in hiring financial expertise, the level of experience should be considered for effective audit committee.

2.5.7 Remuneration Committee and Board Effectiveness

The remuneration committee are charged with the duty of recommending to the board, appropriate compensation due to the executive directors (Harymawan *et al.*, 2020; Okike, 2007). For effectiveness of the remuneration committee, Okike (2007) noted that Nigerian corporate governance code requires wholly non-executive directors as members and chairman of the committee.

Boyle and Roberts (2013) explained some of the impediments of remuneration committee effectiveness in recommending appropriate compensation for the executive directors. First, when a CEO is part of the Remuneration committee, there is a high possibility of exhibiting opportunistic behaviour to influence their pay. However, even when CEOs are sidelined from the remuneration committee, they still influence the committee decision by promising bumper contract to the remuneration committee.

In examining the impact of remuneration committee on corporate performance, Appiah and Chizema (2015) found that there are negative correlations between independence of remuneration committee chairman and board effectiveness. However, the presence of remuneration committee and frequent meetings are positively correlated to board effectiveness. The negative relation between independence of the remuneration committee could be attributed to assertion of Boyle and Roberts (2013), that collusion always exist between the CEOs and the remuneration committee in return for a favour. The ability of collusion between the executive and remuneration committee (mostly made up of non-executive directors) can be predominantly found in developing economies or countries with a weak legal system (Ehikioya, 2007).

Most studies have now given more attention to the importance of independence of the remuneration committee, which serves as a panacea for the board to be more effective and unbiased in determining the compensation due to directors (Boyle and Roberts, 2013). However, the independence of the corporate board will not solely be sufficient to enhance the effectiveness of the board as there are other compiling factors that mitigates board effectiveness. Munisi and Mersland (2016) argued that among other factors, the remuneration committee

should be sensitive in setting the remuneration of the board members, as weighty remuneration can boost the zeal and willingness of the board to effectively discharge their fiduciary role. In understanding other factors that will likely enhance remuneration committee, Boon-Leong and Swee-Sim (2020) suggested that the committee should appraise the performance of the board and management and remunerate them according to their performances (pay-performance). However, Lokman and Mohd Tareh (2020) opine that the performance of the management does not absolutely correlate with directors' remuneration. They noted that the size of an entity determines how remuneration committees set directors' compensation. Therefore, it is imperative to say that the remuneration committee should review different approaches of setting remuneration, and set the compensations based on current situation.

2.5.8 Ownership Structure and board effectiveness

Among other factors, the ownership structure is one of the major determinants of successful corporate governance implementation in an organisation and it can either enhance or undermine company performance. The ownership of an organisation has the obligation to provide necessary supervision to the management to ensure good governance (corporate governance) and boost firm value (Setiany *et al.*, 2020).

Zaid, Abuhijleh and Pucheta-Martínez (2020) argued that a diversified shareholding affects nexus of individuals who benefit from the company. They noted that respective opinions of the different owners can affect the strategic decisions of an organisation and subsequently, can

undermine or underpin corporate governance implementation. This is in a situation where there is conflict of interests among shareholders, especially the majority and minority share owners.

On the contrary, Rashid (2020) is of a different opinion on the impact of ownership structure on company performance. He found that companies perform better in all ramifications when owned by a director or internationally owned.

This assertion cannot be totally agreed to. The mindset of owners seems to matter more, that is to say, if the owners are enlightened on the corporate governance principles and other professional trainings, it will help in aligning the interest of the owners in making informed decisions that will be helpful to organisation in the foreseeable future. Saona, Muro and Alvarado (2020) assert that having an owner in the board where the company is diversely owned can create information asymmetry. However, they opined that in such situation, the board should have independent executives who can bring required check in the organisation.

Furthermore, irrespective of the ownership structure, either concentrated or disperse, the main objective of the entity is to build an organisation that creates value to owners, attractive to prospective investors and attentive to the welfare of all stakeholders (Syamsudin Setiany and Sajidah, 2017). Consequently, one can argue that either dispersed or concentrated ownership can either undermine or underpin corporate governance. To ensure proper implementation of corporate governance in the banks, the board should be consisted of reasonable number of independent directors to encourage transparency and accountability in the company.

2.6 Directors Over-boarding

Human capital is unquestionably, one of the ultimate qualities needed for effective board and company performance (Ployhart & Moliterno, 2011). However, they claimed that this human capital can be affected by the problem of 'over-boarding'. That is a situation where directors (executive and non-executive) are employed in different corporate boards because of their skills, abilities and experience they have amassed. Since they are part of different boards, it may conflict their interest on which board should they give utmost priority. The evidence of over-boarding limiting the ability of the board to be absolutely effective was supported by the work of Kor and Sundaramurthy (2009). Their findings show that when individuals with human capital in the board are also members of other corporate boards, it does limit their capabilities to function. This is, however, a phenomenal issue which has created gap on the corporate governance guidelines as no known guideline has been postulated to widely tackle it. Therefore, the need to make a law to forbade one from serving as a representative in more two company boards arises.

Despite the discrepancies on the drawbacks of board effectiveness, which include over-boarding, limited human capital and inappropriate board composition, Khanna, Jones and Boivie, (2013) argued that there are more factors which could undermine the effectiveness of corporate boards; amongst them is level of information processing demands. This over information can be so devastating even to the skilful and experienced board members if not properly managed. This phenomenal issue of over information can be sorted by selecting people who are experienced in a peculiar field with years of experience in that field and employ more directors for proper dissemination of duties.

The board of directors are charged with the roles of monitoring and over-sighting (Jensen & Meckling, 1976), which also encompasses the right of hiring and firing. Nevertheless, this work suggested that the strategic planning of the organization should however be prioritized for effective operation. Apart from making strategic decisions, hiring qualified individuals whom records have shown their worth and potentials should be extensively considered. This is to ensure there are proper over-sighting and monitoring to make sure that the mapped-out strategies are well executed. The question now is whether it is only about implementation. The board should be a bit flexible in implementation of the strategies, as changes in technology, time and natural phenomenon may contradict the mapped-out strategies. Based on that, this study intends to recommend regular meetings of the entire board, which will enable them to meet up with such emergencies, instead of relinquishing all the power of decision making in the hands of managers in such emergencies or unforeseen circumstances. Regular training will also be recommended for proper board effectiveness.

2.7 Pension Fund and Board Effectiveness

Globally, different economies have and are still witnessing destabilised economic activities because of prevailing crises in the banking sector. Barajas and Catalán (2015) explained that bank crises might have resulted from the government intervention and guarantees to banks liability. The banks however, because of this guarantee engaged in excessive risks, which government weak regulations and supervisions could not eradicate.

To enhance corporate board effectiveness, major shareholders such as pension fund and other institutional investors are regarded as being instrumental in acting as watchdogs which keep the board of directors on their toes to perform. Azegele (2021) found a positive relationship between corporate governance and effectiveness of pension fund managers. For the management of pension funds to be effective, they will hold respective banks they have invested funds accountable. This is more like a ripple effect. However, the claim that pension funds can effectively influence board activities has received diverse opinions. Barajas and Catalán (2015) argued that pension funds can not necessarily ensure board effectiveness in all cases. Their finding shows that the willingness of the pension fund to checkmate the activities of the board increases when their investment increases in the bank. Literature has shown that banks are always loyal to institutional investors when exercising their fiduciary duties. They believe that if the interests of the investors are not well represented, it might result to capital flight where investors might move their funds to an alternative bank where their interests are represented. This assertion that institutional investors boost board effectiveness aligned with past findings (Martínez Pería and Schmukler, 2001; Park and Peristiani, 1998).

On the contrary, pension funds' power to influence board's decision could undermine the independence of the board to effectively carry out their directorial roles. In a situation where the pension fund is so influential, there is high tendency of them developing selfish interest which might jeopardize the interest of the board and other shareholders. Demirguc-Kunt and Huizinga (2004) found a weak relationship between market discipline and deposit insurance scheme. To achieve greater board effectiveness, the entire shareholders should be able to unify their interests to avoid principal – principal conflict. In an attempt to examine common shareholders

interest, Berger and Turk-Ariss (2010) observed that over an eleven-year period, that a common behaviour among all shareholders promoted strong market discipline. This evidenced that common shareholders interest can influence board decision and effectiveness. They also noted that most investors and shareholders are more interested in equity-asset ratio compared to loan portfolio performance.

2.8 Directors Remuneration and board effectiveness

The board of directors who are the apex decision making body of corporations are charged with the strategic role of controlling, monitoring and planning for their organisation (Arumona and Erin, 2019).

However, these directors are faced with challenges of prioritising maximization of profit, which has caused the management to dabble into account falsification. A survey carried out by ACCA (Association of Chartered Certified Accountants) in 2007, showed that quality financial reporting will be threatened in the next five years, if the shareholders continue to pay more interest to profit maximization alone without considering other economic factors (Sarkar, Sarkar and Sen, 2008).

Poor and low-quality accounting information disclosure is regarded as a setback, which militates economic crisis. For example, Mitton (2002) argued that the East Asian economic crisis resulted from weak institutions and accounting opacity. This menace of account manipulation is exacerbated by some company's policy to juxtapose CEO's remuneration and level of profit (Ghosh, 2006). The effect, therefore, is that profits are inflated by the management as to get a

higher remuneration (Sarkar, Sarkar and Sen, 2008). In this case, it is better for managerial compensation to be fixed to avoid inflated profits because it can lead to insolvency and eventually, liquidation of the entity.

In Nigeria, a study carried out on managerial incentives and bank performance, showed that incentives given to the board do not mitigate board effectiveness and performance (Onakoya *et al.*, 2018). The outcome of their analysis shows that number of years of a CEO can boost effectiveness and performance. This is an indication that Nigerian bank directors do not perform because of perceived incentives that may accrue proportionally to the profit made. However, the positive relationship between the tenure of board and effectiveness indicates perfection from experience because of years spent in the board.

2.9 Government influence on corporate board

The economic crisis of 2007 which affected almost all the economies of world has prompted the need to re-evaluate the extent at which government needed to participate to achieve effective governance in organizations. In a study carried out on Nigerian banks, Adegbite (2012) noted that the government should participate in monitoring the banks through their regulatory and enforcement roles. However, he argued that there are loopholes in their participation and recommended that more governmental participation towards effective governance is needed in Nigerian banks. To ensure effective corporate board in Nigeria, the government through Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and Bank and Other Financial Institution Act (BOFIA) re-modified existing

codes of corporate governance in 2014 to address prevailing issues of corporate governance. Despite the amplified corporate governance code, banks are still undergoing one crisis or the other. Shrives and Brennan (2015) noted that one of the reasons why corporate governance guidelines prevail in one country above others lies in the robustness of their regulatory system. In different economies, corporate governance mechanisms are applied differently. Some of the guidelines are enshrined in the constitution and are obligatory; while in other economies, they are principle-based and voluntary (Nakpodia *et al.*, 2016; Black 2008; Arjoon 2006). The principled-based corporate governance codes are always voluntary, which are enacted by different concerned bodies to promote best practices and effective governance in different corporations (Adegbite *et al.*, 2011). As such, the rule-based codes are binding and must be followed to later by all the corporations involved. This system creates opportunity for government mediation by making laws that will deter defaulters (Osemeke and Adegbite 2016).

In considering which system (Rule-based or Principle-based) is more suitable for effective governance in organizations, Black (2008) noted that principle-based system is overwhelmed by weaknesses which the global economic crisis has exposed. However, Nakpodia *et al.*, (2016) argued that corporate governance effectiveness does not depend on which regulatory system is applied, but the uniqueness of the environment that it is applied. Moreover, Carmona and Trombetta (2008) favoured the premise assertion that the environment determines the type of corporate governance system that should be applied. Some of the determinant factors include the accounting traditions and conditions of the institutions in an economy. In emerging economies like Nigeria, this approach should be adopted in determining what type of regulation should be practiced, as the system has been engulfed by weak corporate governance, lack of

transparency and disclosure, and poor relationship between shareholders and other stakeholders (Okpara 2010). In studying which system should be adopted in developing economies, Nakpodia *et al.*, (2016) found that integrated regulation system should be adopted in Nigeria, where peculiar codes should be obligatory, whereas some others should be optional. Furthermore, concerns have been raised on the challenges faced by companies that are politically connected. In Nigeria, the Code of corporate governance of 2014 recommended that government should not own more than ten percent shares of any bank (CBN, 2014). This is with the aim of reducing governmental influence in internal decision making of the banks. According to Chen, Ding and Kim (2010), politically connected entities are poised with challenges of information asymmetry between the managers and investors. Besides information asymmetry, corruption has been identified as another challenge to companies that are politically connected, especially in developing countries (Chen, Ding and Kim, 2007; Gray, Harymawan and Nowland, 2014). This level of corruption in political connected companies has led them into inflating their earnings forecasts (Chen, Ding and Kim, 2010). When companies inflate their earnings, it might undermine the confidence of shareholders and deter prospective investors from becoming part of the company. Nevertheless, Gray, Harymawan and Nowland (2014) noted that there are benefits associated with political connected firms. For example, political connected firms excel in areas of public policy process and always have access to politicians who might be influenced into making policies favourable to the organization.

In a post global economic crisis research carried out in USA, it was ascertained that gaps in governmental policies contributed immensely to the economic meltdown (Wallison, 2009). The

government policies should be enabling for businesses to thrive and remove restrictions that will undermine investors in getting appropriate return on their investment.

Table 2.1. Themes from the literature

Main Theme	Researchers	Specialization	Research relevance
Ownership Structure	Rashid (2020)	Business Administration	Ownership structure was used to ascertain the impact ownership in implementing corporate governance policies in Banks.
	Saona, P., Muro, L. and Alvarado, M. (2020).	Business and Economics	
	Setiany, E., Syamsudin, S., Sundawini, A. and Putra, Y. (2020	Accounting and Business Administration	
	Zaid, Abuhijleh and Pucheta-Martínez (2020)	Finance and Economics	
Leadership challenge	Arayssi, Jizi and Tabaja, (2020)	Department of Finance and Accounting	Leadership of the board go a long way in determining the extent of corporate governance
	Hauser (2018)	Finance, Insurance and Business Law.	

	Puni, A. and Anlesinya, A. (2020).	Business Administration and Human Resource Management	implementation and company performance. The board are charged with duty of overseeing, monitoring, and controlling of the company. Therefore, their effectiveness will be important in achieving desired company performance.
	Badru, Ahmad-Zaluki and Wan-Hussin, (2017)	Economics, business and finance	
Shareholders Interest	Anderson, Chi and Liao (2019).	Finance, corporate governance, and Board efficiency	This theme helps in ascertaining the possible ways to eliminate principal-principal conflict. It further helps in
	Magnanelli and Pirolo (2021)	Management and Organizational studies	

	Crisóstomo, Brandão, and Lopez-Iturriaga (2019).	Accounting and Finance	solving majority and minority conflict.
	Burunciuc and Gonenc, (2020)	Economics and Finance	
Bailout fund	Adedoyin (2019)	Computing and Informatics	Bailout fund by government has been highlighted as a program that encourages corruption and unaccountability by the banks. This theme therefore helps in finding ways to ensure bailout fund program will be utilized only when necessary.
	Amaramiro and Njemanze (2019)	Accounting	
	Ojekunle (2019)	Public Administration	

2.10. Development of Conceptual Framework

2.10.1 Introduction

This section presents the theoretical framework of this study. Corporate governance models, theories and principles have been reviewed to establish their importance on corporate governance implementation and effectiveness in commercial banks. Figure 2.1 demonstrate theoretical framework which was developed with the intention to critically analyse “shareholders perception on corporate governance implementation in Nigerian commercial banks.” In the development of the framework, the later stream of this research work and the work of the Sharma (2011) and Levrau and Van de Berghe (2007) framework was adopted.

2.10.2 The Sharma Board Effectiveness Framework

Sharma (2011) developed a framework that expresses the interrelationship between Board, IT (Information and Technology) governance and firm performance; unlike other theoretical/conceptual frameworks on board effectiveness, which focused on the board roles and characteristics. For example, Lerau and Berghe (2007) framework is basically on how the board characteristics, through cohesiveness and debate will achieve board effectiveness and company performance, whereas Nicholson and Kiel (2004) focused on how external and internal corporate governance mechanism will be aligned to achieve board effectiveness and company performance. However, Sharma (2011) board effectiveness framework is unique, and it goes beyond most frameworks built on corporate governance theories. It incorporates and explores other external factors such as insufficiency in the system that has incapacitated the ability of the

board to executive their directorial duty in this contemporary globalized and technologically driven world. The most significant idea different from other studies is the ability of the research to align internal corporate governance mechanism with 'Information and Technology'.

The framework focuses on the input of two major internal corporate governance mechanism, which includes board structure and board role. The last component of the framework is the IT governance, which basically aims at aligning both mechanisms in achieving board effectiveness and firm performance.

The board characteristics is the first component of the framework. It conceptualizes that certain board characteristics mitigates board effectiveness. Some of the identified characteristics include the size, independence, and diversity of the board. She also noted that size of the board, proportion of outsider directors (NED) and diversity in the board enhances corporate board effectiveness. Sakawa and Watanabel (2017) also discovered that the size and independence of external directors are positively correlated to board effectiveness and company performance. However, they noted that the case is different in non-OECD countries and the findings in the Japanese banking industry shows negative relationship of larger board and independent of outside directors and board effectiveness. This framework does not argue on the appropriate size or proportion of outside independent directors, but encourages a reasonable number in the board size, proportion of outside directors in the board and a diversified board.

The second component of the framework deals with the roles of the board. She noted that the board is bestowed with two major roles; control (that is overseeing the activities of the management, making appropriate report to the shareholders, and ensuring that the company

abides by rules and regulations) and direction (to ensure that the company strategy and blueprint are implemented). Sharma (2011) expressed that agency theory is the source of control role of the board, which primarily intends to eradicate selfish interest that the management tends to exhibit. Furthermore, the monitoring role is assumed to be important as it will be difficult for dispersed individual shareholders to monitor their stakes. However, Bravo, Reguera-Alvarado and del Pilar Pérez (2018) argued that for the board to be effective, their roles should go beyond monitoring and control, and be involved in company's disclosure practices. The voluntary disclosure on the side of the board will, therefore, enhance the level of accountability and effectiveness, by which they are compelled to disclose palpable information to the stakeholders (Garcia-Torea *et al.*, 2016).

The third component of Sharma (2011) board effectiveness framework is IT Governance. It emphasizes the importance of information and technology in this contemporary dynamic and complex market. Figure 2.1 below (next page) shows Sharma, 2011 Board Effectiveness framework.

Figure 2.1 Relationship between Board, IT governance and Firm Performance (Sharma, 2011)

2.10.3 Levrau and Van den Berghe Framework

A process-oriented framework for board effectiveness was developed by Levrau and Van den Berghe (2007) which is represented on figure 2.2 below. In their research, they enumerated several factors believed to arbitrate the direct effect of board characteristics on firm performance. The model employed was based on input-process-output which was previously used by (Cohen and Baily, 1997; Gladstein, 1984) in research framework for studying teams of an organization.

The model indicates that the extent directors carry out their strategic and control roles determine how effective the board will be. The authors argue that combination of three process variables will highly affect the task assignment of boards, thereby, will enhance how well the board carries out its role of service, strategy, and control. The three identified processes include cohesiveness, debate, and conflict of norms. The members of the board are encouraged to employ cohesiveness in discharging their duties as it results to good communication and collaboration among the board members. Levräu and Van den Berghe (2007) assert that minimal cohesion employed in the board will make the directors to work as team which will lead to board effectiveness. Moreover, constructive debate in the board is imperative in decision-making, as regular debates before making decisions will improve the board's performance. The third process which is conflict norm will usually ensue when there is disagreement in the board. Conflicts are witnessed especially when debating on how best to perform the board function. So, conflict norm plays moderating function between board characteristics and debate.

Board characteristics of board size, board independence and board diversity contributed to the input in this framework. Their study argued that large board size undermines board debate and cohesiveness in the board. Their arguments encompasses that the cohesiveness in the board will be reduced when board independence is high but will increase board debate. When it comes to board diversity, they noted that it improves debates but becomes negative if the board becomes too diversified and will lessen cohesiveness. Finally, they assert that increase in conflict norms will effectively enhance relationships between board diversity, independence and size and debate.

Though the model has not been tested empirically by the authors, it goes beyond the conventional characteristics of board members, to encompass the behavioral measures of board effectiveness. The figure 2.2 below shows a board effectiveness framework of Levrau and Van den Berghe (2007).

Figure 2.2: Levrau and Van den Berghe Board Effectiveness of board Framework

2.11 Discussion of the research conceptual framework

The framework portrays what consist of good corporate governance practice. It further shows the prevailing corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks and possible ways to eradicate such challenges. Only few studies have been conducted in Nigeria to ascertain prevailing corporate governance issues, its effect and possible solutions to eradicate them. Thus, there are three main components that either positively or negatively affects good corporate governance in Nigerian banks.

The first section of the figure 2.3 can be classified as board character. They encompass board diversity, board composition (executive and non-executive directors), board committees, board size and leadership duality (chairman and CEO). These board characters are the foundation on which Nigerian corporate governance is built. These mechanisms align with the Anglo-Saxon corporate governance practiced predominantly in the US and UK. Proper implementation of the aforementioned mechanism will amount to effective corporate governance in Nigerian banks. In the component of the first section of figure 2.3 indicates that diversity of the board is not limited to only gender diversity as largely discussed in many literatures. Diversity should, however, include experience, skill, knowledge, qualifications, and demographic representation. Besides diversity, board composition of both executive and non-executive directors is imperative for effective board. The other aspect of the mechanism lays emphasis on the need for separation of the board leadership, as having a chairman and CEO brings check and balances that will ensure each party carries out their duty effectively. Board size and board committees are regarded vital aspect of corporate governance practice that ensures corporate board effectiveness and firm performance. Having technocrats like accountants as part of the audit and remuneration committee members can bring high level of transparency in the financial activities of the organisation.

The second section of figure 2.3 which is on the left side of the framework portrays factors undermining effective corporate governance in Nigerian commercial banks. These factors have been discussed in the literature of this study. The type of ownership structure of Nigerian banks has immensely contributed to factors subverting corporate governance implementation in commercial banks. Concentrated ownership has resulted to lack of independence among the

board members for the fear of losing their jobs. The major shareholder determines who becomes the CEO or a director irrespective of their qualifications, thereby sabotaging prerequisite of being in such delicate position. Corruption among others have been identified as a factor that impair corporate governance and board effectiveness. Corruption resulting from issues of unethical practices, lack of transparency in financial activities and board selection, which undermines performance of banks. Among other factors, multiple board representation in some cases impedes board effectiveness. Multiple representation of a board member questions the loyalty and ability of one to effectively carryout board function in two or multiple companies. This situation is regarded as over-boarding and undermines a director's efficiency in one bank against the other.

The final section of the framework examines the panacea to implement principles of corporate governance in organisations. Several economies in the world have good corporate governance codes on ground, however, proper implementation has been identified as a challenge. Board training and seminars have been identified as one of avenues to ensure efficacy of the board. On another note, ability of government to legislate good policies has been indicated in the framework. Government policies through its institutions like CBN and BOFIA are imperative in punishing the offenders who default in implementing the recommended corporate governance principles. The figure 2.3 below has demonstrated the conceptual framework of this study.

Figure 2.3 Research Conceptual framework on shareholders perception on CG implementation

2.12 Conclusion

The conceptual framework has elaborately examined theories, concepts and models that are associated with the research topic, aim and objectives. It was observed from reviewing theories, models, and concepts that they become viable when it has survived scientific scrutiny. From reviewing the literature, theories and models reveal factors hindering corporate government implementation in Nigerian banks.

The conceptual framework adopted two frameworks of Sharma (2011) and Levrau and Van den Berghe (2007), which was adjusted to suit the research topic, aim and objectives. The framework reveals that government policies and board training, and seminars are vital in achieving board effectiveness and corporate governance implementation.

The next chapter will deal with the research methodological approach adopted in this study. The choice of research method applied was influenced by the research topic, aim and objectives the research wants to achieve.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DESIGN

3.0 Introduction

This chapter deals with methodology employed to achieve the main aim and objectives of this study. Research methodology deals with the systematic approach employed by researcher to address phenomenal issues raised in research (Sahu, 2013). This chapter, therefore, explained the methodology applied to achieve the purpose of this study and the justification for choice of selecting them. It encompasses research philosophy, strategies, design, and sampling, choice of research method and data collection.

3.1 Research Philosophy

The research philosophy was used to ascertain the ontological and epistemological phenomena this work addressed. Saunders *et al.*, (2016) identified five basic research philosophies, which include Positivism, Interpretivism, Pragmatism, critical realism, and postmodernism. However, Collis and Hussey (2014) narrowed it down to two main research philosophies, namely, Positivism and interpretivism. The 'positivism' approach, which is developed from traditions of natural sciences, is used to evaluate the ontological presupposition of the rules, codes and laws governing what people believe in, through experiment, to have a better understanding. On the other hand, 'interpretivism or anti-positivism' philosophical approach opines that there is no single or peculiar method of understanding the world and creates avenue for more exploration (Davies and Hughes, 2014).

In differentiating the dichotomies existing among the research philosophies, Carson *et al.*, (2001) noted that the aims of a study determine which research philosophy should be applied; interpretivism (subjective), positivism (objective) or any of the prior mentioned philosophical approaches. Johnson and Clark (2006) noted that it is paramount to justify the reasons for choice of any methodology and approaches applied in your research.

In achieving the objectives of this study, interpretivism philosophical approach was employed. This is in view of certain advantages it gives, which will not only answer the questions this research posed but proffer panacea to eradicate the phenomena it addresses. One of the most notable advantages why the researcher opined for interpretivism philosophy is that it gives the researcher the opportunity to have in an in-depth understanding of the phenomena. Unlike Positivism philosophy, which limits its work to empiricism, meaning that the final decision is made based on the outcome of scientific experiments. This denies the researcher the ability to physically engage concerned individuals who might be more willing to disclose information contrary to the one updated on internet (Kimani, 2017).

However, interpretivism creates avenue to engage concerned individuals physically and directly, which enhances better understanding and interpretation of the social environment and contexts (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). Moreover, contrary to positivists, whose intention is to test theories through empirical means to ascertain cause and effect (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2008). Opting for interpretivist style accorded the researcher the opportunity to contribute on existing corporate governance theories especially on the areas that are concerns Nigerian corporate governance. This was practically possible because this system gave the interviewer opportunity to engage

stakeholders of Nigerian banks on the areas of corporate governance. The interviewees were able to answer the 'how and what' question designed to achieve the aim and objectives of study.

3.2 Research Approach

Basically, there are two main research approaches, which can be applied by a researcher to achieve intended objectives of a study. They include Deductive and Inductive research approach (Saunders *et al.* 2012; Collins and Hussey 2009). Deductive approach is adopted by researchers whose primary aim is to test theories or conceptual frameworks empirically, usually through quantitative means. It narrows down general inferences to draw to a particular conclusion or solution. On the contrary, Inductive approach develops theory through empirical observation, usually through interviews and other qualitative means. A finding from an empirical observation under inductive approach is used to generalize and proffer solution to an existing phenomenon (Collins and Hussey, 2009). In some situations, some studies do adopt a mixed research approach, especially when the study requires both approaches to achieve its objectives. This type of research is flexible and referred to as 'Abduction method (Saunders *et al.*, 2012).

This study considered inductive research approach above all other approaches. Using the interview, we were able to discover to what extent does the board implement corporate governance in Nigerian banks, the challenges facing its implementation, possible solutions to the challenges and most appropriate to incorporate such changes in Nigerian banks.

3.3 Research Methods

3.3.1 Introduction

In achieving research objectives, many authors and researchers do apply different research methods which they deem appropriate to perfectly arrive at the desired goal of the study. Basically, many studies have identified two main research methods; Qualitative and Quantitative (Abutabenjeh and Jaradat, 2018; Morgan, 2016; Barnham, 2015; Bryman, 2006). The qualitative and quantitative methods are respectively distinguished between words and numerical forms (Morgan, 2016).

However, depending on the objectives of the study, the need to incorporate both research methods may arise. This type of research method can be referred as 'Mixed research methods' (Saunders *et al.*, 2012). Mixed research method can be traced to multiple operationalism and has been in existence for over three decades (Johnson, Onwuegbuzie and Turner, 2007). The process includes collection of data through quantitative means, which will be analysed, and the findings integrated to draw inferences by employing qualitative method (Tashakkori and Creswell, 2007).

To achieve the aim and objectives of this study, we employed qualitative (Semi-structured interview) research method. One of the underpinning advantages of adopting qualitative data collection is that it creates opportunity for an in-depth investigation. According to Barnham (2015), qualitative research offers 'hard and factual data' and more insightful compared to quantitative research. He noted that while quantitative data requires scaled answers, qualitative requires a discussed answer. In the section below (3.5), we have discussed extensively qualitative

research and determinant reasons why the method was opted for compared to the aforementioned research methods.

3.3.2 Mono Method

Qualitative research method gives a researcher the opportunity to employ various data collection techniques like interview to get relevant information from the participants. The data collected is translated through analytical procedures to formulate a conceptual framework (Saunders *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, unlike survey quantitative research methods, which uses tools like questionnaire in data collection, the interview method gives some added advantages to researchers. While use of questionnaire denies one the privilege of meeting the participants face to face, interview involves naturalistic and interactive measures where the researcher and the participants meet face to face and build rapport to gain cognitive access to information available to them.

In carrying out a qualitative study, it is basically expected that researchers should maintain certain standards to give credibility to their work, which includes fittingness, confirmability, auditability, and triangulation (Patton, 2015). However, Pelzang and Hutchinson (2018) argued that though the above enumerated standards are relevant in qualitative study, there is need to incorporate cultural integrity to holistically make the study credible. According Lapan, Quartaroli, and Riemer (2012) cultural integrity involves the ability of the researcher to develop cultural trust by respecting or portrays character which is in tandem with the participants' cultural values. During this study, the cultural integrity is accommodated in the interviews, especially in dealing

with respective interviewees. Nigeria being a highly multicultural country, the shareholders encompass individuals from different ethnic, cultural, and religious background. The pattern of the interview therefore, recognized the culture of the people and channelled the interview in respect to the environment. It also asked questions on how multi-cultural individual directors can enhance corporate board effectiveness.

Furthermore, to carry out qualitative research in a cross-cultural environment like Nigeria, the ability of the researcher to effectively execute such study is always questioned. Pelzang and Hutchinson, (2018) noted some qualities a researcher must possess to carry out a credible study in multicultural or cross-sectional environment. It requires high level of vigilance, and an in-depth understanding of the cultural, political cum social dynamics of the area of study. Possessing such qualities enhances the ability to absorb and eliminate risky deeds that might pose threat to the beliefs, norms, and values of the people, which might undermine the participant's honesty and willingness to convey appropriate information. The researcher been born in Nigeria, understands some of the values attached to socio-political, cultural cum religion in the country. These factors were carefully integrated into the research to make a credible finding.

Qualitative study gives the researcher certain advantage which other research method may not give in carrying out a study. Sahu (2013) noted that it gives the investigator the advantage of discovering and understanding the reasons for people's choice of behaviour. It involves discovering the psychology behind motivations and feelings of individuals. This study adopted qualitative method to ascertain the feelings of shareholders on the implementation, challenges, and possible solutions to address the prevailing corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks.

Moreover, another advantage of adopting qualitative research is that it gives opportunity to researcher to understand individuals experience and attitude (Gunaydin and McCusker, 2015). In this case, semi-structured interview will be used to ascertain from shareholders based on their experiences, the factors that mitigate corporate board effectiveness in Nigerian commercial banks.

3.4 Semi-Structured Interviews

Engaging in an investigative research, interviews are deemed appropriate in data collection to produce quality research that is dependable and credible. Interviews are classified into three; structured, Semi-Structured, and unstructured interviews. Easterby-Smith *et al.*, (2008), argued that structured interviews are recommendable when engaging in positivistic research and a study that requires large-scale information for generalization of findings. Furthermore, Evans and Lewis (2017) expressed the importance of semi-structured as it is relevant in development of research themes. It allows a respondent to answer in their own way without being confined to respond in a particular way. Employing semi-structured interview allows a researcher to explore on the experiences, realities, assumptions and imaginations of the participants on perception the phenomenon under investigation (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Schultze & Avital, 2011).

However, unstructured interview was neither considered in this research. Easterby-Smith *et al.*, (2008) noted that there is high possibility of incorporating poor quality information in an unstructured interview resulting from absent of guiding questions during interview. Moreover, Adams (2015) argued that structured interviews limits researchers' ability to totally ascertain

respondents' point of view as it does not create room for probing, while unstructured interview tends to limit focus on the study as the researcher may deviate from the research objectives.

On the other hand, semi-structured interview is encompassing and creates flexibility through the use of several system and technologies when adopted. Such flexibilities and technologies include adoption of E-interviewing with either skype or zoom (Deakin and Wakefield 2013; Hanna 2012) and by employing telephone or face-to-face interview (Deakin and Wakefield 2013; Hanna 2012). Having diversified opportunity to carry out semi-structure interview is beneficial to users especially where the place of study is different from area where the research is to be carried out. Secondly, in the time of pandemic, technologies will make it easy to achieve the same level of result by using zoom or skype. However, in a situation where one uses questionnaire or other data collection tools, the quality of the data might be undermined where travel is restricted. Furthermore, semi-structured interview if utilized creates high level of rapport between the researcher and participants thereby enhance mutuality that will mitigate positive interview outcome (Brown and Danaher, 2017).

Consequently, this study adopted semi-structured interview in achieving the aim and objectives of the study as it will be vital in achieving the objectives of this study. McNulty *et al.*, (2013) explained that Semi-structured interviews are interpretivist in nature and enhances the opportunity to have an in-depth knowledge of the phenomenon under study. They noted that Semi-structured interview is best in uncovering the reality of corporate governance challenges which are not readily available on the published annual reports.

Other reasons for semi-structured interview adoption in this study is that it allows the researcher to explore subjective viewpoints (Flick, 2009), and collate an in-depth account of individual encounter. Moreover, semi-structured interview allows the researcher to have a schedule which guide and allow the interviewer to ask questions peculiar to research objective and giving the participants the opportunity to respond in their own terms (Evans, 2017). The opportunity to probe interviewee contributed to researcher's choice of selecting semi-structure interview as questionnaires and other structured interviews do not create avenue to probe (Adams, 2015).

Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2007) highlighted some advantages and reasons why wide range of researchers opt for semi-structured interview compared to structured and unstructured interviews. They noted that semi-structured interview is a pertinent data collection method that underpins the researcher's ability to have an in-depth and primary accounts on the respondents' mindset, view and perception on the phenomenon being studied. This type of data collection helps the interviewer to organise the questions in themes to address respectively the intended research objectives. Moreover, it is dynamic in nature, which permits necessary changes considering the flow of the discussion. Unlike the structured interviews that is non-dynamic and have pre-prepared questions that researchers are required to stick to. This study therefore exploited semi-structured interview prerequisites which permits the interviewer to ask unprepared questions (probes) that arose from questions been addressed.

Furthermore, in undertaking an exploratory research, Blumberg, Cooper and Schindler (2014) noted that qualitative research method, such as semi-structured interview is imperative in achieving the overall aim of the study. Which is one of the reasons this method was adopted. Semi-Structured interview helps to make further review on the answers provided by the

participants, especially where more detailed answer is needed or in a situation where the researcher wants to build on interviewee's response (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2007).

Despite the advantages of Semi-structured interviews, Saunders *et al.*, (2016) identified some undermining challenges in employing it during data collection. These underlining factors includes bias that might arise either from the interviewer or interview, cultural differences, credibility, and validity of the information. The researcher had already put into consideration all these constraints of semi-structured interview to produce a quality study.

To ensure the appropriateness of the study, the researcher interviewed fifteen (15) correspondents who are predominantly bank managers that have shares in respective Nigerian banks with substantial knowledge in corporate governance. To attain data saturation, Guest *et al.*, (2006) argued that between 5 to 25 respondents are satisfactory in an interview data collection method especially in phenomenological research like this project. The interviews lasted for minimum of 60 minutes and maximum of 80 minutes. Before engaging the interviewees, they read and signed the consent form which is UWS prerequisite in carrying out this type of research. The interviews were recorded and transcribed, however, six (6) correspondents declined being audio recorded for an undisclosed concern. Notes were taken during the interview especially where the researcher intended to probe while full notes were taken on the interviewees that decline being recorded. As required by the research ethical principle, the participants and company they work in was anonymised and gadgets used were passworded to ensure privacy of the participants.

3.5 Case Study Research

3.5.1 Multiple Case Study

A case study can be referred as extensive research on an existing phenomenon, which its procedure usually employs a real-life scenario (Yin, 2014). The real-life situation might be a case related to either a managerial, event, corporate or change in a process phenomenon (Saunders *et al.*, 2016).

In carrying out case study research, there are several types of case study that a researcher can apply, which solely depends on the nature of the prevailing phenomenon or the objective a study wants to achieve. Flyvberg (2011) argued that the set boundaries on the problem being studied is paramount in defining the case study. To ensure appropriate extensive research, defining your case study underpins the researcher's ability to be conversant with necessary dynamics within the context of the research (Eisenhardt and Graebner 2007).

There are four major types of case study strategy, which were identified by Yin, 2014. These include single case, multiple case, holistic case, and embedded case study. The single case strategy is suitable in a critical extreme or unique case. However, it is applicable where phenomenon under study have been considered by few. The multiple case strategy is employed where more than one case is being investigated. One of the most notable advantages of multiple case is that it creates avenue for a study to be replicated across cases (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). However, Stakes (2016) differs on the replication of case study findings on similar cases. He argues that case study research aligns more to particularisation than generalisation. This implies that a finding in a particular organisation might not be replicable or applicable in eradicating

prevailing phenomenon in a similar organisation. The issue of being non-replicable might be as a result of the different economy (country) and time horizon (period of time) the respective research were carried out. Rule and John (2015) noted that despite the popularity of case study research, there is dichotomy of opinions among authors on its effectiveness on replication as seen in the argument of Stakes (2016) that case studies are definite and not generalisable in all cases.

The Yin's (2014) third and fourth types of cases studies which is holistic and embedded have similar meaning. While holistic case is employed where an organisation is studied as whole, the latter which is embedded, studies each sub-unit of an organisation.

In carrying out this research, multiple case study was employed. Baxter and Jack (2008) expressed that the holistic purpose of a study is necessary in selecting the type of case study to be applied. Furthermore, they noted that any study that has more than one case, that the use of multiple case study becomes inevitable. Furthermore, another factor that prompted the researcher's interest in considering multiple case study among others is because it enhances validity of study. Saunders *et al.*, (2016) argued that increase in number of cases studied, the more valid the study can be, especially in generalisation.

The aim of this study is to ascertain the shareholders perception on corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks. Therefore, application of multiple case was essential ascertaining the similarities and differences among the banks studied, which will be relevant for literature and future research. Vannoni (2014) argued that multiple case study enhances diversified view by comparing different cases. Another reason for employing multiple case study

is that it enabled the researcher to explore more cases and convincing evidence (Gustafsson, 2017). Moreover, employing multiple case study was vital as it created opportunity for solidifying the evidence and making this work more reliable and attractive to wide range of individuals who are interested in this research. Heale and Twycross (2017) argued that multiple case study has stronger and more reliable evidence compared to single case study and they are better for extensive exploration and development of theory. Therefore, having multiple cases will intensify the level of evidence and confidence of those who will utilise this work. Despite advantages associated with multiple case studies, Baxter and Jack (2008) argued that multiple case study is expensive and time demanding. The researcher considered such limitations of multiple case study to achieve the objectives of this study.

To ensure high level of accuracy and ability of result replication, the researcher employed all the banks existing in Nigeria as the population. Top ten Nigerian banks were considered for the sample size, however, only five (5) banks were selected among the top ten banks because of limited access to financial organisations like banks. The outcome of the findings will be replicated in similar sectors which will be relevance in those organisations in achieving quality corporate governance and company performance. This agrees of Yin (2003), who retreated that case study's goal is to analytically generalise.

3.6 Research Ethics

Ethics have been argued to be one of the most critical aspects in research design formulation (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). They defined Ethics as an accepted behaviour that generally guides a

researcher's manner in carrying out a study, especially in connection to the rights of research participants or those that might be affected by it. When carrying out any project, attention should be given to any ethical issues which arise. Schwartz (2017) identified basic procedures that underpin identification of ethical issues that might emerge in carrying out research. It includes i) Awareness (this is identifying moral issues in the environment). ii) Judgement (evaluating proper action to be taken). iii) Intention (it involves prioritising standard above personal values and iv) Behaviour (executing the project based on the objectives). These stages are pertinent to this research considering the sampling environment (Nigeria) being a complex society where religion, culture cum political ideology is dispersed and affects individual's way of reasoning.

There are basic recognisable ethical principles that are paramount when embarking on a study that involves humans. According to Markham and Buchanan (2012), noted that these principles are enshrined in the UN Declaration of Human Rights, the Nuremberg Code, the Declaration of Helsinki, and the Belmont Report. They highlighted that the vital precepts shared by these policies include preservation of human rights and dignity, benefit optimisation and reduction of harm, justice, safety, and protection. These principles however, formed an integral part of this research. That is; protection of the participants of study and keeping them anonymous. The participants were assured of data protection by transcribing the interview to a pass-worded computer which is only accessible to the interviewer. Moreover, they were informed that apart from the purpose of this study, that the excerpts of the interview will not be used for any other purpose. However, in a situation where the need may arise for further use of the excerpts, their permission will be demanded, which they reserve right to either accept or reject.

Among other ethical concerns, Saunders *et al.*, (2016) noted the importance of Informed Consent. This deals with the researcher's ability to enumerate a detailed information and assurance to prospective participants on the implication of their involvement in the research process. It involves letting them know that their participation is without any coercion. Consent forms were created in the cause of carrying out this research, which highlighted to the participants the extent they are protected.

To boost ethical concerns, University of The West of Scotland has through her ethical programme enlightened researchers on how to deal with ethical concerns that might arise in the cause of doing research. To buttress ethical and consent issues, they ensure each researcher meet up with ethical requirements by endorsing and approving the ethical and consent form. The researcher has gone through this process and the procedures implemented. The informed consent forms were signed by both the participants and the researcher to ensure its legality. Moreover, to ensure proper understanding of the contents of the consent form, it is paramount for the researcher to select words that will be averagely understandable (Williams and Anderson, 2018). The researcher, therefore, minimized any ambiguity in choice of words to facilitate swiftness of communication. Finally, the researcher has put into consideration the sampling environment culture and the need to abide by it. This is to avoid risking anything that might either jeopardize the interviewee or interviewer work or life.

3.7 Reliability and Validity of Study

The quality of a research is evaluated and determined by the extent of its reliability and validity (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). They defined Reliability as one's ability to replicate prior research, arrive at the same result when same methodology is applied. To produce a reliable study, there are several factors a researcher considers. These factors are classified into internal (which deals with researcher's ability to maintain certain level of consistency at the time of the research was embarked on) and external factors (which ascertains if the technique for data collection and procedures of analysis will consistently produce similar findings if the same research is carried out (Saunders *et al.*, 2016).

In carrying this research, the researcher recognised the importance of reliability which contributes to how quality of research is rated. Roberts and Priest (2006) argued that reliability deals with the extent a specific test or process of data collection such as questionnaire will generate a likely result in non-identical scenario if nothing has changed. To ensure consistency in results, the researcher eliminated some undermining factors as identified by (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). These factors include participant's error & bias and researcher's error and bias.

Moreover, in as much as reliability is significant in a study, its validity is paramount in rating the quality of research in its entirety. To ensure the validity of this work, the researcher decided to engage in comparative distinction between the results obtained in this study and previous results in a similar study. This procedure was identified as one of the best ways in ascertaining validity of a study (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). This measure of comparing a prior related study to ascertain validity of research has been applied in previous studies. For example, Beckenbach *et al.*, (2009)

in researching the Interpersonal Relationship Resolution Scale compared results of similar studies to the outcome of their studies. Furthermore, Saunders *et al.*, (2016) noted that validation encompasses, the ability of the researcher to verify the collected data, analysis, and interpretation. Though they identified other validation techniques, participants validation is always recommended

Participant's validation is a complex technique, as it requires returning data back to participants for accuracy confirmation of their interviews, which gives them the chance to amend any miscommunication (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). Considering time consuming of this method, and time constraints experienced by the researcher, this type of validation was not employed. However, the researcher knowing the importance proper analytical tool for quality reliable and valid study, used thematic analysis in analysis results of the interview. Applying proper analytical tool has been identified paramount in reliability and validation of research (Mahembe, Engelbrecht and Wakelin, 2016).

3.8 Time Horizon

In determining time horizon of a study, Saunders *et al.*, (2016) noted that it is imperative to identify the type of time horizon which will be suitable in answering the posed research questions. They identified two main types of time horizons: Cross-sectional and Longitudinal studies. The cross-sectional studies intend to address prevailing phenomena especially within a short period of time (Levin, 2006). This type of study can also be referred to as 'snapshot' in research because of short time frame in data collection (Saunders *et al.*, 2016; Levin, 2006).

Contrarily, longitudinal studies align with studies that analyses data over a long period of time. It encompasses collection of several snapshots (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). In carrying out longitudinal studies, Caruana *et al.*, (2015) expressed those measures are repeated or continuous over a long period of time, which can be in years or over a decade.

In carrying out this research, Cross-Sectional studies was employed because of its strengths and suitability to the phenomena under study. Some of its strengths include the ability to ascertain prevailing issues of corporate governance in Nigerian banks. Saunders *et al.*, (2016) argued that this type of study employs survey or qualitative research strategy which was also adopted in this study. Through qualitative research (semi-structured interview), this research will not only understand the challenges of corporate governance in Nigeria but will make recommendation based on responses on how to eradicate corporate governance challenges. Furthermore, this research is constrained to adopt cross-sectional studies because of limited time this research is to be delivered. Caruana *et al.*, (2015) noted the necessity for longitudinal studies, however they argued that where time is a factor, cross-sectional studies should be adopted.

3.9 Selection of Sample Size

The best way to have a perfect outcome from a study will be the ability to investigate all the population concerned with the phenomena under investigation. However, Saunders *et al.*, (2012) identified some reasons why it may be impossible to engage an entire population while carrying out research. Some of the limitations include insufficient fund and time constrains. Easterby-Smith *et al.*, (2015) defined sample as a subset of the population from which evidence is

gathered. That means that from the sample, an inference will be drawn for an entire population. They noted that sampling is applied not only in academic research, but also in policymaking.

Saunders *et al.*, 2012, noted that it is important to engage a reasonable number of samples during the investigation. Selecting a sample out of an entire population have advantage associated to it. For example, it increases the overall accuracy of the result because, the researcher will have more time to get a detailed and quality information from the participants. Moreover, after collection of data, the researcher will have sufficient time to test and check the accuracy of the data before analysing it (Barnett, 2002).

Although the researcher intends to incorporate the entire population of the study, which is the entire major shareholders of Nigerian commercial banks; it will be practically impossible considering the closed nature of businesses in Nigeria, which limits access to the intended interviewees. Besides, it was also observed that in some cases, the major shareholders are reserved and reluctant in participating in interviews for confidential reasons. This is not only challenging in Nigeria, as securing participants to give consents for research in developing economies have proven to be problematic (Benatar, 2002; Lindegger and Richter, 2000). It was also found that the reasons why individuals avoid participation in either interviews or questionnaire is because of risk of losing their jobs, deteriorating relationships with partners, or been held responsible for divulging confidential information (Shareia *et al.*, 2005). Considering the above challenges, the researcher decided to include shareholders of Nigerian commercial banks who are also in managerial position in respective banks. This is to have a reasonable number of interviewees and to boost the robustness of the research.

Table 3.1 below indicates respective Nigerian commercial banks certified to operate either locally, internationally, or both. It indicates the population of the cases under study. However, table 3.2 shows the number of actual cases used. Three Interviews were carried out from the respective cases shown on table 3.2, making them total of fifteen (15) respondents.

Table 3.1 Banks with local or international authorization (Case population)

S/N	Banks with International Authorization	S/N	Banks with local Authorization
1	ACCESS BANK PLC	1	CITIBANK NIGERIA LIMITED
2	DIAMOND BANK	2	ECOBANK NIGERIA PLC
3	FIDELITY BANK PLC	3	HERITAGE BANK LIMITED
4	FIRST CITY MONUMENT BANK PLC	4	KEYSTONE BANK LIMITED
5	FIRST BANK NIGERIA LIMITED	5	STANBIC IBTC BANK PLC IBTC
6	GUARANTY TRUST BANK PLC	6	STANDARD CHARTERED BANK LIMITED
7	SKYE BANK PLC	7	STERLING BANK PLC
8	UNION BANK FOR NIGERIA PLC	8	UNITY BANK PLC
9	UNITED BANK OF AFRICA PLC	9	WEMA BANK PLC

10	ZENITH BANK PLC		
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Table 3.2 Nigerian commercial banks employed for the case study.

1	First Bank Nigeria limited
2	Zenith bank Plc
3	United Bank for Africa
4	Fidelity Bank
5	Union Bank Nigeria plc

Table 3.3 Portfolios and qualifications of interview participants

Respondents	Position	Qualification	Gender	Branch
A	Zonal Manager	PhD	Male	Enugu
B	Non-Executive Director	MBA	Male	Lagos
C	Top Senior manager	B.Sc. Accounting; M.Sc. Finance	Female	Enugu
D	Manager	M.SC Banking and Finance	Male	Enugu

E	Branch manager	MBA, M. Sc. Finance	Female	Enugu
F	Director	Ph.D. MBA	Male	Lagos
G	Branch manager	MBA	Female	Lagos
H	Senior manager	MBA	Male	Enugu
I	Marketing Manager	B.Sc. Marketing & MBA	Female	Enugu
J	Senior manager	M.Sc. & ICAN	Male	Abuja
K	Manager	MBA and M.Sc. Business Management	Male	Abuja
L	Manager	M.Sc. Economics	Male	Enugu
M	Senior Manager	Ph.D.	Female	Enugu
N	Manager	MBA	Female	Lagos
O	Manager	M.SC Finance	Male	Enugu

3.10 Description of Five Cases on Corporate Governance Implementation in Nigerian Commercial Banks

3.10.1 Introduction

Case studies were presented on this section as part of empirical research. Adopting case study gives a practical understanding of corporate governance implementation in the Nigerian commercial banks. The five cases selected were those that met the criteria enumerated in the

methodology, which are banks authorised by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to operate locally and internationally. Among them are, First Bank Nigeria limited, Zenith bank Plc, United Bank of Africa, Fidelity Bank and Union Bank Nigeria plc.

3.10.2 Case Study One: First Bank Nigeria Limited

The First Bank Nigeria Limited is a multinational bank which has been sustaining its financial services for over 126 years and considered as the most leading bank in West Africa. They offer range of corporate and retail financial services via more than 57,000 branches to over seventeen million customers with net asset estimated to \$15,000,000,000 (fifteen billion dollars). The headquarters of the bank is situated in Lagos with its subsidiaries in countries like Ghana, Guinea, The Gambia, Republic of Congo, Sierra-Leone, Senegal, and United Kingdom.

The bank's corporate purpose is to prioritise the need of stakeholders, partners, and customers, and ensure great customer experience in their organisation. Considering their efforts to standardise the operation the bank, they were rated the most valuable bank brand in Nigeria from 2011-2016 and the best retail bank for period of eight years (2011-2018). The vision of the bank is *'To be Africa's bank of first choice'* and with its mission *'to remain true to their name by providing the best financial services possible'*.

3.10.2.1 Corporate Governance in First Bank Nigeria

First bank Nigeria, just like any other commercial banks subscribe to principles of corporate governance and perform their activities as recommended by the CBN. They acknowledged that

effective corporate governance is vital to enhance the interest of stakeholders. Oversight function is carried out by the board directors who ensure specific statutory and regulatory requirements are implemented. First bank Nigeria is largely diversified and has outgrown limiting diversity to gender, but the board encompasses individuals with experience, different educational and cultural background.

The board is made up of ten (10) directors; seven of the directors are non-executive directors, two independent non-executive directors and one Executive director. These board members are selected base on their experience, integrity, independence of opinion. However, having greater number of non-Executive directors aligns with world best practices. To achieve board effectiveness, the board convene quarterly, and members are assigned into committees like Audit committee and Remuneration committee.

3.10.3 Case Study 2: Zenith Bank Plc

Zenith Bank which was established in the year 1999 delivers financial services to nexus of individuals across Africa, predominantly in Anglophone West African countries. The company asset is estimated in total of \$16.1 billion. The bank has developed diverse service delivery avenues by engaging of its people, information, and communication technology. Considering Zenith bank's market capitalization, profitability and total assets, the bank can be considered as one of the largest banks in Nigeria. The bank remains a tier 1 rated bank and claimed to have exceeded customers' expectations. The bank has the vision of building a top-notch brand that will be reputable in the international financial services space. Moreover, they also have the vision

of building great customer service and performance not neglecting the need to maximize shareholders wealth. The core values of the institution include integrity, professionalism, excellence, ethics, commitment, transparency, and service. The bank business encompasses Investment, retail, commercial and corporate banking.

3.10.3.1 Corporate Governance in Zenith Bank PLC

The bank noted that they maintain the highest standard of corporate governance within the bank and its groups. The corporate governance practice is always subjected to review to ensure the bank is abreast with best practices. The bank indicated in the annual report that they abide with corporate governance codes issued by CBN and SEC (Security and Exchange Commission) respectively. The ownership structure of Zenith bank is dispersed, and no individual own more than 20% of the bank's total shares. Just like in the first bank, the board are charged with setting strategic goals, monitoring, and ensuring corporate governance implementation. The board is made up to 12 board members, six non-executive directors which includes the chairman and 6 executive directors, CEO being among the executive directors. Unlike First bank, Zenith bank equitably shares its board into Executive and Non-Executive directorship. Three of the Non-Executive directors are independent.

The board discharge its duties through different committees which include Audit, asset and liability, remuneration and risk management committees. The bank did not emphasize on the diversity of the but noted fairness in selection of the board of members. The banks set remuneration in three ways; sitting allowance (non-executive directors), fixed remuneration

based on responsibilities and variable remuneration based on financial performance of Zenith Bank. Furthermore, the bank has adopted the whistleblowing policy within the bank and its group. This is with the aim of uncovering irregularities that might undermine corporate governance and company performance.

3.10.4 Case Study 3: United Bank for Africa PLC (UBA)

United Bank for African is known as a pan-African financial services provider. The bank has metamorphosed over the years since 1949 and later, took over the asset and liability of defunct British and French Bank Limited (BFB). For the first time, the bank listed its shares in Nigerian Stock Exchange in 1970 and was the first bank in Nigeria to ever make an initial public offering. In 2005, there was a positive drastic change in the bank resulting from merger and acquisition between them and Standard Trust Bank. However, they resolved to maintain the name, UBA (United Bank for Africa). The bank boost of about 20,000 direct and support staff and it headquarter located in Lagos, Nigeria. They have about 20 subsidiaries in over 20 African countries and offices in Paris, London, and New York. The group total assets are estimated to be about US\$14 million with about 13,355 employees. The bank has banking subsidiaries in Nigeria, Mali, Congo, Tanzania, Senegal, Mozambique, Liberia, Uganda, Benin, and Ivory coast.

UBA intends to be a model for African businesses through creation of ultimate value for their stakeholders, observing the highest standard of professionalism and ethics, and to build an institution that will be relevant in the forceable future. The bank vision is to be undisputed and

dominant in lending financial services in Africa. They want to achieve this vision by rendering excellent services and prioritizing their customer need irrespective of sector or segment.

3.10.4.1 UBA PLC Corporate Governance

Good corporate governance is considered as one of the core values in UBA PLC and they have noted the importance of implementing good corporate governance principles as it is paramount in the operation of their businesses. The bank is guided by CBN corporate governance, Security and Exchange Commission code of corporate governance, and their own governance charters. The bank highlighted having their own governance charters which complement the existing corporate governance guidelines. Their idea of 'own governance charter' is unique as it has not been found in other analysed banks.

To guarantee highest standard of corporate governance, its implementation and effectiveness, three structures have been created to ensure they are executed. The three structures include:

- Board of directors
- Board committees
- Executive management commission

UBA recognised the importance of leadership duality by separating the office of chairman and CEO and being occupied by respective individuals. This practice of separation of board leadership is commonly practiced across Nigerian banks and other developed economies of the world, as it is regarded as the best practice. The board has total number 18 members, 9 executive directors

and 9 non-executive directors. The chairman constitutes part of the non-executive director with two independent non-executive directors, while the CEO forms part of executive directors.

The board discharge its duties through different committees, which encompasses audit and governance, credit, risk management and finance and general-purpose committee. The chairman is charged with coordinating the business of the organisation while the CEO engages in day-to-day activities of the company and ensuring implementation of mapped out strategy by the board.

UBA retreated the need for protection of shareholders and make efforts to effectively communicate with shareholders. the shareholders are rightly notified for meetings and given opportunity to give their opinions and vote during the General Meetings. Protection of each shareholder irrespective of their equity interest or social status. The bank expressed that they engage their board members to enhance the skill and knowledge of the board members.

3.10.5 Case Study 4: Fidelity Bank PLC

Fidelity Bank Plc is a licensed commercial bank in Nigeria authorized to operate internationally by the national banking regulator and the CBN. The bank was established in the year 1987 and has been a major player and reputable financial institution. The 2005 bank reform by then former Governor of CBN, Professor Charles Soludo mandating banks to have capital base not less than 25 billion Naira (₦25,000,000,000) resulted to banks merging and bigger banks acquiring the others (Clementina and Isu, 2015). Fidelity bank to ensure its continuity in rendering great financial services to its wide range of customers, acquired FSB International bank Plc and Manny Bank Plc, which led to the bank being ranked in the top ten among Nigerian commercial banks in

2011, accessing by capitalization, it was respectively ranked 7th in Nigeria and 25th in African continent.

Considering the efforts of the bank over years, they boost of total asset worth over US\$4.2 billion (NGN:1.4 trillion) and its shareholders equity estimated to be over US\$610 million (NGN: 203 billion). The bank has over 400,000 diverse shareholders and 240 business channels to reach out to 4 million plus customers. Fidelity bank was initially listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange in 2005 and its headquarters in Lagos state, Nigeria.

3.10.5.1 Fidelity Bank Plc Corporate Governance Code

The bank expressed the importance of corporate governance in the day-to-day activities of their financial services. The corporate governance section of the bank annual report is paramount as it intends to update the shareholders on how they have discharged the fiduciary responsibilities entrusted in them in relation to governance and how the bank have complied with the relevant statutory regulation. The bank has an acronym CREST (Customer First, Respect, Excellence, Shared Ambition and Tenacity) which serves as a guideline relevant to sustain growth of the business and good relationship with their stakeholders.

The bank, just like most of the Nigerian commercial banks aligns its operation with the policies and provisions of CBN corporate governance codes for Banks and Discount Houses in Nigeria, Company and Allied Matters Act (CAMA), Security and Exchange Commission (SEC) and rules issued by the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The aforementioned regulatory body codes and policies are detailed enough to cover issues like board composition and management, shareholders, and

other stakeholders right, code of ethics, board committees and process, whistle blowing and appraisal. Fidelity bank's quest to remain a major competitor in the rendering financial services necessitate their intention to ensure full compliance of the new corporate governance codes by the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN).

Fidelity Bank Plc reiterated that the board members are imperative in corporate governance implementation in Nigerian commercial banks. To ensure effective governance in their board, Fidelity Bank boast of 15 board members which include seven (7) Executive directors, the CEO being among them and 8 on-Executive directors of whom two (2) are independent. The bank noted that their remuneration policy was created to address the compensation of both the Executive and Non-Executive directors. The priority of the remuneration policy is to attract and retain talent, skill and experience required to effectively manage the operation of the bank. The board is made up of several committees like Audit which is dominated by NED and shareholders representatives. Other committees include, management, Asset and Liability, operational risk and management, and other committees. The bank also put measures to avoid insider trading by prohibiting concerned individuals and all those related to them in any way from having access to company's securities at specified period.

The bank expresses the importance of board diversity, especially gender inclusion both at directorial and management level. They noted that findings have shown that female directors and managers possess skills, ideas and insights that are pertinent in effectively serving their diverse customers. Finally, the board is keen on external view over their performance, therefore they engage in shareholders' complaint management policy. Such policy creates room to enable

shareholders to share their concerns about the affairs of the bank, which will be reviewed and attended to.

3.10.6 Case Study 5: Union Bank of Nigeria Plc

Union Bank history is dated back to 1836 during the time of William IV when British merchants obtained a royal charter to carry out banking businesses in the Caribbean. Upon passage of bill by the British parliament for banks to expand beyond Caribbean, the British merchants formed colonial banks which started operating in Nigeria in 1917. In the year 1925, Colonial bank was acquired by Barclays Bank DCO (Dominion, Colonial and Overseas).

The name Barclays DCO was changed after the bank was incorporated in Nigeria in 1969 and has its name changed to Barclays Bank of Nigeria. The aim was to comply with the then new banking laws which was enacted in 1968. For the first, the shares of the bank were listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) in 1971. A year later, the Federal Government of Nigeria acquired 51.67% of Barclays bank, therefore becoming the majority shareholder. The remaining 40% of the shares was later sold to Nigeria public, which resulted to 100% local ownership. To reflect absolute acquisition of Barclays bank Nigeria Plc by Nigerian government and individuals and to abide by banking and investment laws, the bank's name was changed to Union Bank of Nigeria Plc. Moreover, the ownership of Federal Government of Nigeria in the bank was fully divested in 1993.

Union Bank of Nigeria plc has the vision of being the most reliable and trusted financial service partner. The mission is to enhance standard of lives by delivering simplest, best solution and

guaranteeing most possible experience at all times. The asset base of the banks is estimated to be NGN1.87 trillion and total equity of NGN252 billion. The customers are over 5.8 million with 289 sales and service centres and 2,362 direct employees.

3.10.6.1 Corporate Governance in the Union Bank of Nigeria

The CBN corporate governance code of 2014, the Securities and Exchange commission corporate governance of 2011 and Banks and other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) of 1991 and other relevant statutes contributed to the bedrock in which Union Bank corporate governance practices are built. The bank highlighted the need for full implementation of these codes as it is imperative to ensuring board effectiveness, transparency to the shareholders and other stakeholders.

To further enhance board effectiveness and ensure corporate governance implementation, the bank appoints independent consultants who appraise the performance of the board and report back to CBN and shareholders during the Annual General Meetings (AGM). This process will help the bank to maintain highest level of ethical practices. Union Bank has the policy of complaints management. This is an avenue created for wide range of customers and shareholders' voices to be heard. It serves as a feed back to the performance and character of the board. In situations where member of a board, management or staff wants to report any mismanagement, or inappropriate activities in the bank, a whistleblowing procedure was created for this purpose. Whistleblowing encourages individuals who wish to remain anonymous to report irregularities that might undermine company performance.

In the Union Bank, the board are charged with duty of overseeing the management of the bank. the board is consisting of sixteen (16) board members, five (5) executive directors who include the CEO and 11 NED. One of the NED is the chairman and two Independent NED. The board discharge their duties through several committees and sub-committees. The committees in Union bank include Audit, board credit, remuneration and Nomination and board risk management committee. The board meet regularly to discuss and tackle challenges. Union banks up to 10 minutes in the last accounting year.

3.10.7 Summary

This section presents the five cases used in this study in terms of shareholders perception on corporate governance implementation in Nigerian commercial banks. The five banks were chosen based on their authorization by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to operate locally and internationally. The banks are ranked among the first-tier banks in Nigeria. The banks include First Bank Nigeria Plc, Zenith Bank Plc, United Bank for Africa, Fidelity Bank Plc and Union bank of Nigeria Plc.

The corporate governance of each case was evaluated, and it was observed that they all indicated their intension to uphold the highest standard of corporate governance as recommended by CBN, Securities and Exchange Commission and other regulatory bodies. The board of directors are saddled with responsibilities of ensuring corporate governance is implemented in each bank. All the corporate governance guidelines and codes have been enshrined in company books; however, effective implementation becomes the challenge.

Table 3.4 Linking Objectives/Research Questions to Interview Questions

Primary Objectives	Research Questions	Interview question
To examine and understand the prevalent issues of corporate governance in Nigerian Banks	What are the prevailing issues of corporate governance in Nigerian commercial banks?	In your opinion, what might be the general issue surrounding corporate governance in Nigerian commercial banks?
		What do you think is the reason(s) why Nigerian banks are yet to holistically adopt the corporate governance codes?
To critically evaluate the influence of those corporate governance issues and how they affect current corporate governance status of Nigerian banks.	What are the effects of these corporate governance issues on the current corporate governance status of Nigerian banks?	To what extent does lack of diversity (inclusion of women and people of different ethnic group) affect board effectiveness?
		To what extent does separation of role of chairman and Chief Executive Officer fit in into the Nigerian environment?
		What do you think about multiple board representation by a directorship?
		How has religion contributed to implementation of corporate governance in Nigeria?
Does voluntary withdrawal of a director decrease the share value of your bank?		

		<p>To what extent do you think that lack of board diversity might affect board effectiveness in implementing corporate governance principles?</p>
		<p>What do you think about government bailout on stressed banks, which might undermine corporate board effectiveness?</p>
		<p>To what extent can a government representative in the board bring about corporate board effectiveness?</p>
		<p>To what extent do you think combination of rule base and principal base will be efficient in implementation of corporate governance?</p>
		<p>In what ways can the board be educated, informed and encouraged on the importance of implementing corporate governance codes?</p>
<p>To examine the process of implementing the suggested changes</p>	<p>What are the appropriate ways to implement the findings?</p>	<p>In your opinion, how can these two individuals be empowered to bring transparency in the board (Chairman and CEO)?</p>
		<p>In what ways can pension funds contribute in enhancing board effectiveness?</p>

		How can different shareholders align their different interest to make the board of directors effective?
		In what ways can government ensure proper implementation of codes of corporate governance in Nigerian commercial banks?
		What do you think are the necessary step to enhance board effectiveness towards checkmating financial reporting by the management?
		The issue of CEO compensation has triggered dichotomy of opinion across companies. In your own opinion, what could the best way to set directors remuneration?

3.11 Data Analysis

3.11.1 Thematic Analysis

Thematic Analysis (TA, hereafter) has been identified as one of the most used analytical methods in qualitative studies (Braun and Clarke, 2006). They argued that it offers researchers desired theoretical flexibility and accessible approach in analysing qualitative data. Castleberry and Nolen (2018) in identifying the benefits of TA to researchers, ascertained that it enhances the ability of a researcher to identify, analyse and group themes within data collected. Through themes, it minimizes the data volume and creates flexibility that boost merging with other data analysis

method. In describing the wide usage of TA and its importance in qualitative study, Braun and Clarke (2006) described it as 'foundational method for qualitative analysis'.

O'Holleran *et al.*, (2018) noted that TA is paramount in inductive study which aids in getting answer to the inquiry. Inquires can be ascertain through qualitative method like semi-structured and unstructured interviews. However, Saunders *et al.*, (2016) argued that TA is not peculiar to a definite philosophical approach, but the assumptions of a study determine how to employ TA in data interpretation. Its systematic approach creates orderliness and logic in qualitative data analysis.

Considering the objectives of this study, which is to ascertain shareholders perception on corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks. Semi-structured interview was employed in data collection to have an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon under study. The use of semi-structured interviews is based on the arguments of O'Holleran *et al.*, (2018) that TA is useful in analysing qualitative data, especially through semi-structured interviews that permits in-depth inquiry on phenomenon.

Saunders *et al.*, (2016) identified six ways TA analysis can be useful to researchers in carrying out qualitative studies and they are as follows:

- It boosts the ability of comprehending large and distinctive amount of qualitative data.
- TA is essential in integrating data that are related which were drawn respectively from transcripts and note.
- With help of TA, themes and patterns are identified from data set which creates avenue for further exploration.

- It helps in developing thematic description of transcribed data.
- Based on ostensive thematic patterns and relationship, TA helps in developing, testing and explanation of theories.
- Finally, it is essential not only in drawing conclusions but also in verifying them.

To adequately apply TA in analysing interview data, this study employed the six-step process recommended by (Creswell, 2003). One of the major advantages of these six distinctive Creswell’s frameworks is its iterative nature which allows repetition. Thus, allowing researchers to ‘do and redo’ until collected data are translated and interpreted appropriately.

Table 3.5: Six-Steps of Thematic Analysis

Stage	Summary
Step1: Preparation of data for analysis	Stage one deals with transcribing interviews and typing of the notes taken during the fieldwork in preparation of data analysis.
Step2: Reading and re-reading	This entails getting familiar with data when producing the transcripts of the interview and typing of other associated notes. It generally helps to have a lucid understanding of data.
Step 3: Coding of the data	This stage involves categorizing of data with similar meaning. Categorizing or grouping of data helps in comprehension of the meaning of collated data. In coding, it encompasses labelling each unit of data extracted from transcripts, documents or other sources.

Step 4: Developing of theme description	At this stage, different codes are merged to create lesser themes, usually between 5-7 themes. The themes are used as headings in the findings reported.
Step 5: Explaining themes to transmit findings	Extensive discussions of the developed themes are done narratively to report the findings of the collated data. Quotations and citations of participants are further used to support themes.
Step6: Interpretation of Data	Lastly, this is where findings are used to either confirm or challenge past research submissions. It helps researchers to make amendments, contribute new knowledge or theories.

Source: Creswell (2003)

3.12 Pilot Study

A pre-testing was carried out by engaging members of the public, including managers in different capacities who are knowledgeable about the topic under research. A sample of seven participants were engaged. However, at the end of the pilot study, only six interviews were conducted. The researcher was able to adjust where there were complexities and, in a situation, where respondents have noted the need for restructuring of questions without changing the intention of asking such question.

Notwithstanding the pilot study interview respondents limited knowledge in the area of study, most of the participants are knowledgeable about corporate governance and semi-structured interview design. Besides the participants of the pilot study, the lead supervisor of this research and two other senior lecturers at respective universities helped in reshaping the interview questions for more clarity and understanding. The outcome of critical assessments contributed to the final interview questions of this study.

3.13 Conclusion

This chapter has presented the methodology adopted in carrying this study. It analysed different methods of research and adopted the suitable one in achieving the aims and objectives of this work. Moreover, the next chapter extensively presented the analysis of findings using Thematic Analysis.

Chapter 4: Data Analysis and presentation

4.1: Introduction

This chapter extensively deals with data analysis and presentation of the study which deals with shareholders perception on corporate governance implementation in Nigerian commercial banks. Applying case study research method as earlier stated in the research method, semi-structured interviews were conducted in the top ten rated Nigerian banks licensed to operate both locally and internationally. The interview questions used to obtain data were categorised into three (3) groups with the aim to achieve the primary objectives of this research. The first category focused on the prevailing issues undermining corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks. The second category addressed the effects of such corporate governance issues in effective operation of banks, while the last category focused on the possible panacea to ensure proper implementation of CG principles and recommended changes in Nigerian commercial banks.

To adequately present the analysed data, this chapter is divided into five main sections (4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, 4.5) which was further split into other subsections. The first section (4.1) addressed the board leadership and structure issues; section (4.2) focused on the dichotomy of interests among different shareholders; section (4.3) discussed the ownership structure issues in Nigerian Banks; section (4.4) chiefly addressed the challenges associated with bank distress and bailout funds; while section (4.5) extensively discussed the proffered solution for proper implementation, adequate monitoring, and training. The last section (4.6) provides the summary and conclusion of this chapter.

4.2. Board Structure and Leadership Issues

In ensuring proper corporate governance implementation in banks, the leadership structure of the bank remains paramount. Gaps in boards leadership structure is associated with corporate scandals that have overwhelmed some Nigerian banks and other financial institutions globally (Onakoya *et al.*, 2018). In identifying the general issues undermining corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks, 10/15 of the respondents who remain unanimous are of the opinion that lack of quality board leadership remains the bottleneck surrounding sound corporate governance in Nigerian commercial banks.

To explicitly analyse leadership issues undermining board effectiveness, this section was further split into three subsections to discuss the following: a) lack of corporate governance implementation, b) Unethical leadership and c) lack of board diversity (religious, knowledge and gender representation).

4.2.1 Lack of Corporate Governance Implementation

Leadership challenges has become a factor which has created gap in effective corporate governance in Nigerian banks. Moreover, leadership challenges in Nigerian banks could be linked to their inability to holistically implement CG principles and guidelines. The semi-structured interview conducted shows that 13/15 of the interviewees are convinced that a lot needed to be done in the areas of ensuring proper implementation and execution of existing CG codes by the board. For example, Respondent D has this to say:

.... If corporate governance principles and guidelines are holistically or to a great extent adopted, it will create value for all concerned. But some individuals who benefit from noncompliance of the corporate governance codes will cease to benefit from their selfish interest. Those individuals are basically part of the board and always want to maintain unworkable corporate governance for their self-interest.

The statement above shows that leadership crisis is deep rooted in Nigerian banking industry. This means that many board members of banks still prioritise their personal gain above the concerns of all the stakeholders especially the shareholders who are the major fund providers of the banks. The evidence further buttresses the claims of Agency theorists who are of the opinion that human beings are intrinsically self-centred, which mitigates principal-agent conflict (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

Despite lack of corporate governance implementation, most of the interviewees agreed that there are great corporate governance codes and principles in place for banks operation yet lack of its proper implementation is still an underlying challenge that needed to be eradicated. However, the issue of controlling interest shareholders in determining who gets each position in the board has been noted as an underlying factor that subverts corporate governance implementation and board effectiveness. These few individuals (major shareholders) do not prioritise individual qualifications and quality in getting board member job but only consider their cronies who will consider them above general welfare of the company. One the interviewees labelled Respondent K has this to say about board members:

... Many of them (influenced by the controlling shareholders) are interested in just making the money and concentrating the organization and control in few individuals that are related to them. They do not think about separation of functions (between executive and nonexecutive directors) to ensure achievement of corporate governance principles.

Lack of CG compliance by these banks has also resulted to them being distressed and unable to discharge their obligations at one point or the other. Some of these obligations might involve unable to release deposited funds back to customers or investment repayment to investors. In attempting the question on level of CG compliance in Nigerian banks, respondent B said:

... Honestly, we are having few challenges of total compliance, that is why few banks are distressed. Hopefully, the government should partner with them (Chartered Institute of Bankers) to a complimentary law that will punish offenders, which will deter future offenders.

Contrary to the majority opinion by the interviewees that there are great CG codes on ground for Nigerian banks, 3/15 of the respondents expressed that Nigerian bank have a lot to do in attaining the goals of CG. They also expressed their disappointments on the implementation of the existing codes. When asked if Nigerian banks have fully adopted the codes of CG? This is what the Interviewee G has to say:

...No, not at all. We have a long way to go in that. The code of corporate governance entails a lot and if you look at organizations like banks, you will discover largely that they are far from attaining the goals of corporate governance.

Despite the differentiating opinions of the interviewees on the level of CG codes implementation, they all agreed that more needed to be done to ensure holistic implementation, which will be favourable to all the stakeholders, who are victims of lack of compliance in CG implementation.

4.2.2 Unethical Leadership

One of the identified challenges of leadership is unethical behaviour by the board. During the interview, it was understood that trying to attain some social status is one of the major factors that contributes towards the greedy and selfish representation of the board members. Some of these board members start to live above their means and wants to be seen among the elites in the society. When probed Respondent D on what might be the reasons behind unwavering selfish interest by directors in Nigerian banking industry? This answer was given:

... Generally, I tend to see it that it is a class (social status) issue and societal expectation issue. In as much as issue of pushing on to make profit is the aim of banking industry, many of the owners want to belong to certain class and that have led them to compromising. The compromise includes lack of full implementation of things (bank guidelines), lay down rules as expected in corporate governance. Such that those compromises create room for their personal gains or group gains. So, greed and way of life is affecting corporate governance implementation because the directors or the owners of banks prioritize their personal gains over the companies gain... Respondent D

Critically looking at the sentiments of the above respondents, it shows that there is likely collusion between the owners (controlling interest holders against other shareholders) and the

board members. This assertion gave rise to inquiry into ownership structure of Nigerian commercial banks which was discussed later in this chapter.

On the other hand, it was found that some boards exhibit unethical behaviour when the company makes loss. The board members tend to cover up their losses by declaring fake profit in the company's account. This kind of behaviour is not objective and deceitful to both the shareholders and prospective investors because, the balance sheets inform both the shareholders and investors on their next line of action. That is whether to invest, sale shares or any other necessary actions. When carrying out the interview, 13/15 of the interviews expresses their satisfaction on the level at which different boards monitor and scrutinise their financial statements before making it available to the public. However, they argued that more is needed to be done as a Nigerian bank that declared huge profits in 2018 was distressed in 2019. On how to tackle issues of false profit declaration by banks, one the respondents (H) said:

...The board should be highly objective, transparent and should insist on accountability in the activities of the bank. And when there is low profit, they should recognise and accept it that way. However, the mitigating factors of low profit should be investigated as well. The board should do what is right and not just reporting what the shareholders want to hear. That is being prudent. Window dressing and inflating the profits to pay high dividends should be avoided by the management.

The response above is an indication that members of the board are more eager to keep their jobs and receive positive recommendation based on performance than being prudent. The accounting prudence concept suggest that liabilities and profits should be recognised in the company's

account without being altered. This is to portray fair and realistic view of financial statements to avoid over/under estimation of figures. It's suggested that rather than manipulation of figures to declare profit when company has not made any, investigation should be launched to ascertain the reasons why the company yielded low profit. When the Interviewee H was probed on board ensuring that prudence is maintained banks, this is the given response:

...The audit committee should always review the financial reports by the management alongside the external auditor. This will bring proper check and balances in the organization...

Considering the response on ensuring the board observing prudence despite the outcome of the accounts, it still boils down to ethical consideration. Which means, the board should be able to appoint a knowledgeable external auditor who will independently without any prejudice examine the books of the banks. Apart from the external auditor prowess, some respondents expressed the need for expertise in the sub-committees of the board like audit committee. So that they can conveniently monitor and control any financial malpractices that might arise by management doings.

It is also noticeable that some members of the board are ignorant of actions that might amount to unethical behaviour by them. On questions related to unethical behaviour by the board, 12/15 of the interviewees agreed that both management and board still divert banks fund for their personal use, and sometimes collect loans without due process. Even though those funds might be paid back, there are risks of losing such cash when there is loss of job or fatalities. In defining general challenges facing CG in Nigerian banks, respondent O has this to say:

...The major issues surrounding CG in Nigerians banks includes lack of transparency, misappropriation of funds, unethical practices in banks and diversion of companies fund for unofficial use...

The assertion above means that many Nigerian banks will continue to be distressed from time to time and will continue to seek for government bailout if proper monitoring is not enforced within the board. The findings show the need for proper orientation and culture of board working for the interest of the shareholders and avoid any unethical practice that might undermine the interest of the bank.

4.3 Respective Shareholders Interest Challenges

Basically, most researchers pay more attention to agent-principal conflict compared to internal conflict between the principals (controlling shareholders and minority shareholders). This theme pays attention on how minority shareholders' interests are been subdued in the Nigerian banking sector. The issue of controlling and minority shareholder interests could be referred as global phenomenon especially in emerging economies where CG implementation is weak. This conflict between the controlling shareholders and minority shareholders can amount to tunnelling, where the majority investors usurp the wealth of the minority investors (Anderson, Chi and Liao, 2019). On the contrary, protection of minority investors is gaining ground in developed economies as several reforms have been made to ensure the interest of minority shareholders are protected, especially in an event of mergers and acquisition (Burunciuc and Gonenc, 2020).

In carrying out this research interview, 11/15 of the interviewees agreed that there are massive disparities between minority and majority shareholders protection in Nigerian banks. During the interview, some of the respondents focused on how different shareholders could align their interests, so that each shareholder's interest will be protected. Respondent A has this to say on how different shareholders could align their interests:

... The board should care for all the different shareholders and all other stakeholders. Different shareholders should not overemphasise their selfish interest but should focus on what will enhance the profitability of the company in general. The major concern of all the shareholders should be, is the board doing the right thing? This will be achievable by everyone putting behind their respective interest to the interest of the entire shareholders...

From the above response, it shows the importance of leadership as the board of directors are among the vital individuals that can bring harmony among different shareholders. Therefore, for board to effectively discharge their directorial duties, it is important that individual who are qualified and with intention to discharge their duties without prejudice should be voted for. The respondent is also concerned about individuals thinking about the organisation first before their personal gains.

Besides minority and majority shareholders challenges, there are other disagreement among other classes of shareholding individuals. The findings in the interview reveal that some classes of shareholders prefer profits shared as dividends. However, some of these shareholders sense collusion when the board decides to plough back profit made as retain earnings, which might be in the interest of the organisation. Respondents reiterate the need for the board to educate

shareholders, especially ordinary shareholders who are more concerned on short-term profit on how profitable organisation works. This what respondent I has to say:

...Greater percentage of shareholders interest is to have return on their investments, see the growth of the organisation and continuity. However, there are individual differences and perceptions that do arise among shareholders. For example, some prefer profits to be shared as dividends, while others might want it plough back into business as retain earnings. By having board members and other executive members, the shareholders have relinquished to great extent the control and management of the organisation to them. And their decisions are seen to be in the best interest of the organisation. Therefore, that perception that your interest is no longer represented, that the board are now representing their own interest, sometimes might not be true. It is the board that know the in and out of an organisation. So, when they recapitalise through retain earnings, the ordinary shareholders who prefer all profits been shared feel mistreated. Most ordinary shareholders lack knowledge on how banks and other profitable organisation works. So, it will be important that these shareholders should be properly highlighted by the board on the reasons for any decision being made and how it be favourable to all concern...

Furthermore, it was revealed while carrying out interview that some of the prospective directorship candidates do induce different shareholders in Nigerian banks. This is to either win a directorship position or to be re-elected as a director. Some of the interviewees noted that people manipulating their way into sensitive positions is not peculiar to Nigerian politicians alone but also in private and important parastatals like the banking sector. Respondent L has this to say:

...many board members and aspiring board go as far as inducing the shareholders with cash and offers so that they will be voted into the board. However, I suggest the shareholders should set aside their personal interest when voting for directorship positions. They (shareholders) should consider voting for people into the board base on competency, experience and people with managerial acumen acquired over the years...

This evidenced that individual shareholders prioritise their selfish interest above the welfare of the organisation. The intention of these shareholders or group of shareholders might be to receive special favour or treat from these prospective directors if they are eventually voted in for directorial positions.

Besides inducement by the prospective board members, it was also ascertained during the interview that some shareholders vote for a candidate or candidates to compensate them for various reasons not known to other shareholders. Therefore, undermining competency, meritocracy and experience over nepotism, favouritism, and selfish desires. It was understood that this kind of unethical behaviours attract enormous adverse effect on banks. To further buttress the need for merit over individualistic gains, respondent L argued that:

...the membership of the board is not something that should be used as compensations. It should be people who have experience and exposed to the rudiments of banks and have something to offer. Once the standard is compromised and not the basis they were elected, you will discover that they will operate as 'greenhorns' and the bank in general will suffer. Because experience is required and need skills because they are the ones that chat the cause of banking operations...

This is to say that different classes of shareholders should vote for reputable individuals into the board to have their interest protected. Those who have known for ethical leadership based on set precedence should be given headway above those with controversial or questionable character. Such individuals with set precedence will have the ability to attend to all shareholders (minority and majority) interest and eradicate any possible decision that might undermine harmony among divergent shareholders.

4.4. Ownership Structure Challenges in Nigerian Banks

In the financial and non-financial sectors, ownership structure has been identified as a major factor which might undermine or underpin company performance. According to Ozili and Uadiale (2017) there are three levels of ownership structures which includes, high ownership concentration, moderate ownership concentration and disperse ownership. Ownership challenges in Nigerian banks was identified while carrying out this research interview. Therefore, the questions were not structured to ascertain the best ownership structure but to have a general view of how ownership structures affect corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks.

During the interview, 10/15 of the respondents expressed that ownership structures is unequivocally a major setback in absolute implementation of corporate governance in Nigerian banks. Few individuals who own the controlling interest of the banks tends to neglect the concerns of other shareholders who fragmentally among the minority shareholders. Interviewee

D noted that these few individuals live luxurious lifestyles at the expense of other shareholders.

This what the responded D has to say:

...many of the owners want to belong to certain class and that have led them to compromising. The compromise includes lack of full implementation of things (bank guidelines), lay down rules as expected in corporate governance. Such that those compromise creates room for their personal gains or group gains. So, greed and way of life is affecting corporate governance implementation because the directors or the owners of banks priorities their personal gains over the companies gain...

When probed on why the board of directors could not curtail such unethical behaviour of these class of shareholders who owns greater number of stakes in banks, since oversight is one of the major rules of the directors (executive and non-executive directors). The response is:

... Some of these shareholders are also among the executive and non-executive directors, which makes it easy for them to make decisions on behalf of other shareholders, who are usually in the minority. And when you have a majority shareholder or in some cases the founder, other board members do not challenge him/her to avoid job loss... Respondent D

The above indication evidenced that corporate governance guidelines is yet to gain the prominence needed to thrive in the Nigerian banking sector. It further shows that some directors are pawns in the hands of directors who have massive voting slots and determine who becomes a director or member of the board. Their presence in the board also poses a great challenge as unanimous decision cannot be made since one or more shareholders are part of the board. It will

further undermine the independence of directors, who might not want to question decisions made by a director whose shares or interest is significant in the bank.

On the other hand, it was gathered that some groups of owners do not pay attention to the advice of the board, thereby undermining the advisory role of the board. Greater percentage of the interviews are of the opinion that these few individuals who owe significant shares in banks understand fully the principles of corporate governance, especially in decision making. However, they pay no regards to existing principles of CG because they strongly believe they can do whatever they deemed wise since they bank largely belongs to them. This, if unattended to do undermine the interest of minority shareholders and deny them the voice to indicate abnormalities. This is the response of interviewee O on this issue:

...major corporate governance issue in Nigerian commercial banks is issue of he who plays the piper dictates the tune. Most commercial banks are owned largely by very few individuals, and they control the shareholding, and they believe that they have the right to operate and manage the commercial banks the way they like. So, most of them do not pay attention to guidelines and issues of corporate governance which is essentially about separation of functions in order to ensure adequate control and supervision. So, many of them know what it means, but because they are largely the shareholders, they believe it is their enterprise and reserve the right to manage it the way they want...

The response above further buttresses the view of the respondents on the impact of ownership structure in Nigerian banks. That large ownership by few individuals pose threat to full implementation of CG in the Nigerian banking sector. This might be a problem of government

failure and corruption in the appropriate body charged with monitoring the level of CG compliance by these banks. Negligence by these few individuals who own controlling interests in banks have mitigated scandals and distress of some banks. In 2018, Diamond bank suffered financial distress which was traced to poor CG and subsequently forced to merge with another bank to avoid unpleasant liquidation. Chijioke (2018) argued that the CEO was not qualified to handle the position but because of ownership structure of the bank, he assumed the position and made some questionable decisions like board appointments that later caused the bank's adversary. This means that a lot needed to be done on the arrears of checkmating corporate governance challenges banks face regarding ownership structure, especially when it is owned by few individuals or a family.

It was observed during the interview that these controlling shareholders do not only become directors of their respective banks, but also ensure that they exert absolute control of the board. They achieve such control by ensuring that their cronies or individuals related to them are part of the board and management. Respondent O has this to say about board members:

...many of them (influenced by the controlling shareholders) are interested in just making the money and concentrating the organization and control in few individuals that are related to them. They do not think about the separation of functions to ensure the achievement of corporate governance principles...

This argument of Respondent O further buttresses the claim of Chijioke (2018) that some directors who are majority shareholders appoint those that will be loyal to them. These set of directors sometimes are not qualified and fail to question any unfavourable decision of the Chief

Executive. Many of the respondents (14/15) are in favour of dispersed ownership as it brings better checks and balances in the board. The more widespread the ownership structure is, the better the board will be constituted through a proper voting system void of manipulation. It further aligns with the findings of Ozili and Uadiale (2017), that dispersed ownership of banks performs better than highly concentrated ownership.

Moreover, ownership structure has undermined the separation role performed by the chairmen and CEOs respectively in Nigerian banks. The oversighting role of the board is merely paper work for annual reports but is not implemented. This always happens when the ownership of the bank is private. The outcome of such unethical practice in banks has reportedly created an atmosphere that is not enabling for the minority shareholders. In the interview, 13/15 of the interviewees agreed that most banks have both CEO and Chairman but the aim for such positions are not utilized. The respondent H argued that:

...But in most Banks, you will discover that when it is private ownership, the very few shareholders with controlling interest will want their own person to emerge as both the chairman and CEO in order to ensure that his/her interest is properly protected thereby neglecting other minority shareholders. The corporate governance principles aim at proper separation where the board is seen as a superior organ overseeing the activities of the CEO and his managers, but for the purposes of control, the few controlling shareholders want their cronies to be in the board to protect their own interest...

The above assertion is an indication that massive effort is needed to ensure holistic implementation and monitoring of banks' activities by relevant authorities. That is government

authorities that are vested with such powers like the CBN (Central Bank of Nigeria). Such unscrupulous actions of the owner could lead that bank being distressed and subsequently requiring government fund intervention and bailout as the case maybe.

On the contrary, it was observed that there are occasions where disperse ownership can undermine corporate governance implementation in banks that are widely owned by set of individuals. This is in a case where many shareholders are uneducated and unknowledgeable on the demands and principles of corporate governance. These set of shareholders do not know their rights and therefore, unwilling to demand proper governance from the board. In some cases, they see corporate governance principles as an imposition by the government rather than a guideline for best practices. Respondent G in his response has this to say:

...The truth about this is that we have illiterate investing public. Many major shareholders of banks in Nigeria are not sufficiently educated. Many of them do not understand the need for corporate governance. They see it as people coming to dictate to them how to manage their money. Many of these investors believe that investment in banks will give them more money. So, when trying to implement the principles of corporate governance in banks, they assume that you are trying to sensor their investment and returns. Because many of them encourages many illegal activities...

This response implies that illiteracy is not the only challenge posed to disperse ownership of Nigerian banks, but it encompasses ethical issues. The implication of this Respondent G's assertion is that there is need to educate existing and potential investors on the principles of corporate governance. The investors should be abreast with contemporary corporate governance codes. When investors are well informed on such principles and codes, they will be

able to identify excesses of the board and management. The second part of the response highlighted that some shareholders do not care about corporate governance. It is not because of naivety of such shareholders on requirements of corporate governance. They basically exploit lack of corporate governance implementation to execute their illegal deals and transactions. There is need to educate shareholders on the impact of lack of corporate government implementation in their organisations. Though profits may accrue through illegal deals in banks, the long run consequences are drastic. They are such consequences as seen in the case of Diamond bank. All the shareholders bear the consequence and risk losing part of their stakes resulting from mergers and acquisition.

Basically, to tackle the excesses of concentrated ownership, it might be considerable to have government representative in the board of different banks. The reason for such idea is to increase the chances of transparency in banks' activities and ensure corporate governance implementation. However, 13/15 of the respondents are of the opinion that it is unnecessary for such government representation. Their argument is because private individuals own the banks and should be allowed to determine the best way to maximize organisational profits. Respondent J expressed that:

... In the case of Nigerian banks, the government is not allowed to be represented in the board because they are private establishment. In well developed economies, the economy is driven by private sector and government presence in the private sector is considered as an intrusion. What the government should do is providing enabling environment so that privately owned businesses should thrive. The interest of the government lies largely on the revenue collection in terms of taxation...

The assertion of the above respondent is that the government should create enabling environment for businesses to thrive rather than having a representative in banks. The question maybe, how will government create enabling environment? Enabling environment encompasses good policy, ensuring implementation of such policies and persecution of offenders. Nigeria, through its relevant parastatals have had wonderful economic policies. However, implementation has been noted as a challenge undermining such policies to thrive. It implies that the government should pay maximum attention in ensuring holistic implementation of principles and codes of corporate governance. If they should be able to do that, there will be no need for a representative in any organisation to monitor their daily activities.

Although it is widely believed that disperse ownership favours corporate governance implementation than concentrated ownership, responses from interviews show that there are ways in which selfish interests of the major shareholders can be curtailed and limited. Limiting such excesses will protect minority shareholders and encourage prospective investors to risk their funds in such organisation.

Among other suggestions, 10/15 suggested that some qualifications and records should be part of set benchmarks on who becomes a director in a bank. These include academic qualification, experience, skills, and ethical records. By doing so, it might be hard to higher an unqualified director in a board. During the interview, respondent B stated that:

...experience and skills are required because they (board members) are the ones that chat the cause of banking operations. Basically, their functions are to engage in what we call strategic planning and long-term planning. It is only someone who is experienced that can help the banks

in achieving their goal because one does not give what he does not have. So, the shareholders should not compromise in determining who should be in the board.

This implies that by virtue of board roles, members of the board should, therefore, be well informed. Contrary to selecting board members based on meritocracy will undermine the total governance of the bank. It might be argued that government should not be in position to make it an obligation for banks to implement corporate governance guidelines and codes. However, considering government role in ensuring ailing banks are saved in form of bailout funds, it will be reasonable for them to put measures that will eliminate such occurrences. This argument therefore takes us to the next discuss, which is bank distress and bailout fund.

4.5 Bank Distress and Bailout Funds

In Nigeria, bank distress and bailouts have been a prevalent issue that needs be tackled or totally eradicated. Without banks being distressed, there will be no need for government intervention in the form of bailout funds. Bailout was introduced in Nigeria to ensure a bank's stability and this bailout programme was prominent during the global economic meltdown (Aliyu, Jamil and Mohamed, 2014). They expressed that non-performing loans and poor risk management were associated to banks distress, which was an evidence of poor corporate governance implementation in the banking sector.

To further ascertain the causes of this phenomenon (bank distress), the researcher, during the interview asked interviewees questions on their views regarding bank distress and bailout funds. All the interviewees (15/15) agreed that banks being distressed is an ongoing phenomenon that

needed to be tackled. However, there are dichotomy of opinions on whether the government should continue with bailout or not. Consequently, the opinions of the respondents are adequately analysed.

Bank distress and need for bailout is an evidence of existing poor corporate governance implementation by the board. Therefore, the board have failed to effectively carry out their directorial roles. A study carried out in 2019 which was posted on a website of popular Nigerian dailies Pulse.ng shows that seven unnamed banks are on the verge of being distressed (Ojekunle, 2019). When asked question on opinion about bailout funds, Respondent A has this to say:

...The main aim of bailout funds by government is to ensure banks do not fail if they are distressed. It is necessary and it is done all over the world. It (bailout) should be a loan a bank should pay after recovering so that directors will avoid being stressed knowing they will be indebted to the government (CBN)...

This response above suggested that banks should be persuaded to refund every fund given to them in at a point when they were distressed. The Interviewee further stated that fear of being indebted to government through central bank will deter directors from making decision that might cause them to be distressed. Since some of these directors are not major shareholders in the banks that they are part of the board; it might give them little or no concern of what becomes the bank after being distressed. When probed on what becomes the fate of this banks in a situation where the directors' decisions have resulted to bank distress, Respondent A replied:

...The CBN should monitor the bailout funds to avoid the board embezzling such relief fund. The need for bailout funds is an indication of poor corporate governance in the board. which means

board have not done what they are ought to have done. Bailout is there to ensure employment is not lost and depositors money are safe. To ensure effective corporate governance, new directors should be employed to fill the corporate governance gaps which resulted to banks being stressed...

This implies that there is need for the government to take over the management and board of such banks, especially where there is evidence of management by the board. If the major shareholders should be aware of implications of take overs by the government, it will deter them from hiring unqualified individuals to oversee the affairs of their bank.

There are some other reasons why government bailout is necessary on ailing banks. It was ascertained during the interview that collapse of a bank always have devastating effects on the economy. Which means that it has ripple effects, as it does not affect the shareholders only but the society at large. However, despite this view that government should bailout ailing banks, most of the interviewees agreed that lack corporate governance contributes to distress in banks. The result from the interview shows that 12/15 of the participants supports government bailout but argued that it will encourage laziness on the side of the board. Respondent J has this view on bailout fund:

...Let me reiterate the main reason for government bailout. A failure of one bank do have devastating effect on the economy and can lead to distress of families. And bailout builds a loss of confidence in the economy. So, the government is saving a lot of issues by issuing the bailout fund. However, from the angle of corporate governance, it (bailout fund) will encourage laxity. The board will always think that after all, the government will bail us out. In my opinion, the government should not eradicate bailout funds...

Despite the overwhelming support for government intervention on ailing banks in the form of bailout funds, 3/15 of the respondents are totally against it. The common argument is based on the ownership of the banks. Basically, banks are owned by private individuals and should not involve the government on its challenges. They further argued that since government do not bailout other businesses, especially in non-financial sectors, that there is no need for government intervention. Respondent C gave this response on the need for government bailout:

... I look at bailout fund for distressed banks as a form of encouraging laziness, promoting corruption, encouraging underhand (secret or dishonest) dealings in banks. The management of banks get really involved in whether a bank is professionally managed or not. And so, when a bank is not well managed, to the extent that it is not your personal money and then you get a bailout from the government, to assist the business means you are laying back to government to spoon-feed you. And that to me, is not a good thing. Bailout should be discouraged as far as I am concerned. If a bank is distressed, it should be allowed to die (be liquidated) and die a natural death...

This argument might be in the view of bringing equal treatment to all business owners irrespective of the sector or the type of business affected. However, financial sectors are quite different from other non-financial businesses. It does not only cost jobs, but it also affects members of public who have their cash deposited in banks. If government fails to salvage an ailing bank which subsequently bankrupt, it might cause civil unrest and increase in criminal activities. Therefore, measures to eliminate this phenomenon becomes paramount. In some cases, when companies are bailed out by the government, the board is being changed. This

means that the only consequence of negligence on the side of the board can only cause them their jobs.

In the interview, 9/15 of the respondents suggested that loss of job should not be the only penalty given to the members of the board that their unprofessionalism resulted to collapse of a bank. That such individuals should be persecuted accordingly to discourage future offenders.

Respondent C further said this about bailout funds:

...However, what I would like to suggest is that to deter the corporate gate keepers from laxity, I mean the BOD, is that there should be sanctions accosted to each bailout. The members of BOD who were found wanting or acted below expectations should be persecuted, not just relieving them off their post. If they are not penalised appropriately, it will only encourage future offenders who tends to get away with such crime...

The above shows that probably, members of the board who previously neglected their oversight duties or engaged in one scandal or the other in Nigerian banks, have not been properly punished. Therefore, the government need to enact law with severe punishment capable of deterring intending offenders.

4.6 Multiple Board Representation and Bank Distress

Corruption and lack of corporate governance implementation have been largely identified as major challenges contributing to bank distress and subsequently need for bailout or liquidation.

However, there other neglected factors like 'multiple board representation' which have been underdiscussed by researchers.

The Nigerian code of corporate governance, which was revised by the Financial Reporting Council (FRC, 2018), recommends that a director can be a board member in different organisations so far it is not detrimental to any of their employers. The collated data from the interview shows that 9/15 of respondents are against the recommendation, as conflict of loyalty and interest. Respondent C has this to say:

...As far as Nigeria is concerned with its abundant human resources, I think it (multiple board representation) will undermine the corporate governance effectiveness. Directors should be encouraged to focus on one board and give their best on lifting the organisation than to get employed in multiple boards. Being employed in multiple boards brings egotism, makes a director to feel extremely important and therefore, can makes one relaxed is discharging of duties...

Apart from being reluctant in discharging of duty, directors will work harder in a situation where the only job they have is at stake if they underperform. Single board representation encourages hard work and improves board effectiveness. Respondent C further argued that:

...But when you are appointed only in one board, and you know your success and image is based on the success of the organisation, you will be putting in more effort to ensure that the board is effective...

Moreover, board directorship requires a lot of time, not just for meetings, but requires critical thinking towards the best policy for the organisation. To be active in multiple boards, especially in a bank, requires a lot of attentions as banks are prone to fraudulent activities. Therefore,

utmost attention is needed, especially in monitoring the activities of the management.

Respondent E has this opinion on multiple board representation:

...The issue of multiple board representation to me, it reduces board effectiveness in banks. There is no one who is jack of all trade. If someone is in two or three boards, you will discover there will be divided loyalty. even the time required to do effective job may not be there. Because board representation does not just start and end with attending meetings, it involves critical thinking before attending meetings because it is required to have a clear line of thought about what you want done in the corporation. But if you are in two or three boards, it means you will flimsily spread your time and concentration, which will not make the best out of your membership...

On the contrary, 6/15 of the respondents agreed with multiple board representation. The argument being that directorship positions are temporal and some cases part-time. Thus, anyone with capability of working as director in one or more banks should be availed with such opportunity. While some agree with multiple board representation, they are of the opinion it should be restricted to maximum of three to avoid overburden of the director in question. Moreover, other arguments suggested that a versatile director can be on different committees of different banks. When questioned on the impact of multiple board directorship, respondent B stated:

...There is nothing wrong with multiple directorships. The directorship position in a bank is not a full-time job. To the extent that people are very skilled and qualified, they can act in diverse companies or different companies as directors. After all, it is not a full-time job or a permanent job. For instance, an accountant who is well versatile can serve as a director in one or two banks

(different banks). The roles do not conflict and there is no conflict of interest whatsoever. There is nothing wrong in that. One person can be a director in one or two banks...

This implies that being a director in multiple boards requires a higher skill and knowledge. Consequently, some standard should be set for one to be qualified to merit being a multiple director. It might be based on appraisal of past records, skills, and experiences.

4.7 Effective Corporate Governance in Nigerian Banks

This section basically addresses all the identified challenges of corporate governance in Nigerian banks and how to minimise or totally eradicate such challenges. Corporate governance codes and principles is not totally new to Nigerian business environment, both in financial and non-financial sectors. However, lack of implementation has been identified as one greatest challenge facing it to thrive in Nigerian corporate society. Beside corruption and negligence on the side of the board, which have undermined holistic implementation, the result from the interview reveals that constant training and conferences can hasten compliance by the board. Engaging them on conferences and trainings will help them to be updated with the prevailing corporate governance codes and most importantly the need to implement them. This section is separated in two parts: policy implementation both on the side of government and training for the board to be abreast with prevailing corporate governance challenges in the corporate world.

4.8 Policy Implementation

Despite the board largely blamed for lack of corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks, respondents argued that government has a lot of roles to play. Some of the respondents claimed the government is overwhelmingly corrupt, consequently, it affects other aspects of the economy. When asked the way forward on the best way to ensure corporate governance implementation, respondent A has this to say:

...by ensuring good governance in the country (i.e., in all areas of state affairs). The government should have political will to do what is right and should lead by example for others to follow. They should be apolitical in dealing with financial issues and implementation of the corporate governance codes and principles. The government should eradicate corruption in the system and avoid nepotism in the attending to issues. The government should do the right thing, so that other institution will emulate them...

This implies that government have not done enough to ensure CG implementation. The respondent clearly stated that the government should be apolitical when dealing with financial issues. Finance in the life-wire of every economy and should be prioritised especially in implementation of codes guiding it.

The Nigerian codes and principles of corporate governance are always updated to keep the country's economy abreast with the global practices. The latest of these codes is the one revised by the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRC, 2018). These guidelines enumerated the how to encourage the management in implementation of CG practices. Respondent G has this opinion on CG implementation:

...the ethics is there; the code of conduct is there in corporate governance. Everything is streamlined and tell you how to behave, the penalties and sanctions if you deviate from what the law has given you or said. The punishment is there and is stated clearly. So, we all need to show compliance to the codes of corporate governance...

This further evidenced that a lot needed to be done by the government in ensuring compliance of the codes of CG. This is not by engaging on day-to-day activities of the banks. However, it can be routinely done by using the relevant agencies like the CBN (Central Bank of Nigeria) and other regulatory bodies to verify, from time to time the information given to public by these banks.

Accordingly, deterring the board is considered as another viable means to ensure the executives comply with the codes of corporate governance. Penalising individuals found guilty of mismanagement should be vital in encouraging prospective defaulters. The situation in Nigeria shows that cases levelled against ex bank executives involved in scandals is not enough to discourage future offenders. Respondent C has this to say:

...to a very extent, our banks here in Nigeria are complying with the CG guidelines, which is noticeable in their respective annual statements. However, the government is not doing enough in terms of punishing offenders. I know of a bank that became bankrupt last year 2019. Which was caused by gross mismanagement by the board. Up until now, we have not heard of any punishment on the individuals apart from losing their positions...

This further buttress arguments that government are incompetent towards policies implementation. In deciphering the sentiments of respondent C, job loss should not be the only punishment meted on those found guilty of any form of mismanagement. Otherwise,

mismanagement will be a routine by these executives when they are aware of getting lenient penalty.

4.9 Training, Seminars and Conferences

Basically, corporate governance is a recommendation on how to pilot the affairs of an organisation. According to The Cadbury committee (1992), corporate governance is defined a systematic way by which companies are directed and controlled. This means that those appointed at the helm of companies' affairs should be updated with the prevailing situations in the corporate environments. During the interview, 15/15 of the respondents explicitly indicated the need for the board to be sent to trainings and conferences for the benefits of the respective banks. Corporate governance has evolved over years; therefore, the respondents reiterated the need for the board of directors to be abreast with prevailing concerns of corporate governance and corporate organisations.

Despite training and conferences identified as one of the most effective ways of encouraging corporate governance in Nigerian banks and the general corporate world. However, some respondents 8/15 highlighted the need for trainings not to be limited on areas of corporate governance. The respective board members should be encouraged to undergo trainings in their different academic backgrounds. This will be vital in strengthening their respective expertise and skills. In respective to this argument, this is what respondent A has to say:

...First, the members of the board should be knowledgeable in their areas of expertise (accountants, networking, banking, engineering, etc.). More training in their academic

background and orientations should be given. The directors should be compelled to attend trainings as scheduled and should personally expose themselves to the prevailing issues in the areas of banking and corporate governance...

The response above is an indication that a board should be largely diversified. This is not only on the areas of gender or ethnic representation but most importantly based on skills and academic qualifications. When the board is well diversified, it brings moderation and cut excesses in piloting the affairs of the bank.

Furthermore, the challenges of either the chairman or the CEO overriding their duties have been identified as an undermining factor of effective corporate governance. One of the respondents stated that it is not just issue of either the CEO or the Chairman trespassing on their duties, but their inability to identify their respective duties. Respondent G has this to say:

Training is very important to members of board and management. This will enlighten them of what is expected of them and roles they must play in corporate business. So, these positions should be occupied by those who have been trained in that capacity. Training is very important; exposure is important as well. The regulators (CBN and NDIC) should perform the roles of educating these people (CEO and Chairman) on their distinguished roles in banks

The respondent is of the opinion that the relevant government organisations should embark on training the board on their roles and duties. That will ensure good and effective corporate governance are implemented in organisation and will enhance company performance.

considering the numerous schedules of the board of directors, which might undermine the individual board members ability to undergo trainings and conferences. It was recommended

that trainings should be done during board meetings. This meeting could be monthly or quarterly, depending on the prevailing challenges in the corporate environment.

In some cases, the busy nature of board of directors' duties and roles, especially the executive directors, has become a bottle neck that undermines their ability to regularly engage in trainings and conferences. Moreover, the timeframe for the training by relevant organisations like the CBN and NDIC might be favourable to set of banks, while unfavourable to others. To ensure that directors of a bank or group of banks are abreast with prevailing corporate governance challenges, respective banks organising personal trainings for their executives becomes unavoidable. In response to training and conferences, Respondent J suggested:

It is recommended that the board should meet frequently, at least once a month or quarterly. During such board meetings, training should be organised to let the people know the new things, innovations, and developments about the business (banking) and any other thing that they need to know. The Board should be meeting regularly to be trained and a technocrat should be invited to train the board members on what they should do in the business and how they should be guided.

Basically, most Nigerian banks board of directors have less number meetings annually. The above respondent is of the opinion that banks should meet frequently. The meetings should encompass training sessions to discuss contemporary issues of corporate governance. Having meeting and training regularly is paramount, as it will be a reminder to the board on need for corporate governance implementation and keep them updated on the developing issues in the banking sector.

Contrary to Respondent J's opinion on the need for regular meetings and trainings, some other respondents are of the opinion that training, and seminars can be biannually. To be appointed as a board member, one must be informed and experienced. Therefore, trainings and seminars should be an avenue to refresh them on what they already know. Therefore, they do not necessary need daily or monthly training and seminars as it might accumulate extra cost for the company. In support of this opinion, respondent C suggested:

...The board members are experienced people. But then, once in 6 months (biannually) the board members should be gathered, refreshed, and updated on corporate governance guidelines and emerging corporate governance issues. Trainings and seminars can be done as the need arises...

The above contribution noted that though trainings and seminars should be organised biannually to refresh the director's knowledge on the principles of corporate governance. However, the respondent noted that seminars and trainings can be organised in a case of corporate urgency or to be updated on the prevailing issues of corporate governance challenges.

Despite 15/15 of the respondents concurring that training and seminars are crucial in ensuring that the board of directors are updated and abreast with developing issues on corporate governance. Nevertheless, some of the responses from the interview indicates that most shareholders are unknowledgeable about principles of corporate governance. Thus, they cannot hold the directors accountable for lack of proper implementation. Some of these shareholders are of the opinion that corporate governance is a medium sensor and monitor their investments. The following answer was given in response to shareholders contribution on corporate governance implementation:

...Many of them are ignorant and do not know what principles of corporate governance is and have different misconception about what corporate governance is and will resist to any extent to ensure that the principles of corporate governance are not put into practice in their organizations. The way to go about it is by education and seminars so that they understand what corporate governance is and that it will strengthen the principle of accountability... (interviewee F).

This is an indication that there is need for both the principal and agent's collaboration in achieving desirable corporate governance implementation. Therefore, educating them (board of directors and shareholders) respectively through seminars and workshops become imminent.

When the shareholders are well educated on the importance of corporate governance in banks, it will eradicate the existing doubts that corporate governance is not put in place to monitor individuals' investments and will further undermine their profit maximization. Interviewee F further explained sentiments of shareholders in Nigeria banks on corporate governance implementation:

...Many major shareholders of banks in Nigeria are not sufficiently educated. Many of them do not understand the need for corporate governance. They see it as people coming to dictate to them how to manage their money. Many of these investors believe that investment in banks will give them more money. So, when trying to implement the principles of corporate governance in banks, they assume that you are trying to sensor their investment and returns...

4.10 CONCLUSION

The concluding section presents the synopsis of chapter four, which analyses the prevailing factors that influences effective corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks. There are seven (7) distinctive sections discussed in this chapter. The section one provides the introductory information of chapter six. The sections two to section six analysed extensively the contemporary issues of corporate governance in Nigeria and possible ways to implement the proffered panaceas in Nigerian banks. while the last section presents the summary of the findings and possible solutions as discussed in sections 4.1 to five. 4.6.

The quality of board leadership is notably, one of the major determinants on whether corporate governance will thrive in an organisation or not. Quality leadership encompasses individuals with skills, experiences and knowledgeable in respective areas of their disciplines. Therefore, if leadership composition of any organisation lacks in any of the traits of leadership, it undermines effective corporate governance implementation. The second section of the interview analyses identified lack of quality leadership as a major factor impeding effective corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks. some the directors lack quality but appointed based their personal relationship with major shareholders of the banks. such appointments have led to collusion with these set of shareholders, therefore, undermining the general principles of corporate governance. Among other leadership challenges, unethical display by some directors has notably hindered effective corporate governance in Nigeria banks. unethical behaviour does not necessary emanate as result knowledge deficiency in the areas of corporate governance, but it is as result personal and selfish interests on the side of directors. This might be in form of corruption, tampering with financial statements to report profit even when there is none.

Secondly, the analysis revealed that dichotomy of interests among different shareholders has distorted quality corporate governance and effectiveness of the board. subjugation and lesser attention given to minority shareholders has become a thing of concern and discuss among corporate governance experts. The analysis indicts the board for often neglecting these set of investors. Besides challenges of the minority investors, principal-principal conflict has become noticeable. The challenges which arise in situation where directors are more loyal to one shareholder compared to others. Moreover, conflict of interests arises among directors on what should be kept as retain earnings or to be paid out in dividends. Such challenges make it difficult for the directors to decide a favourable outcome for individual shareholders.

Thirdly, ownership structure can either underpin or undermine effective corporate governance in banks. there are classes of ownership structure; concentrated, moderate, and fragmented ownerships. All these can affect how corporate government is implemented in organisations. However, concentrated ownership structure is identified as a type of ownership structure that mostly pose threat to corporate governance effectiveness in organisations. When organisational structure is highly concentrated, it means that very few or a person outrightly owns it. The analyses indicated that such owners absolutely decide who will be in the board, thus, the board loses their ability to carry out their roles without fear of loss of job. in some situation, these owners are part of the board, and find it hard to listen to rest of the members. Some of them engages in illegal businesses of balance sheet without being questioned. The interviewees, hve noted that its paramount that the government through its relevant organisations, monitor such banks, where ownership structure is highly concentrated.

Fourthly, the need for bailout funds is an indication of existing poor corporate governance. Over years, distressed Nigerian banks have occasionally been bailed by government to avoid ailing banks to be liquidated. Considering the importance of banks which host individual wealth. Any form of misfortune will not only affect the shareholder, but investors and depositors. There is dichotomy of interest on whether government should aide distressed banks since they are privately owned. Some respondent argued that it encourages laziness of among the directors. However, some interviewees argued that a bank is a special kind of business, that its liquidation will have a lot of negative impact in the society. They are, therefore, keen on board of directors who have neglected their duties to be penalised heavily to deter future offenders.

Finally, policy implementation and trainings are identified as the major ways to ensure more effective corporate governance and implementation. The analyses indicate that the government has done little to ensure developed corporate governance principles are implemented. Offenders who went contrary or those found wanting are not appropriately penalised to deter future offenders.

Therefore, the existing situation does not discourage any future offender. Besides implementation, the respondents have identified the need for banks to engage their directors with routine seminars and trainings, as to refresh and keep them abreast on prevailing corporate governance issues which might undermine effective corporate governance. The next chapter (5) provides the discussion of the findings. The discussion will be relation to the objectives of this study.

Chapter 5: Discussion of Findings

5.0 Introduction

This chapter presents a holistic discourse of the analysed data in the preceding chapters in tandem with the existing literatures on shareholders perception on corporate governance implementation on banks. The discussion is based on all arguments raised in this study with paramount attention to the matters raised in the data analysis which predominantly focused on understanding the limitations of corporate governance implementation in Nigerian commercial banks.

Generally, this thesis examined the shareholders perception on corporate governance implementation by the board in Nigerian commercial banks. It encompasses the ability and effectiveness of respective banks' board of directors to holistically implement the prevailing corporate governance codes. The analysis of this project was carried out on commercial banks licensed to operate by the CBN (Central Bank of Nigeria) and listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). In examining the effective implementation of contemporary corporate governance codes by the board, corporate governance theories like; agency theory, stakeholders' theory, stewardship theory, resource dependency theory and managerial hegemony were extensively discussed in the literature. These theories addressed corporate governance variables and the expectations of the board. Besides the corporate governance theories, different corporate governance models being practiced across the globe like; the Anglo-Saxon, Continental European model and Japanese corporate governance model were all discussed. However, the Anglo-Saxon corporate governance model formed the greater part of this research work as it is similar to the

practices enshrined in the Nigerian corporate governance codes (Omolayo, Otome and Atekebo, 2017). The researcher employed semi-structured interview in data collection, conducting 15 in-depth interviews. Thematic analysis was further used in analysing the data. Consequently, the analysed data created the medium for discussion of the findings in relation to the research objectives, therefore, reaching to a meaningful conclusion.

Furthermore, the discussion and findings of this thesis has been presented in relation to the three primary objectives.

5.1 Analysed Data in Relation to Research Objective 1

Research objective 1: To examine and understand the prevalent issues of corporate governance in Nigerian Banks. Considering Nigeria quest to be abreast with developed economies in areas of corporate governance. This objective, therefore, intends to understand contemporary challenges facing quality corporate governance implementation, precisely, in relation to Nigerian commercial banks. Interviewees were asked two pertinent questions to help understand the prevailing corporate governance challenges in Nigerian banks. First, they were asked the general issue limiting corporate implementation in Nigerian commercial banks. The second question focused on why Nigerian banks are yet to holistically adopt prevailing corporate governance codes.

Thus, the outcome of the question formed the challenges discussed below.

In the analysis, it was indicated that poor corporate governance implementation is largely one of the greatest challenges facing corporate governance in Nigerian banks. The findings indicate that though corporate governance principles have overwhelmingly gained awareness in the Nigerian banking industry, some respective banks are yet to practice in its fullness, the guidelines, and principles of corporate governance. The board in corroboration with major shareholders still engage in dodgy activities that undermines corporate governance at the expenses of other shareholders and stakeholders.

This assertion of poor corporate governance implementation agrees with (Asogwa, 2016). The researcher argued that past and present bank failures in Nigeria is due to lack of proper corporate governance in the sector. This buttresses the view of respondent C that despite the level of corporate governance acceptance in Nigerian banks, it is still devoid of holistic implementation [*Though corporate governance has gained prominence in Nigerian banks, lack of total implementation is still a great challenge affecting its effectiveness. Apart from effective implementation, the corrupt practices in banks pose great challenge in governance of banks*]. Eighty percent (12/15) agree with respondent C that more efforts are needed on the area of total corporate governance implementation. (Okoye *et al.*, 2020)

Among other corporate governance challenges, lack of quality leadership in the board has been identified as a major issue surrounding implementation of corporate governance codes in Nigerian commercial banks. This phenomenon is labelled 'poor managerial performance' which resulted to poor performance of banks (Aliyu, Jamil and Mohamed, 2014). Many factors have been traced to leadership challenge in Nigerian banks. For example, Onakoya *et al.*, (2018) noted that lack of ethical leadership has contributed to poor corporate governance implementation.

They argued that lack of ability of the board to have empathy, fairness, trust has undermined ethical leadership in banks and has become a bottleneck in achieving holistic implementation of corporate governance in Nigerian banks.

Moreover, responses from the interview posits that selfish interest on the side of the board of directors has become an underlying factor that promotes unethical leadership, which subsequently mitigated poor corporate practices in Nigerian commercial banks. These individuals (board of directors) who benefit from poor corporate governance implementation will always want to maintain the status quo so that they will continue to exploit the organisations that is entrusted to them. The findings show that lack of ethical leadership exacerbated poor protection of the minority investors by the board leadership. The major shareholders more often decide what happens in the banks even to the detriment of other minority shareholders. These findings are consistent with the work of (Anderson, Chi and Liao, 2019). They noted that dichotomy of interest between the majority and minority shareholders can lead to tunnelling. This is where the key shareholders usurp the wealth of minority investors. One of the interviewees noted the need of board management to protect the interest of every shareholder irrespective of the stock they hold. The consequence of this wide gap in the leadership structure of respective banks is that it will negatively affect earnings, Foreign direct investment (FDI) and discourage prospective investors who have intention of buying minimal stake in the bank. This assertion of downward earning where investors protection is weak is consistent with findings of (Zhong, Chourou and Ni, 2017).

The figure 5.1 below shows that Nigeria scored only four (4) on protecting minority investors. This ranks below many other African countries. The score is an indication of poor leadership management and paucity in corporate governance implementation.

Figure 5.1 Minority investors protection

1	Economy	Getting Credit	Protecting Minority Invest	Paying Taxes	Trading across Borders	Enforcing Contracts
16	Lesotho	19	26	16	2	
17	Senegal	9	13	32	22	
18	Nigeria	5	4	29	40	
19	Niger	6	16	34	17	
20	Cabo Verde	28	38	10	9	
21	Mozambique	39	26	18	6	
22	Zimbabwe	9	11	24	29	
23	Tanzania	9	12	31	42	
24	Mali	31	16	37	7	
25	Benin	31	16	35	10	
26	Burkina Faso	31	16	27	15	
27	Mauritania	22	26	39	23	
28	Gambia, The	31	38	36	11	
29	Guinea	31	32	44	34	
30	Ethiopia	42	47	19	27	
31	Comoros	22	32	33	13	
32	Madagascar	22	23	20	21	
33	Sierra Leone	39	22	13	32	
34	Burundi	42	24	23	35	
35	Cameroon	13	31	42	46	

Source: World Bank Doing Business 2019

Furthermore, since 2007/2008 economic meltdown, Nigeria has severally revised their corporate governance principles to enhance performance of companies and be abreast with global standard. However, the country is yet to achieve the desired standard of corporate government as practiced in developed economy. Financial institutions are still undergoing challenges because of poor corporate governance practice. Lack of proper implementation of corporate governance in Nigerian banks are being attributed to weak legal institution and corruption (Ediagbonya, 2020). This is in tandem with the view of Respondent C who has this to say on corporate

governance implementation; ...*the problem why there is no absolute implementation is because government malfunction...*

5.2 Analysed Data in Relation to Research Objective 2

Research objective 1: To critically evaluate the influence of those corporate governance issues and how they affect current corporate governance status of Nigerian banks. This section critically discussed the effect of underlying corporate governance challenge in Nigerian banks.

5.2.1 Corporate Governance and Board Diversity

Firstly, this section discussed the poor corporate governance impact on the ability of Nigerian banks to judiciously diversify the banks' board and management. Despite the importance of independent directors in the board, the diversity of the board cannot be overemphasised. Harjoto, Laksmana and Yang (2018) expressed that the board's capability of carrying out their advisory and monitoring role depends on the level of diversity in the board. From the interview carried out, it was ascertained that there are several aspects of diversity which include gender, experience, and career diversity.

Lack of corporate governance implementation has undermined the ability of banks to effectively diversify their board thus undermining the board effectiveness in Nigerian commercial banks. Respondent A has this to say on this issue '*...Lack of following diversities have undermined board effectiveness in Nigerian banks to great extent; 1) gender diversity 2) experience diversity 3)*

career diversity. They should be people with integrity. Having people from different career background (such as lawyers, bankers, engineers' accountants, economists, and other professionals) adds credibility to what the body (BOD) are doing. Diversity is important and plays massive roles in board effectiveness...'

This aligns with the views of Magnanelli and Pirolo (2021). They noted three important types of diversity viz: professional diversity (people from different and vital professions), occupational attributes in relation to international experience and occupational experience in relation to years of experience (basically within related organisation).

Despite 10/15 of the respondents in the interview expressing poor diversity in Nigerian banks, Respondent B totally disagreed with them. Respondent B has this to say. *...There is no bank in Nigeria that does not have directors from all the parts of this country. (When it comes to female representative in the board) women also play important roles (in banks). For instance, the CEO of First bank is a woman (female). The Chairman of FCMB is a woman (female). In (name of the firm withheld), Funke Oshubode is a woman (female) too and Chairman of a board. Women (female directors) are participating actively in the governance of the banks in Nigeria...*

This respondent is speaking from particular point of view of diversity. It could be possibly that the banks are beginning to consider female directors in the board. However, the respondent did not put into consideration other aspects of diversity. This might explain the reasons behind banks failure in Nigeria as their boards are not properly diversified.

To further buttress the importance of diversification of board, Magnanelli and Pirolo (2021) reiterated the need for inclusion of professionals in the board. They noted individuals with

different career paths are vital in promoting the innovation of sensitivity of an organisation, enhancing the vision of the management, and proffering effectual panacea to challenges faced by the firm. In examining the effect of board diversity, that is on corporate investment oversight, it was ascertained that experiential board performs better than homogenous bank (Harjoto, Laksmana and Yang, 2018).

Furthermore, considering globalisation of industries, the ability of banks' inclusion of individuals from different nations become sacrosanct. This type of diversity is to an extent lacking in Nigerian banks. Nigeria is made up by different ethnic groups and inclusion of individuals from different ethnic groups in the bank board will be vital. Respondent D noted that not all types of diversity enhance banks performance. The respondent emphasised the need for the members of the board to reflect ethnic diversity of Nigeria *'...However, considering the ethnic differences and gender issues. It will be important to include directors from different ethnic group and gender to checkmate the excesses and weaknesses of the others. Which is important in achieving good corporate governance in institutions.*

Khan and Abdul Subhan (2019) expressed the importance of including not only people across ethnic groups but also expatriates from foreign nations. In their findings, they observed that though gender diversity is plausible, however, nationality diversity is highly correlated with firm performance. This assertion agrees with the findings of (Fernández-Temprano and Tejerina-Gaite, 2020; Choi, *et al.*, 2014).

Furthermore, the excerpts of interviews indicate the need for meritocracy in Nigerian banks selecting the members of the board. Some banks are keen only in diversifying the banks board

without considering competency of appointed individuals to ensure performance of the banks. Improper diversification of Nigerian boards has undermined the performance of Nigerian banks. Respondent J argued on the importance of merit over mere diversification '*...when it comes to ethnicity, there is no sentiment in business. People who invested reasonable funds in banks will go for people who will give them result, who will give them adequate return on funds they have invested. So, trying to get every ethnic group to be in the board will be out it. Because it is not goal oriented. It is in politics that talk about representation. But in business, you talk about result...*'

5.2.2 Ownership Structure challenges

The ownership structure of banks has been identified among the contemporary issues facing corporate governance implementation in Nigerian commercial banks. Among all the three types of ownership structures enumerated by Ozili and Uadiale (2017), there is likelihood that corporate governance principles are less likely to be implemented in concentrated ownership. One of the respondents during the interview stated that individuals having controlling interest of banks undermine holistic implementation of corporate governance.

The respondent further reiterated that most owners live on excesses at the expense of other minority shareholders. The reason behind controlling shareholders living a luxury life at the cost of the other shareholders is that most of these owners are also members of board, therefore, appointees or elected members of the board are less likely to carry out their directorial duties effectively. A board member who is a non-equity holder of a bank is less likely to challenge an uncalculated decision made by a major shareholder who is a CEO or chairman of the board. Thus,

hampering board independence, lack of quality disclosure and underwhelming minority investors protection.

The assertion that when owners or group owners are members of the board, mitigates them dominating the decisions made by the board thereby undermining company performance is consistent with (Dabor, Isiavwe and Ajagbe, 2015; Ajagbe & Ismail, 2014). The arguments of Dabor, Isiavwe and Ajagbe (2015) indicates that corporate ownership in Nigeria is less fragmented which has weakened the separation of ownership and control. Moreover, Ajagbe & Ismail (2014) reported that major equity shareholders influence corporations to embark higher-risk investment because they gain on the upside. This further buttress the arguments of interview respondent that, since banks are largely owned by few individuals and family, total separation of duties in the board becomes less achievable.

5.2.3 Issues of Bank Distress and Bailout Funds

Evidence emanating from analysed interviews indicates that government involvement in bailing out distressed banks is necessary to sustain their operation and avoid likely liquidation. Fourteen of the fifteen (14/15) respondents totally agree on the necessity of bailout funds. Nigerian banks have previously folded which resulted to depositors, creditors, investors, and other shareholders losing their funds and investments. For example, Baiyewu (2019) expressed the colossal damages caused by defunct Savannah Bank Plc in 2002. The bank has its 85,000 shareholders and depositors' hundreds of millions (Naira) liquidated. The respondents therefore highlighted the need to avoid such future occurrence. Respondent D on highlighting the importance of bailout

funds has this to say *...the federal government intervening when you have banks that are not doing well is based on what we call 'corporate interest...*

Despite the importance of bailout funds on ailing banks, 80% of the respondents noted that bank distress is a sign of poor corporate governance in place. Banks and other corporations who benefit from bailout funds tend to take uninformed decisions bearing in mind of government intervention. Bailout fund has become popular phrase in Nigeria financial sector since the economic meltdown of 2007/2008. Adedoyin (2019) noted that government has intervened by bailing out banks that are insolvent since 2007/2008. However, Adedoyin noted that this policy of intervention has resulted to high level of irresponsibility among financial and other bailable institutions. Moreover, corruption and other corrupt practices have been linked to bank distress. case of corruption is not peculiar to only financial sector as it holistically affects other aspects of the economy. Respondent B has this to say, *...I look at bailout fund for distressed banks as a form of encouraging laziness, promoting corruption, encouraging underhand (secret or dishonest) dealings in banks...*

Despite economic instability contributing to banks insolvency, previous studies have shown that factors that leads to banks distress are related to poor corporate governance (Adedoyin, 2019, Aliyu *et al.*, 2014).

5.2.4 Issues of Board Function

On January 15, 2019, Nigeria adopted a revised corporate government code with the aim of being abreast with best practices as in developed economies. The code empowers the chairman to

oversee the general leadership of an entity, while the CEO is board delegate who oversees the management aspect of the organisation and strategy implementation (Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance 2018)

Despite these efforts to enhance Nigerian corporate governance, some undermining factors have sabotaged its effectiveness. Lincoln *et al.*, (2017) in their research identified some undermining factors of corporate governance in Nigerian banks. They include poor leadership that ignores sub-committees' recommendations, favouritism appointments, lack of independency of different committees, poor qualifications of appointees and bribe prone board and supervisors.

Evidence emanating from the interview buttresses the view of poor implementation of corporate governance codes especially in areas of board functions and leadership. The excerpt of interview shows that 13/15 respondents agree on weak implementation of board role and functions. Respondent D has this to say on separation of roles of Chairman and CEO *'A glance at it may seem it is not working but it is working. There is no way when there is weak check will be equivalent to when there is no check at all. Though one might be weaker, there are still checks in place. The separation of the roles of chairman and CEO should be encouraged. It brings element of caution in the board.*

Nigerian commercial banks that have effectively enforced codes of corporate governance have shown higher performance compared to those with weak implementation. Olutokunbo *et al.*, (2020) in their findings established correlation between performance and banks that effectively implement distinctive duties of chairman and CEO respectively (separation of duties). They noted that that positions of Chairman and CEO in some banks is only on paper but not effectively

implemented. Such situation explains why more banks are being bailed out by Nigerian government as a result of bankruptcy. These banks have not effectively implemented the recommendations of 2019 corporate governance recommendation.

Past studies have established that lack of separation of power or duality role by CEO encourages power abuse and undermine proper check and balances (Kyereboah-Coleman and Biekpe, 2006; Ghana, Ehikioya, 2009; Ujunwa, 2012; Tang, 2017 and Mwamtambulo, 2020). According to Mwamtambulo (2020), duality of CEO position results to captured board. This is a situation where the CEO makes absolute decision without any possible check from equivalent force. However, there are known literature in support of CEO duality. On the contrary, Brickley *et al.*, (1997) noted the cost of implication of having both chairman and CEO in the board and how it is important to save cost for company in that aspect.

The question here is, why bank failure despite board separation of CEO and chairman in Nigeria banks? Though many banks have adopted the separation of CEO and chairman in the board, however, in many cases, separation of those positions are mere cosmetic as respective major shareholder influences their decision. Therefore, the need for independent of both the chairman and the CEO arises.

5.2.5 Challenges of Multiple Board Directorship

The relationship between multiple board directorship and its impact on company performance has been discussed by limited journals. In the Nigerian corporate governance codes that became effective in 2019 did not extensively discussed issues of multiple board directorship.

Directors are charged with the responsibility of monitoring and advising the management. These responsibilities are already demanding and taking over directorial responsibilities from a similar organisation might undermine effectiveness in one or both organisations (Hauser (2018). Besides the ability of a board member to carry out two directorial positions in different companies, Perry and Peyer (2005) in their research, find that prospective investors react negatively to a board member appointment as a director in another board.

There is dichotomy of opinions on whether multiple board directorship is a good corporate governance practice or not. In the interview, 10/15 of the respondents are of the opinion that it should not be encouraged. However, 5/15 are of the opinion that multiple directorships do not have any negative effect on company performance.

Among the opponents of multiple board representation is respondent D *'...as far Nigeria is concerned with abundant human resources, I think it (multiple board representation) will undermine the corporate governance effectiveness. Directors should be encouraged to focus on one board and give their best on lifting the organisation than to get employed in multiple board. Being employed in multiple boards brings egotism, makes a director to feel extremely important and therefore, can make one relaxed in discharging of duties...'* The respondent further reiterates that loyalty of a multiple director may be in doubt as attention will be given to one company compared to other(s). In some cases, people of the same class appoint each other or group friends as directors thereby undermining expertise in the board.

Furthermore, being part of the board does not necessarily entail attending meetings only, but it encompasses critical thinking especially in enacting policies for the betterment of the

organisation. Respondent has this to say '*...The issue of multiple board representation to me, reduces board effectiveness in banks. There is no one who is jack of all trade. If someone is in two or three boards, you will discover there will be divided loyalty. Even the time required to do effective job may not be there. Because board representation does not just start and end with attending meetings, it involves critical thinking before attending meetings because it is required to have a clear line of thought about what you want done in the corporation...*'

This implies that a board member in a bank should not take up a similar position, especially in another bank. Respective banks see each other as competitors and do preserve some information within the organisation. Therefore, information sharing, and loyalty of a multiple director becomes a challenge. This might explain the reasons behind negative reactions by the investors when a member of a board is appointed in another board (Perry and Peyer, 2005).

However, some respondents are of the opinion that multiple board directorship does not undermine corporate governance effectiveness. But what matters is the individual ability to carry out such positions judiciously without undermining any. Respondent B opines *...There is nothing wrong with multiple directorships. The directorship position in a bank is not a full-time job. To the extent that people are very skilled and qualified, they can act in diverse companies or different companies as directors. After all, it is not a full-time job or a permanent job. For instance, an accountant who is well versatile can serve as a director in one or two banks (different banks). The roles do not conflict and there is no conflict of interest whatsoever...*

Sarkar and Sarkar (2009) in their findings, it was ascertained that multiple independent directors are assets to their respective principals. They enhance company performance through

networking and connections to the external environment. This finding is explicit on independent directors (mostly non-executive) taking up multiple directorial positions. It explains the view of respondent B, who stated that the part time nature of their job permits multiple board job. Past studies have found positive relation between multiple outside directorship and performance (Mizruchi and Stearns, 1994; Booth and Deli, 1995).

Therefore, the evidence from the interview and literature is an indication that executive director's ability to take multiple directorial position should be limited, especially when their effectiveness will be undermined. Nevertheless, Non-Executive independent directors might pick the stipulated number of similar positions considering the part time nature of their jobs and chances of ameliorate the connection they bring to the organisation.

5.3. Analysed Data in Relation to Research Objective 3

The third primary objective of this study ascertained ways to implement good corporate governance in Nigerian banks. A lot of challenges facing corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks were deciphered. The respondents in the interview enumerated factors sabotaging implementation of corporate governance in Nigerian banks. In the responses of the interview and from literature, suggestions were made on how to ensure effective corporate governance in banks. These suggestions encompass corporate board effectiveness and effective government policies. It is only an effective corporate board and competent government that can ensure implementation of corporate governance code.

5.3.1 Board Trainings and Seminars

To achieve desired compliance of corporate governance codes, education, trainings, and seminars for the board have been identified as vital factors. Pereira and Filipe (2018) in their study on quality of board members' training and Bank financial performance found positive relationships. Banks that engaged their board in quality training, seminars and quality education have higher performance compared to others who do not.

The excerpts of interview indicate that 15/15 of the respondents agreed that regular trainings and seminars for board members are paramount in achieving good corporate governance practice. Some members of the board though educated, lack relevant trainings and qualifications that are related to corporate governance and its principles. Respondent A has this to say *'...training is very important to members of board and management. This will enlighten them of what is expected of them and roles they must play in corporate business. So, these positions should be occupied by those who have been trained in that capacity. Training is very important; exposure is important as well. The regulators (CBN and NDIC) should perform the roles of educating these people (CEO and Chairman) on their distinguished roles in banks...'* The assertion above is an indication that lack of experience and skills is still prevalent in the Nigerian banking system. Past corporate failures both in Nigeria and globally have been attributed to poor corporate governance (Ghosh, 2017). Therefore, the need for training and educating the board on prevailing corporate governance codes and other developments arises.

Previous research has found positive relationship between trainings and performance (Arumona and Erin, 2019; Boadi and Osarfo, 2019; Pereira and Felipe, 2018; Chevalier and Ellison, 1999 and

Golec, 1996). According to Golec(1996), investors reacts positively to appointment of an individual with high qualification like Master of Business Administration and doctoral degrees especially in areas of management. Moreover, Boadi and Osarfo (2019) expressed the importance of knowledgeable board through trainings and seminars. They noted that the appointed board members ought to understand the concept of corporate governance and all that it entails to effectively discharge their duties. Khan et. al (2020) further highlighted the importance of management quality in emerging economies as it is important in making objective and decisive decisions. Apparently, frequent meeting is very vital for the board. Having frequent meeting will create opportunities for the board to be updated on contemporary issues and amendments. Respondent B highlighted the importance of seminars during such meeting and has this to say *...It is recommended that the board should meet frequently, at least once a month or quarterly. During such board meetings, training should be organised to let the people know the new things, innovations, and developments about the business (banking) and any other thing that they need to know. The Board should be meeting regularly to be trained and a technocrat should be invited to train the board members on what they should do in the business and how they should be guided...*

This is an indication that trainings and seminars can be done during board meetings, which will save cost for the banks. Moreover, considering the uprising of non-performing loans make training of board members paramount. A 2020 report shows 14% increase in NPF (non-performing loans) in the first half of 2020 (Adesoji, 2020). The poor performance is an indication of ineffective board. According to Adesoji (2020), the assets pledged as collateral more often depreciates below the value of the loan, which mitigates banks' inability to recover all the funds

loaned in a case of non-performing loans. The board and entire management should, however, needed to be educate by professionals on how to calculate the future value of an asset. This is to avoid not being able to recover the value of their respective loans. Figure 5.1 shows graphical representation of sectors with highest number of non-performing loans in Nigeria.

Figure 5.2. Sectors with highest number of non-performing loans in Nigeria

Furthermore, financial education has been considered pertinent in the board. Considering the financial nature of the bank's businesses, every board member irrespective of academic

background is therefore, required to have trainings and regular seminars on financial management. Arumona and Erin (2019) posits in their research findings that companies that have their board members trained in area of accounting and finance within corporate governance framework performed better than those without. In the developed countries like United states, have intentions to enhance qualification prerequisite for directorial positions (Okoye *et al.*, 2017).

Besides board training, seminars, and conferences, Anania and Rwekaza (2018) argued that training of other staff is imperative as it will create harmony in the implementation of corporate governance at all levels of organisation. They were of the opinion that trainings in areas of financial bookkeeping, leadership, and management help organisations to achieve desired performance. This assertion is likely to impact performance of Nigerian commercial banks.

5.3.2 Government Institutions and policies

Though the board is saddled with strategic responsibility of making strategic plans, monitoring, and overseeing the activities of the company (Ebiziem *et al.*, 2020), there is need for government to compliment board function through its policies. All the respondents in the interview conducted agreed on the need for government intervention to ensure corporate governance effectiveness. These interventions could be in form of policies and prosecution of offenders. One of the interviewees (Respondent D) responding on the need for government intervention said *...If you consider the synthesis nature of banking industry, it is important the government takes decisive measures on issues and in implementation of codes and principles of corporate*

governance. First, the government should ensure strict control and ensure implementation of corporate governance by banks. Secondary, the government should equally put in place mechanism for persecution of offenders...

Okpamen and Ogbeide (2020) expressed the importance of government making policies through its institutions to checkmate the excesses of corporate board members. They noted that its not only about making policies but ensuring its implementation in respective boards. Governments supervision through its institutions like CBN, NDIC (Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation), SEC (Securities and Exchange Commission) and BOFIA the (Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act) is paramount in achieving corporate board effectiveness and implementation of corporate governance codes in Nigerian commercial banks. Mutarindwa *et al.*, (2020) found increase increased stability and high internal governance in local banks when the country's apex bank publishes supervisory guidance. Respondent C noted that some codes are already existing which were recommendations of regulatory institution. Therefore, the board should endeavour to judiciously implement the recommendation of the regulatory institutions. The respondent has this to say:

...The ethics is there; the code of conduct is there in corporate governance. Everything is streamlined and tells you how to behave, the penalties and sanctions if you deviate from what the law has given you or said. The punishment is there and is stated clearly. So, we all need to show compliance to the codes of corporate governance...

Moreover, the need to re-evaluate the process of selecting board members is pertinent considering the decrease in board effectiveness. Pereira and Filipe (2018) suggested that more

rigorous procedures should be employed in appointing board members. They argued that government through its institutions should make simultaneous policy based on educational qualification and experience as a criterion for banks in selecting their board members. Nevertheless, the government ability to ensure proper implementation in the board is questionable as corruption is systemic in Nigeria environment. Respondent K is of the opinion of government leading by example, being objective and remaining apolitical on financial institutions. The respondent has this to say *...by ensuring good governance in the country (i.e., in all areas of state affairs). The government should have political will to what is right and should lead by example for others to follow. They should be apolitical in dealing with financial issues and implementation of the corporate governance codes and principles. The government should eradicate corruption in the system and avoid nepotism in the attending to issues. The government should do the right thing, so that other institution will emulate them...*

This means that if the government remains apolitical on in ensuring respective banks properly implement corporate governance codes by penalising defaulters, it will result to effective corporate governance implementation and company performance.

5.3.3 Directors Remuneration and Corporate Governance implementation.

Agency theory posits that there is inherent tendency in agents to selfishly satisfy their own interest against that of principals who the owners of business. This mindset resulted to 'agent-principal issues' bringing mistrust between these set of individuals. However, Stewardship opines that agent can in effectively carry out their job effectively therefore prioritising the interest of

the principals (shareholders). This section therefore discuss how executive remuneration will sway the mindset of the board to see themselves as stewards who without coercion will implement the principles of corporate governance.

Studies have conducted by researchers on the effect of executive remuneration on corporate board effectiveness. Harymawan *et al.*, (2020) noted that executive remuneration is associate with board effectiveness. Aslam *et al.*, (2019) argued that when board of directors' compensation is correlate to their performances, it enhances board effectiveness. This type of remuneration system will likely be effective in Nigerian banks considering corporate governance challenges facing in the country. This assertion aligned with the view of respondent C; *...The responsibilities of the board should be quantified, how often they sit (time), qualifications and the experiences they have got. They should be well remunerated in relation to the work they do. The general profit made by the bank should be a determining factor in setting their remuneration...*

However, the posit of respondent C is not implemented in many banks as directors; remunerations are not quantified by their present achievements. Board of directors in several organisation especially in UK have their remuneration fixed while in the United States, both the Executive and non-executive directors are compensated according to performance of the organisation (Agyei-Boapeah *et al.*, 2019). Previous literatures have found positive relation between compensation of board members and firm performance (Aslam *et al.*, 2019, Kent *et al.*, 2018 and Shao *et al.*; 2012). Consequently, lack of corporate governance effectiveness in Nigerian banks and firm performance can among other factors be traced to the nature of remuneration system. The excerpts of the interview indicated that remuneration of directors is mostly fixed.

Therefore, directors might not be motivated to work harder or may become reluctant as their remuneration is not directly correlated with the firm performance.

5.4 Summary of Discussion

This chapter has extensively discussed the primary objectives of this thesis. The chapter addressed the challenges, effect, and possible solutions for effective corporate governance implementation by board of directors in Nigerian commercial banks. Having substantially researched on this issue, recommendation and contribution were made. The next chapter will present the recommendation, contribution, and limitations of this thesis.

CHAPTER 6: RECOMMENDATION, CONTRIBUTION AND CONCLUSION

6.0 Recommendations

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the discussion of recommendation, contribution, and limitation of the study. It encompasses the summary of the key findings of this research work and suggested avenue for future research. The shareholders perception on corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks was examined in this thesis. It includes prevailing corporate governance challenges encountered by the board in implementing good corporate governance principles, the effect of these challenges and the best way to eradicate such challenges. The analysis was conducted by using banks that are listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). To understand what entails good corporate governance principles, the researcher examined corporate governance models such as Anglo-Saxon, Continental European, and Japanese corporate governance model. Emphasis was more to Anglo-Saxon model since it is the type adopted in Nigeria. Moreover, different theories like Agency and Stewardship were also included in the thesis as they help in understanding the impact of board variables. These variables include board diversity, board composition, Leadership duality, board committees and board size. Such variables help in effectiveness of the board. Martinez-Jimenez *et al.*, (2020) expressed the importance of board as it helps in effective corporate governance and firm performance.

6.2.1 Government Policy in Nigerian Commercial Banks

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) have successfully outlined corporate governance principles guiding Nigerian banks and other listed organisations. However, the study reveals government inability through its institutions to ensure the board of respective banks effectively implement corporate governance codes. Effectiveness of the board entails their ability without any irregularity abide by the recommended principles.

Lack of diversity have been identified as one the challenges undermining corporate governance implementation in Nigeria bank. However, most codes of corporate governance and previous studies pay attention to only one aspect of diversity which is gender diversity. When diversity is concentrated only on gender, it alienates other aspects of diversity such as Experience, skills, and knowledge. Martinez-Jimenez *et al.*, (2020) argued that gender diversity does not guarantee board effectiveness. The banks used as case studies were much interested in gender diversity than other aspect of diversities as enumerated. It is understandable that gender equality is gaining ground, therefore, many banks want to portray to the stakeholders their support for gender equality by incorporating female directors in the board. However, appointing a non-qualified member based on gender, whether male or female will largely affect the effectiveness of the board and firm performance.

Therefore, this thesis recommends that the government through its institution and other relevant independent regulatory body should review the previous codes on diversity and enact

corporate governance codes that will encourage diversities base on Experience, Skill and Knowledge. It will encourage board appointment by the banks to be made irrespective of gender, ethnic or religious affiliation.

Moreover, corruption in the board was also identified as a prevailing corporate governance challenge in Nigerian commercial banks. The effect of corruption has led to unethical practices and lack of transparency in the board. Over years, commercial banks in Nigeria have been distressed which led to some of them folding up and subsequently others being bailed out by the government through bailout fund scheme. Banks that were dissolved because of insolvency have chain reaction to the economy. It affects the providers of credit, investors, customers, employees of the bank and those whom their business are in one way related to the bank. This, therefore, creates the need to put measures that will eradicate future occurrences. The excerpts of the interview revealed top directors granting loans to cronies through dubious means. Example was cited about defunct Oceanic Bank Plc, where the then CEO was found guilty of corruption and unethical practices.

The increase in corruption in banks can be traced to lack of deterrent measures put in place for those that have been found wanting. Some offenders get away with irregularities and the government readiness to bailout ailing banks in cases of eventuality keeps the issue escalating. Therefore, this study, recommends stricter measures to be employed by the government in penalising offenders. The CBN and other regulatory bodies should enact a code that heavily penalises corrupt board, especially those that their actions have resulted to bank bankruptcy. Taking such measures will serve as a deterrent to future offenders and will create sense of responsibilities among respective board members.

6.2.2 Effective Board Training and Seminars

The findings of this research shows that lack of adequate trainings, seminars, and conferences among the board of directors in Nigerian commercial banks has contributed to boards inability to implement corporate governance principles in banks. Evidence from the interview qualitative sources carried out indicated that some board members are neither updated nor abreast with the latest changes of corporate governance principles. Though most banks indicated in their annual reports that trainings were organised, but whether the training encompasses all areas of corporate governance becomes a challenge. Data collected from the interview also show that some CEOs do not know what their roles entails in the board. This happens especially where the chairman has more influence or a major shareholder of the bank. The director(s) pleases some influential shareholders who hold vital position in the board at the detriment of other shareholders and corporate governance implementation. Nevertheless, some board members have had experience in some other sectors different from financial sectors, though experienced in management, not being grounded in financial sector like bank will be a bottleneck to effectively perform their board duty and ensure corporate governance implementation. Respondents expressed the need to have technocrats across different disciplines, as it will bring networking needed in the bank for expansion. As much as networking is fantasised in Nigerian banks, however, without good management of the proceeds of the networking, the company existence might be jeopardised. Arumona (2019) have found positive relationship between financial training and effectiveness.

Consequently, this thesis recommends obligatory trainings for board members in Nigerian commercial banks, especially in the areas of corporate governance and finance. It will be essential

for board effectiveness and firm performance. Training board members in corporate governance will enhance their knowledge on how to pilot the affairs of the company. It will further create awareness in the board on their respective roles in the board. A board that is knowledgeable in the area of corporate governance will be conscious not to undermine existing codes of corporate governance and will stand his/her ground in situations where compelled to promote irregularities. The excerpts of the interview evidenced that resignation of a board member without proper reason sends negative signal to investors. One of the respondents said this on withdrawal of a board member: *...it is a time for conscience examination. Because directors who have conscience, if an organization fails to adhere to laid principles or ethical principles of corporate governance usually resign their positions. So, resignation of a director is an indication of error somewhere. It means that there are critical issues or ethical issues that the company is trying to undermine. So, directors with conscience will always decide not to be party to that. It will affect the board effectiveness because such a critical person might not suitably be replaced...*

Respondent F.

The above response is an indication that training of directors will empower them to know their rights and roles in the firm. Thus, any attempt to force any form of irregularities on them will result to their withdrawal which does not speak well of the organization. Therefore, board training will encourage proper check and balances in the banks, which will lead to board effectiveness and firm performance.

6.2.3 Remuneration Policy

The finding in this research reveals that remuneration style adopted in a bank is correlated with board effectiveness. The higher the compensation; the tendencies for higher firm performance and board effectiveness and vice versa. It was ascertained that board members in Nigerian commercial banks and other non-financial sectors are hugely motivated by the amount of compensation given to them. The board members feel inappropriately compensated when the profit made by the company is insignificant to the amount given to them in remuneration. Therefore, not being well remunerated might lead to loss of highly qualified board member and getting a replacement in the same calibre might not be easily done.

Most of the banks evaluated have similar remuneration system. The respective boards of the cases analysed have basic salaries and do give out some certain percentage of incentives when the bank's profit is higher. It was a style adopted to ensure that the best of directors is retained in the bank, so that their skills, expertise, and experiences are utilized. However, some directors are satisfied with bogus compensation given to them, therefore, they are less motivated by fund given to them, which undermines effectiveness in implementing corporate governance and ensuring firm performance.

This thesis, therefore, recommends a three-way remuneration system:

- Basic Salary if no extra profit is not made,
- Basic salary plus incentive for extra profit on targeted profit and,
- Percentage deduction on basic salary if any loss without a cogent reason like (COVID or General Economic Meltdown such as in 2006/2007).

The first system is where the board is paid the basic salary when the bank neither made loss nor significant profit. Most banks have already adopted this system, however, the definition of 'significant profit' was not properly defined. So, it will be encouraged if the banks define what entails significant profit for transparency purposes between the board, shareholders, and prospective investors. The second system recommends for bonus to be paid to directors on profits made, especially when the profits made are higher than the targeted profits. Having such principle on ground will be motivating to board members to perform. The intention of the board to maximize shareholders value will automatically results to corporate governance implementation. The third recommendation encourages certain percentage deduction in situation where there is a massive loss. Some board members are comfortable with their basic pay, therefore, they become complacent and not much motivated to work harder to ensure higher profit maximization. Awareness of salary deduction will be a source of motivation in the board to effectively carry out their monitoring, control, and strategic roles effectively well.

Below is figure 6.1, which demonstrates how remuneration of the directors enhance board effectiveness and consequently corporate governance implementation. The single aim of the three system of remuneration is to motivate the directors. Some researchers may argue that the third system of remuneration which involves deduction, will be perceived as punishment and act of compulsion. However, the researcher has stated that there should be exemptions in cases of national crisis like COVID, war or Global economic challenge.

Figure 6.1 Directors Remuneration and board effectiveness

Source: Thesis analysed data

6.2.4 Ownership and Control

Ownership structures of organisations has become a major challenge in the corporate world, whether it is concentrated, fragmented or family ownership. Despite the progress of different economies efforts through development and implementation of corporate governance codes to ensure the interest of shareholders are protected, the protection of minority investors is yet to be fully taken care of. The minority shareholders are neglected during major decisions in organisations. They are less involved in decisions like merger and acquisition of companies (Opoku-Mensah and Yin, 2021). Such decisions do undermine the aim of corporate governance in organisation.

This thesis, therefore, recommends that the regulatory bodies should be involved during major decisions in banks, especially when it concerns merger and acquisition or any activity that will

affect their holdings in the organisation. Moreover, the representation of the regulatory body should be backed by law and their duties not in any form undermining the independence of the organisation. This will help to protect the interest of all shareholders, eliminate principal-principal conflicts, and encourage more potential minority investors.

6.2.5 Conclusion

This section has effectively made recommendations based on the empirical findings of this study. The recommendations include factors that will enhance corporate governance implementation and firm performance. First, the thesis recommends that proper board training through workshop and seminars. Secondly, favourable government policies through its institution like CBN and BOFIA and ensure full compliance by the banks. Lastly, the remuneration system of the banks should be renewed to be significant to the level of performance by the respective banks.

6.3.0 Managerial Contribution

6.3.1 Contribution

There are important contributions emerging from this thesis. First, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, this is maiden empirical research of a framework likened to this study framework. The analysed frameworks of this study Levrau and Van den Berghe (2007) and Sharma (2011) have not been empirically tested. This study, therefore, is a contribution to empirical study on effective corporate governance implementation in banks.

Secondly, this research contributes to understanding of prevailing challenges of corporate governance implementation in developing economies like Nigeria where corporate governance principles are still developing. Corporate governance variables such as board diversity, board composition, leadership duality and board size were examined to know the extent of implementation. Besides, this is the first research to examine shareholders perception on corporate governance implementation in Nigerian commercial banks.

On the third note, this study will be pertinent, especially when it comes to effective ways to ensure corporate governance implementation in Nigeria. Adegbite (2015) have noted how weak environment has contributed to corporate governance implementation in developing markets like Nigeria.

Lastly, this research will be useful to shareholders, board of directors and government institution like Central Banks and other regulatory body on the best way to ensure corporate governance principles are effectively implemented in Commercial banks. If the recommendations of this thesis are utilised, the principals (shareholders), will know the best way to remunerate the board to be motivated in implementing corporate governance. Besides that, the board through trainings will understand all that corporate governance entails, and regulatory institutions understanding better on how to get the respective banks and all other firms on how to properly implement corporate governance codes. The prospective foreign investors will utilize the outcome of this study to evaluate their targeted firms to ensure the extent they have progress in implementation of corporate governance which results to board effectiveness.

6.4 Conceptual Model

This section presents the conceptual model of the thesis. The conceptual framework of this study was drawn from the numerous analysed literature review. It encompasses the factors that undermined the implementation of corporate governance in commercial banks. The frameworks of Sharma (2011) and Levrau and Van den Berghe (2007) were adopted, which examined factors that underpins board effectiveness. Despite the framework being developed from the review of literature, the analysed mitigated changes in the framework. The figure 6.2 below shows how data analysed contributed to imminent change in the conceptual framework. The ownership structure can be categorised into concentrated and disperse ownership. The diagram indicated that ownership structure can be undermine either undermine or underpin corporate governance implementation and board effectiveness. The findings in the analysis noted that when ownership is concentrated, the few owners determine what happens in the board, however, the board are more independent in a dispersed ownership structure.

Figure 6.2 Conceptual model

6.5 Limitation of Study

Some limitations were encountered in the cause of carrying out this study. First, considering the busy and close nature of Nigerian banks, the researcher was unable to interview as much respondents as he wanted. Some of the persons contacted during this study never got back to the researcher, thus, making the number of respondents relatively low. Higher participation is likely to yield a more elaborate result.

Secondly, some of the questions asked to some respondents were not answered. It was deduced that some of the respondents who are in managerial positions in a bank are scared of not being kept anonymous. They complained that some who engaged in such interviews in the past were penalised. Therefore, lack of trust limited the amount of information that the researcher could gather.

Thirdly, time was a limiting factor in carrying out this study. Traveling to Nigeria to get the interview was very challenging. Some managers who gave appointments also disappointed. Considering the limited time within Nigerian, it undermined the number of interviews to have been conducted.

Fourthly, the framework of this research employed limited number of corporate governance variables to ascertain challenges, effect, and procedures to ensure corporate governance theories. The review of related literature has also identified other processes of ensuring board effectiveness which mitigates corporate governance implementation. For example, Sharma (2011) model on need for Information Technology (IT) in ensuring board effectiveness.

Lastly, this thesis narrowed its data collection to semi-structured interview only. Using other data collection tool or combination of both would likely produce a better result.

6.6 Recommendations for Future Research

Corporate governance principle is yet to get the desired attention needed in the Nigeria environment as poor and weak system has undermined its effectiveness (Adegbite 2015). Therefore, there are scopes to be researched on when it comes to Nigerian corporate governance.

First, this research considered only banks in the top-tier group, which are authorised to operate locally and internationally. This, therefore, necessitated the need to carry out similar research in the second-tier group of banks, that is banks licensed to operate locally with international authorisation. However, a comparative study can as well be carried to know if the first tier rated banks and second tier rated banks face similar challenges in implementing corporate governance in their respective banks. Such study will be vital for encompassing regulatory body policies in re-examining suitability of existing codes and needs for inclusion or adjustments.

Second, it was observed that there is a lack of investment literacy among the public on Nigerian commercial banks. Research that will recommend avenue to educate the shareholders on corporate governance principle will be vital. When shareholders (including minority) are aware of what is expected of the board, especially when it comes to corporate governance, it will enhance board effectiveness, and minimize firm collapse. One of the possible ways to educate the shareholders, might be to post leaflets containing corporate governance codes and what is expected from the board.

Third, the ownership structure has been found to have effect on the quality of the board and corporate governance implementation. Respondents of the interview expressed that in a situation where there is concentrated ownership, it is less likely to have effective board or proper implementation of corporate governance coded. The reasons being the likelihood of the major shareholders appointing their cronies as directors and undermining their independent opinions. Therefore, empirical research needs to be carried out in Nigerian commercial banks, comparing performance of banks dispersedly owned and banks with concentrated ownership. Moreover, the level corporate governance implementation in disperse ownership and concentrated ownership can be compared.

6.7 Conclusion

This is the concluding part of this DBA thesis. Empirical studies that have been carried out on Corporate Governance focused more on firm performance resulting from board effectiveness. The board are hugely blamed for lack of performance in firms, however, not many empirical studies have examined prevailing factors that undermine board effectiveness especially in emerging markets like Africa. This research examined prevailing challenges that hampers corporate governance implementation in Nigerian commercial banks, the effect of these challenges and the best ways to eradicate the prevailing corporate governance challenges.

In addition, board training, adequate remuneration and great policies from regulatory bodies such as the Central Banks will enhance corporate governance implementation in banks especially in environment where corporate governance is still developing. Therefore, board's ability to

implement corporate governance in banks and other organisations will result to company performance.

Finally, the researcher is firmly convinced that the findings and the theoretical framework of this thesis will invigorate researchers of corporate governance, organisational strategy and any other organisation, to examine possible challenges facing the board effectiveness in different sectors of the economy and possible ways to eradicate them. Carrying out such study will be imperative in improving corporate governance in emerging markets like Nigeria. The findings of this thesis are vital to nexus of stakeholders which include the Shareholders, directors, managements, regulatory bodies, and government.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. Sample of Interview Questions

1. In your opinion, what might be the general issue surrounding corporate governance in Nigerian commercial banks?
2. Reasons why Nigerian banks are yet to holistically implement CG in the system?
3. Why Lack of diversity in banks?
4. To what extent do you think that lack of board diversity might affect board effectiveness in implementing corporate governance principles?
5. To what extent does separation of role of chairman and Chief Executive Officer fit in into the Nigerian environment?
6. What do you think about multiple board representation by a directorship?
7. Does voluntary withdrawal of a director decrease the share value of your bank?
8. In what ways can the board be educated, informed, 14and encouraged on the importance of implementing corporate governance codes?
9. In your opinion, how can these two individuals be empowered to bring transparency in the board (Chairman and CEO)?
10. What do you think are the necessary step to enhance board effectiveness towards checkmating financial reporting by the management?
11. The issue of CEO compensation has triggered dichotomy of opinion across companies. In your own opinion, what could the best way to set directors remuneration?
12. How has religion contributed to implementation of corporate governance in Nigeria?
13. What do you think about government bailout on stressed banks, which might undermine corporate board effectiveness?
14. To what extent can a government representative in the board bring about corporate board effectiveness?
15. In what ways can government ensure proper implementation of codes of corporate governance in Nigerian commercial banks?
16. To what extent do you think combination of rule base and principle base will be efficient in implementation of corporate governance?
17. In what ways can pension funds contribute to enhancing board effectiveness?
18. How can different shareholders align their different interest to make the board of directors effective?

Appendix 2. Sample of sent letter

From: Casmir C. Eze

Subject: Informed Consent to Participate in Study

18th April 2019

Dear Sir/Madam,

RESEARCH ON SHAREHOLDERS PERCEPTION ON CORPORATE GOVERNANCE IMPLEMENTATION
IN NIGERIAN BANKS

With an utmost gratitude, it would be enormously appreciated if you could spare a bit of your busy schedules to participate in the above research work which is substantially paramount to Shareholders of banks operating in Nigeria.

This is a research project being carried out by Casmir Eze of University of The West of Scotland (UWS), United Kingdom, as part of his DBA (Doctor of Business Administration) programme. I am researching on the Shareholders Perception on Corporate Governance Implementation in Nigerian commercial banks. To be precise, I intend to achieve the following objectives: (1) To ascertain the prevailing issues undermining corporate governance implementation in Nigerian banks; (2) what are the effects of non-implementation of corporate governance in Nigerian banks; (3) And the best way to ensure that the identified issues are amended and implemented.

At the end of this research, it will greatly contribute to the body of knowledge on panacea to the challenges facing corporate governance implementation in Banks across emerging markets like Nigeria. Moreover, this research will considerably be important to diverse existing shareholders

and prospective investors dealing with Nigerian banks. As it tends to create sustainability and fix corporate governance issues that have negatively affected effective operation of banks, thereby undermining their performance.

Your willingness to participate in this interview is highly appreciated and participation is voluntary. All the questions asked in the interview is to holistically achieve the research aim and objectives. However, you reserve the right to turn down any question for any personal reasons. The interview will approximately last between an hour (more or less).

It might interest you to know that the interview will be tape-recorded, and notes taken during the process. To achieve high level of confidentiality and data protection, the transcribed interview will be safely stored in a passworded computer to avoid intrusion. The identity of the interviewees and organizations will be coded as to keep them anonymous.

Moreover, the excerpts of the interview may be incorporate in the final dissertation report or further publications. In no situation will your name or any characteristics that will reveal your identity will be in any publications. However, at any circumstance your biographical data is relevant, another separate release form would be served to you for your consent.

I will immensely appreciate if you would append your signature on the line provided below. This is to show you have read, understood, and agreed with the contents.

Your signature above

Thank you in advance for your support

Yours Sincerely,

Casmir C. Eze

University of the West of Scotland

Appendix 3. Example of coding process using Respondent A

S/N	Respondent	Question and Response	code
1	<p>Researcher</p> <p>Respondent A</p> <p>Respondent D</p>	<p>Nigerian commercial banks?</p> <p>The major issues surrounding CG in Nigerians banks includes,1) lack of transparency 2) misappropriation of funds 3) unethical practices in banks 4) diversion of companies fund to unofficial use.</p> <p>Generally, I tend to see it that it is a class (social status) issue and societal expectation issue. In as much as issue of pushing on to make profit is the aim of banking industry, many of the owners want to belong to certain class and that have led them to compromising. The compromise includes lack of full implementation of things (bank guidelines), lay down rules as expected in corporate governance. Such that those compromise creates room for their personal gains or group gains. So, greed and way of life is affecting corporate governance implementation because the directors or the owners of banks priorities their personal gains over the companies gain.</p>	<p>1) Leadership issues 2) Corruption</p> <p>Ownership issue</p>
2	<p>Researcher</p> <p>Respondent A</p> <p>Probe:</p> <p>Respondent A</p>	<p>What are the reasons why Nigerian banks are yet to holistically implement CG in the system?</p> <p>Banking industries a highly regulated however, lack of enforcement is undermining CG.</p> <p>Any penalty for defaulters of the corporate governance codes?</p> <p>Regulators like CBN and NDIC determines penalty and make sure banks operate within the stipulated guidelines. Lack adherence is resulted by poor implementation by these regulators?</p> <p>Regulators like CBN and NDIC determines penalty and make sure banks operate within the stipulated guidelines. Lack adherence is resulted by poor implementation by these regulators</p>	<p>Lack of enforcement</p> <p>Implementation challenges</p>
3	<p>Researcher</p> <p>Respondent A</p> <p>Probe</p> <p>Respondent A</p>	<p>Why Lack of diversity in banks?</p> <p>Lack of following diversities have undermined board effectiveness in Nigerian banks to great extent; 1) gender diversity 2) experience diversity 3) career diversity. They should be people with integrity. Having people from different career background (such as lawyers, bankers, engineers' accountants, economists, and other professionals) adds credibility to what the body (BOD) are doing. Diversity is very important and plays massive roles in board effectiveness.</p> <p>Do you think there should be more emphasis on gender diversity?</p> <p>Gender is important, but diversity should not only be based on gender, but experience and career background should be massively considered.</p>	<p>Board composition</p> <p>Encompassing diversity</p>
4	<p>Researcher</p> <p>Respondent A</p>	<p>To what extent do you think that lack of board diversity might affect board effectiveness in implementing corporate governance principles?</p> <p>A well-diversified board underpin the implementation of CG and vice versa. A balance board with diversified gender, expertise, experience is great for CG effectiveness. Therefore, lack of diversity limits corporate board effectiveness.</p>	<p>Well diversified board</p>
5	<p>Researcher</p>	<p>To what extent does separation of role of chairman and Chief Executive Officer fit in into the Nigerian environment?</p> <p>It is good for Nigerian environment, and it is contemporary in Nigerian banking sector. Prior before introduction of separation of roles of CEO</p>	

	Respondent A	and Chairman, the respective roles are being carried out by one person known as Chairman-Chief executive. Generally, it did not go well with Nigerian bank industry when one person was handling both posts. It is now a compulsory that both roles must be separated which was legislated by both government and CBN. Problem of concentrating both roles is corruption (absolute power corrupts absolutely). Advantages of separation includes, check and balances, creates oversight of the board over the CEO and it enhances the effectiveness of corporate governance implementation.	Board composition
6	Researcher Respondent A	What do you think about multiple board representation by a directorship? There is law limiting multiple board directorship in Nigeria. I think you can only be a director in not more than two or three banks. Assuming you are a director and not performing greatly, it will affect other banks you are a director in, which is not good for the industry. if you are effective, it will be great to work within the stipulated number of banks you can be a director in, to avoid undermining your strength and create space for other vibrant people to work in vacant directorship post.	Work limit
7	Researcher Respondent A	Does voluntary withdrawal of a director decrease the share value of your bank? It does not have any negative impact because he/she (director) will not withdraw his shareholding. Unless there are fundamental issues of health of the bank that caused withdrawal of the director which might cause panic in the bank.	Directors Withdrawal effect
8	Researcher Respondent A	In what ways can the board be educated, informed, and encouraged on the importance of implementing corporate governance codes? First, the members of the board should be knowledgeable in their areas of expertise (accountants, networking, banking, engineering, etc.). More training in their academic background and orientations should be given. The directors should be compelled to attend trainings as scheduled and should personally expose themselves to the prevailing issues in the areas of banking and CG. They should be passionate about their jobs as well.	Board Trainings
9	Researcher Respondent A	In your opinion, how can these two individuals be empowered to bring transparency in the board (Chairman and CEO)? Training is very important to members of board and management. This will enlighten them of what is expected of them and roles they must play in corporate business. So, these positions should be occupied by those who have been trained in that capacity. Training is very important, exposure is important. The regulators (CBN and NDIC) should perform the roles of educating these people (CEO and Chairman) on their distinguished roles in banks. Training, exposure and enforcement of CG are important in this circumstance.	Board Training and capability
10	Researcher Respondent A Probe	What do you think are the necessary step to enhance board effectiveness towards checkmating financial reporting by the management? The board should be highly objective, transparency and insist on accountability in the activities of the bank. And when there is low profit, they should recognize and accept it that way. However, the mitigating factors of low profit should be investigated as well. The board should do what is right and not just reporting what the shareholders want to hear. That's being prudent. Window dressing and inflating the profits to pay high dividends should be avoided by the management. What if they inflate the financial reporting to keep their job?	Ethics and objectivity

	Respondent A	The audit committee should always review the financial reports by the management alongside the external auditor. This will bring proper check and balances in the organization.	Board Financial review
11	Researcher Respondent A	The issue of CEO compensation has triggered dichotomy of opinion across companies. In your own opinion, what could the best way to set directors remuneration? The responsibilities of the board should be quantified, how often they sit (time), qualifications and the experiences they have got. They should be well remunerated in relation to the work they do. The general profit made by the bank should be a determining factor in setting their remuneration.	Performance based remuneration
12	Researcher Respondent A	How has religion contributed to implementation of corporate governance in Nigeria? Religion preaches ethics, moral, rights and wrongs. Most religions teach adherence of law and avoid ills. Therefore, religion has contributed to CG implementation in Nigeria. People who adhere to the teachings of their religion will always do what is right	Ethical behavior
13	Researcher Respondent A	19. What do you think about government bailout on stressed banks, which might undermine corporate board effectiveness? The main aim of bailout funds by government is to ensure banks do not fail if they are distressed. It's necessary and it is done all over the world. It (bailout) should be a loan a bank should pay after recovering so that directors will avoid being stressed knowing they will be indebted to the government (CBN). The CBN should monitor the bailout funds to avoid the board embezzling such relief fund. The need for bailout funds is an indication of poor corporate governance in the board. which means board haven't done what they are ought to have done. Bailout is there to ensure employment is not lost and depositors money are safe. To ensure effective corporate governance, new directors should be employed to fill the corporate governance gaps which resulted to banks being stressed.	Bailout/distress Board Leadership challenge
14	Researcher Respondent A	1. To what extent can a government representative in the board bring about corporate board effectiveness? It can only be effective if the govt representative is qualified and experienced in the business of the bank. They can bring positive effectiveness in the board.	Capable representation
15	Researcher Respondent A	In what ways can government ensure proper implementation of codes of corporate governance in Nigerian commercial banks? By ensuring good governance in the country (i.e., in all areas of state affairs). The government should have political will to what is right and should lead by example for others to follow. They should be apolitical in dealing with financial issues and implementation of the corporate governance codes and principles. The government should eradicate corruption in the system and avoid nepotism in the attending to issues. The government should do the right thing, so that other institution will emulate them.	Ethical implementation
16	Researcher Respondent A	To what extent do you think combination of rule base and principal base will be efficient in implementation of corporate governance? The combination of rule and principle base CG is vital in corporate board effectiveness. The rule serves as a must, which means an obligation while the principle deals with ethics, the combination of the two will greatly enhance corporate board effectiveness	Ethics and obligation
17	Researcher	In what ways can pension funds contribute to enhancing board effectiveness?	Company's Stability

	Respondent A	They bring stability to the banks board considering the volatile nature of their investments in banks.	
18	Researcher	How can different shareholders align their different interest to make the board of directors effective?	Shareholders Selfless interest
	Respondent A	The board should care for all the different shareholders and all other stakeholders. Different shareholders should not overemphasis their selfish interest but should focus on what will enhance the profitability of the company in general. The major concern of all the shareholders should be, is the board doing the right thing? This will be achievable by everyone putting behind their respective interest to the interest of the entire shareholders (major and minority shareholders). So, the interest of all concerned should be considered.	

Appendix 4. Coded words

Coded words from Respondent A
1) Leadership issues
2) Corruption
3) Implementation challenges
4) Board composition
5) Lack of enforcement
6) Encompassing diversity
7) Well diversified board
8) Work limit
9) Directors Withdrawal effect
10) Board Trainings
11) Board Training and capability
12) Ethics and objectivity
13) Board Financial review
14) Performance based remuneration
15) Ethical behavior
16) Bailout/distress
17) Board Leadership challenge
18) Capable representation
19) Ethical implementation
20) Ethics and obligation
21) Ethics and obligation
22) company's Stability
23) Shareholders Selfless interest
24) Ownership Issue

Appendix 5. Thesis Themes

Themes					
Board Structure and Leadership issues	Shareholder's interest	Ownership structure	Bank distress and Bailout fund	Multiple board representation	Effective Corporate Governance
Leadership issues	Shareholders Selfless interest	Ownership Issue	Directors Withdrawal effect	Work limit	Implementation challenges
Corruption			Bailout/distress		Lack of enforcement
Well diversified board					Board Trainings
Ethics and objectivity					Board Training and capability
Board Financial review					Ethical implementation
Ethical behavior					
Board Leadership challenge					